

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Deliverable 5.3

Report on AOPs

WP5 – T5.3 / WP6 – T6.1

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Responsible author(s)	<p>Project leaders: Birgit Mertens/Sciensano/Birgit.Mertens@sciensano.be Karine Audouze/INSERM/karine.audouze@u-paris.fr</p> <p>Group leaders that coordinated the additional deliverable: SG1, immunotoxicity: Birgitte Lindeman/FHI/Birgitte.Lindeman@fhi.no, Johanna Gostner/MUI/Johanna.gostner@i-med.ac.at SG2, endocrine and metabolic disruption: Dries Knapen/UAntwerpen/dries.knapen@uantwerpen.be, Henrik Holbech/SDU/hol@biology.sdu.dk SG3, neurotoxicity: Oddvar Myrhe/NIPH/Oddvar.Myrhe@fhi.no, Antonis Stratidakis/AUTh/antonios.stratidakis@iusspavia.it, Barbara Viviani/UMIL/barbara.viviani@unimi.it EMG, effect markers: Eva Cecilia Bonefeld-Joergensen/AUPH/ebj@ph.au.dk, Adelheid Soubry/KU Leuven/adelheid.soubry@kuleuven.be, Manhai Long/AUPH/ml@ph.au.dk, Maria Wielsoe/AU/mwielsoe@ph.au.dk AOPs developed in task 6.1 to support IATAs design Birgit Mertens/Sciensano/Birgit.Mertens@sciensano.be</p>
Co-authors	/
Internal Reviewers ²	Gilles Rivière/Anses/ gilles.riviere@anses.fr Philip Marx-Stoelting/BfR/ Philip.Marx-Stoelting@bfr.bund.de
External Reviewers ³	Sharon Munn/JRC/ Sharon.MUNN@ec.europa.eu John Colbourne /UoB/ j.k.colbourne@bham.ac.uk
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¹ PU = Public

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Abstract

AOP development will be focused during the first 4 years of PARC on the selected priority outcomes related to immunotoxicity, non-genotoxic carcinogenesis, endocrine disruption, metabolic disruption and neurotoxicity. Different specialty groups have first identified the available AOPs and knowledge gaps for each endpoint, and, based on this information, initiated their works to develop new or complete existing AOPs. These specialty groups (SG) include Specialty Group 1 (SG1) focusing on immunotoxicology and non-genotoxic carcinogenesis, Specialty Group 2 (SG2) working on endocrine disruption and metabolic disruption, and Specialty Group 3 (SG3) addressing neurotoxicology. Two additional groups have been created: one core group (CG) that deals with data and available tools for AOP development and another group involved in the identification of putative effect markers based on available AOPs (Effect Markers Group, EMG). It should be noted that the priority outcomes are similar to those of Task 5.2 (NAMs development) and they have been selected because of their regulatory and health outcome relevance. In addition, work on AOPs for genotoxicity and specific target organ toxicity (STOT) is also ongoing in Task 6.1 of PARC to support IATA development.

This deliverable gives an overview of the AOPs that are being developed as part of Project 5.3.2a (AOP development) and Task 6.1 (IATAs development), their development status, and follow up actions for regulatory acceptance of those AOPs. In addition, an update on the work of the EMG is provided.

Key Words

AOP, IATA, Mode of action, biomarkers, endocrine disruptors, neurotoxicity, immunotoxicity, metabolic disruption, genotoxicity, specific target organ toxicity, non-genotoxic carcinogenesis

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Authors and Acknowledgements

The Task 5.3.2.a co-leaders would like to thank all 5.3.2.a and 6.1 partners for their contribution (details in the Annex section).

Acronyms

ANT: Adult neurotoxicity
 AOP: Adverse outcome pathway
 DNT: Developmental neurotoxicity
 IATA : Integrated approach to testing and assessment
 KE : Key event
 MIE: Molecular initiating event
 NAM: new approach methodology
 NGTxC: Non-genotoxic carcinogen
 STOT : Specific target organ toxicity
 THSD: Thyroid hormone system disruption

1. Background

New approach methodologies (NAMs) provide a large variety and volume of data that are very challenging - if not impossible - to implement in regulatory applications or mechanistic toxicology unless they are integrated and represented in a useful and widely accepted framework. Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) are very helpful tools to structure the information generated by NAMs as they describe the causal relationships between molecular initiating events (MIEs), subsequent key events (KEs) at different biological levels of organisation and ultimately adverse outcomes (AOs). They are developed by integrating and connecting data from various sources i.e. databases and scientific literature, in a logical sequence of causally-linked events.

However, at present, AOPs for important regulatory endpoints are lacking or insufficiently developed. Therefore, in WP5 of PARC, we aim to tackle this regulatory challenge by developing comprehensive AOPs that cover mechanisms underlying regulatory relevant AOs for the selected priorities: immunotoxicity, neurotoxicity, non-genotoxic carcinogenesis, endocrine disruption and metabolic disruption. As a first step, available AOPs (if any) and gaps in knowledge have been identified, and based on this information, priorities have been set for (further) development of the AOPs related to these outcomes using transparent and consistent methodologies and following the FAIR data principles (in connection with WP7.2).

It should be noted that the same endpoints have been prioritized for NAM development in WP5. By providing a framework for the use of these new as well as existing NAMs and/or for the later design of integrated approaches to testing and assessment (IATA) for high-priority endpoints, the AOP development will have an impact on different regulations including REACH and CLP, plant protection products and biocides, cosmetic products and food (food additives, food contaminants and food contact materials).

The work is conducted by several specialty groups (SGs) including Specialty Group 1 (SG1; immunotoxicology, non-genotoxic carcinogenesis), Specialty Group 2 (SG2; endocrine disruption and metabolic disruption) and Specialty Group 3 (SG3; neurotoxicology). In addition, there is a group that focuses on methodologies and tools for AOP development –(Core Group, CG) and another group that identifies putative effect markers based on available AOPs (Effect Markers Group, EMG).

The different activities of the groups are the following:

1. Core Group activities. These are based on partners' expertise in bioinformatics and systems biology, participation in AOP development and capacities to contribute to this task. The CG has organized a workshop and has initiated a publication in collaboration with the three SG (Front. Toxicol., 08 March 2024 Sec. Regulatory Toxicology, Volume 6 - 2024 | <https://doi.org/10.3389/ftox.2024.1285768>).
2. Specialty Groups (SG) activities. The activities of the SGs focus on the priority outcomes of Task 5.3 for the first 3 years and take into consideration human health and ecotoxicological aspects. The SGs all work closely together with similar groups in subtasks 5.3.1 and 5.3.3. The following SGs have been constituted and contributed to the present deliverable:
 - *Immunotoxicology and non-Genotoxic carcinogenesis*. AOPs are available in some areas (skin sensitization) but are either incomplete or lacking in several areas. In line with EU agencies priorities and 5.2 activities, this SG focuses for the first three years on:

1. Respiratory sensitisation;
 2. Immunosuppression (e.g. response to vaccination and infection);
 3. Role of inflammation and cell migration in NGTxC.
 2. *Endocrine and metabolic disruption.* While several AOPs are available, there are no or few AOPs for some important outcomes (metabolic disorders like diabetes and obesity, thyroid-related outcomes). Therefore, the work of this SG includes:
 - Metabolic outcomes: focus on diabetes /insulin resistance and obesity (no or few AOPs available).
 - Thyroid hormone axis effects: cover outcomes other than those affecting the thyroid gland itself and identify additional MIEs, KEs and AOs.
 - Endocrine receptors: broaden the spectrum of current priority receptors to include additional receptors and mediators such as PPARs and Glucocorticoid Receptor, Mineralocorticoid Receptor (MR), Aryl hydrocarbon Receptor (AhR), Retinoic acid Receptor (RAR), Ecdysone Receptor (EcR), mTOR, etc.
 - Epigenetic mechanisms will be investigated in particular for metabolic diseases and obesity.
 3. *Neurotoxicity.* There are AOPs available or in progress on neurodegeneration and on developmental neurotoxicity. Yet, there is a need for additional AOPs to cover the wide spectrum of outcomes. The SG covers:
 - Neurodegeneration including ageing effects. This includes confirming individual available adverse outcome and developing new ones following a top-down approach.
 - Neurodevelopment (DNT) in collaboration with the endocrine disruption group.
 4. *Effect markers.* This group develops effect markers based on AOPs that are developed in 5.3 or recently developed AOPs in the priority fields described above. The activities are carried out in close collaboration with WP4 (4.1.3) which aim to investigate effect markers in humans, adapt analytical methods and in some cases identify new effect markers that are particularly relevant for a class of chemicals.
- Moreover, in WP6 of PARC, a mapping exercise on the availability and maturity (i.e. the level of completeness) of existing AOPs is done to support IATA development for selected endpoints:
- IATA-ED focuses on AOPs related on the thyroid hormone system disruption (THSD) and anti-androgenic adverse effects;
 - IATA-Gentox identifies AOPs related to increases in gene mutations and chromosomal damage;
 - IATA-STOT initially focuses on liver toxicity, more specifically liver fibrosis.

2. AOPs developed in WP5/6

2.1 development status of AOPs

AOPs developed in Project 5.3.2a and Task 6.1 are described below, along with their stage of development (preparatory work in progress/ partially developed/ AOP submitted to the AOP-Wiki database).

Priority description	By which SG/working group?	Why is this a priority?	How will it be addressed?	Development status (preparatory work in progress/AOP partially developed/AOP submitted to the AOP-Wiki database)	comments
SG1 immunotoxicity and NGTxC					
Further develop the AOP 474: Succinate dehydrogenase inactivation leading to cancer	SG1 NGTxC	AOP included in the OECD work plan	Characterisation of KEs and KERs through literature study including alterations in succinate levels, in oxidative phosphorylation, and activation of pseudohypoxia and epithelial mesenchymal transition. The choice of KEs will be finalized within 2 months. Three scientists from Inserm will then work in parallel on a shared document to complete the information on KEs and KERs. AOP-Wiki will then be completed	Preparatory work in progress	Further development and structuring of the AOP 474 is ongoing, including selection of KEs & KERs. A review of SDH inhibitors has been published (DOI: 10.1016/j.envint.2023.108219) S. Bortoli and X. Coumoul also participate to the 5.2.1.a NGTxC project.

Focus on pathways leading to cancer metastasis: role of the AhR receptor and subsequent key events	SG1 NGTxC	Included in OECD AOP work plan; needs to be completed	Literature study and current additional work done in Inserm laboratories	Preparatory work in progress	Literature search on AhR and its role in metastasis is ongoing. AOP439 "Activation of the AhR leading to breast cancer" in final stage preparing for external review.
Explore missing MIEs and/or KEs for immunosuppression	SG1 (Immunosuppression)	Only four AOPs for immunosuppression are currently included in the AOP-Wiki. Based on initial analysis (AOP-helpFinder search + data on immunosuppressive drugs), data on several additional MIEs/KEs exists that may be useful for identification of immunosuppressants.	Text and database mining will be used to expand on the existing AON	Preparatory work in progress	Focus on AOP14 (glucocorticoid receptor activation leading to immunosuppression) using textmining (case study utilising AOPbot being developed in WP7.3) and comparison with more conventional literature search. This is part of a master thesis, focused on effects on Tcell of glucocorticoids (to be delivered in May 2024)

<p>Explore AOP 39 and additional MIEs or KEs from other AOPs in AOP-Wiki that may support the identification of respiratory sensitizers</p>	<p>SG1 (Resp.Sens.Group)</p>	<p>The OECD status of AOP 39 is under development. The applicability domain excludes transition metal complexes. Initial exploratory analysis suggests that other MIEs and KEs may be helpful in sensitizer identification.</p>	<p>Text mining, bioinformatics, and literature study to identify biologically plausible MIEs/KEs to expand the existing AOP network.</p>	<p>Preparatory work in progress</p>	<p>AOP 39 shares similarities with the skin sensitization AOP no. 40, as both trace the pathway from the binding of chemicals to proteins, through dendritic cell and T cell activation leading to the respective adverse outcome. We provide suggestions to include additional relevant KEs to extend AOP 39, such as loss of barrier function, recruitment of inflammatory cells, activation of T helper type 2 cells and B cells, and degranulation of mast cells. Similar KEs to these newly suggested KEs can be found already in AOP-Wiki included in different AOPs: these KEs should be further developed and connected to AOP 39, others should be newly created. The AOP work is a collaboration with WP5.2 due to complementary interests.</p>
<p>SG2 Endocrine and metabolic disruption</p>					

Develop paths leading to insulin resistance/obesity/type 2 diabetes	SG2 Metabolic disruption	No existing AOPs related to these AOs, hallmarks of metabolic syndrome which could concern several pathologies and target tissues. (relevance to human health) were identified in the AOP-Wiki database.	Text mining, bioinformatics, and literature study to identify biologically plausible MIEs/KEs.	AOP partially developed	Two AOPs (AOPs 493 and 497) were designed and deposited on AOP-Wiki. In Y4 KEs and KERs will be completed. Preparatory work on AOP with other MIEs on obesity/insulin resistance by analysis of literature
Development of an AOP describing perturbation of androgen receptor activity leading to reduced fetal growth.	SG2 (anti-)androgen	There is no AOP describing an (anti)-androgenic mechanism leading to reduced fetal growth. This AOP would be relevant for IATA development as well as for biomarker identification. (relevance to human and environmental health)	Scoping review of evidence for increased and decreased AR activation leading to reduced fetal growth, followed by postulation of an AOP.	Preparatory work in progress	Working on optimising the literature search. Planned start May 2024.

Development of an AOP for Androgen receptor agonism leading to reproductive dysfunction (in annual-spawning fish)	SG2 (anti-)androgen	Available AOPs are only applicable to continuously spawning fish. Since most fish spawn annually, it is important to expand the applicability domain to include the vast majority of fish species. (relevance to environmental health)	Literature study focusing on the first KE and KER following AR agonism. AOP 23 is available for continuously spawning fish but it is anticipated that the first KE and KER will be different for annual spawners.	Preparatory work in progress	Preparatory work in advanced stage including a license for animal experiment. Due to start in April 2024. We anticipate that this work will expand the scope of AOP23 and identify KEs and KERs when the feedback loop is positive.
Exploring molecular mechanism of a crosstalk between estrogen and AhR signaling pathways leading to immunosuppression	SG2 (anti-)estrogen	Interactions between estrogen and AhR-mediated pathways are thought to play an important role mediating immunosuppressive effects of biological and chemical stressors but are not yet well understood. Developing this in the AOP framework will help organize current knowledge. This activity will also feed into AOP-development in Task 5.3.2 SG1. (relevance to human and environmental health)	Literature review focusing on MIEs and early KEs describing the interaction between estrogen and AhR-mediated pathways leading to immunosuppression.	Preparatory work in progress.	Refining the literature search to align with the AOP focus. Analysis of literature search to identify crucial KEs is ongoing.

Develop MIE MCT8 inhibition	SG2 THSD	An assay for MCT8 inhibition was included in the current JRC-EU-NETVAL validation study. However, a respective MIE is missing in the thyroid hormone system disruption (THSD) AOP network. This has been highlighted as a priority by Task 6.1.1.b IATA-ED. (relevance to human and environmental health)	Literature study in mammals and fish to develop MIE and link it to downstream event with a new KER.	Preparatory work in progress.	Scoping of literature to determine Domain of Applicability (DOA) almost finished, including determination of which TH transporters, species, sex, life-stages, tissues, etc. to consider. Offline development of KE page (MIE) for MCT8 inhibition using T5.3.2. AOP-Wiki templates initiated. Finish KE page in AOP-Wiki as next step, including exploring evidence to link MIE to (new) downstream KEs/KERs of the existing THSD AOP network in the AOP-Wiki.
Develop paths leading to AOs (e.g. impairment of motor activity and/or social responses or other behavioural endpoints) via hypothalamus disruption	SG2 THSD	So far, the AOPs covering the link between THSD and effects on neural function mainly consider hippocampus as target organ. However, other brain areas are known to be affected by THSD. (relevance to human health)	Literature study to identify biologically plausible KEs/AOs to expand the existing AOP network.	Preparatory work in progress	Literature search of adverse effects observed in hypothalamus and linked to THSD: first screening of the literature almost finished. Risk of Bias assessment and identification of AOs from eligible full text papers as next steps.

Develop sex applicability domain descriptions in the THSD AOPN	SG2 THSD	Better description of the sex applicability domain for those AOPs lacking descriptions or not specifying potential sex-differences will support their regulatory relevance for gender-tailored policies/recommendations. This has been highlighted as a priority by Task 6.1.1.b IATA-ED. (relevance to human and environmental health)	Literature study to identify biologically plausible sex-, gender-specific effects.	Preparatory work in progress	Ranking of the AOPs included in the network according to the endorsement/development status and "Sex applicability domain" filling; literature search, improvement and filling of the SAD as next steps.
Investigate whether KEs and KERs linking THSD to DNT in mammals are also applicable to fish	SG2 THSD / SG3 DNT	Assessing whether KEs and KERs in the THSD AOPN leading to DNT are applicable to fish will support the development of both human and ecotoxicological IATAs for THSD in Task 6.1.1.b IATA-ED. (relevance to human and environmental health)	KEs and KERs included in AOPs linking THSD to DNT in mammals (e.g., in AOPs 54, 42) will be selected for investigation of their applicability to fish based on a literature review.	Preparatory work in progress	Scoping effort based on literature and available information in the AOP-Wiki. Limited data availability for KEs leading to DNT in fish in the THSD-AOP network identified as potential issue. Scope of this priority broadened to any THSD-DNT effects in fish. This priority is linked with priority "Develop MIE MCT8 inhibition" and is shared with SG3. Development of search strings for systematic literature review and evaluation of available evidence as next steps.

<p>Implement taxonomic domain of applicability study results from ERGO (EURION) in AOP-Wiki</p>	<p>SG2 THSD</p>	<p>In order to build on this ERGO effort in PARC, it is a priority to transfer the outcomes of this study to the AOP-Wiki. This will support the development of human and ecotoxicological IATAs for THSD in T6.1.1.b IATA-ED. (relevance to human and environmental health)</p>	<p>Transfer knowledge on the taxonomic domain of applicability of MIEs and AOs in the THSD AOPN that is currently collected in a review to the AOP-Wiki. In the context of AOP-Wiki 3.0 development, this will require some adaptation of the way the findings are presented so they fit the structure of the AOP-Wiki.</p>	<p>AOP partially developed</p>	<p>Study results on Taxonomic Domain of Applicability (tDOA) of MIEs and AOs in THSD AOP network (ERGO) published (Haigis AC et al., 2023; doi: 10.1093/toxsci/kfad063). Challenge to adapt structure of MIE and AO findings to AOP-Wiki structure lies in the fact that conceptual non-adjacent KERs currently do not exist in the AOP-Wiki. Joint effort with the SAAOP ongoing to improve, amongst others, this aspect by using for example umbrella KEs. Dependency on development of AOP-Wiki version 3.0 features and capabilities for development of an implementation strategy.</p>
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Explore linkages between THSD and metabolic disruption with human relevance	SG2 THSD / SG2 Metabolic disruption	This has been highlighted by T6.1.1.b IATA-ED as a knowledge gap and could support the IATAs being developed on THSD. Additionally, there could be links to the SG2 activity on metabolic disruption, which could facilitate AOPN development. (relevance to human health)	A literature search will be conducted to integrate evidence of causal associations with THSD pathways and metabolic disruption followed by expert curation to identify biologically plausible KEs/AOs and KER justification.	Preparatory work in progress	Curation of the network exploring links between THSD and metabolic KEs from the AOP-Wiki, identification of evidence gaps, prioritization of metabolic AO and initial literature research for building up evidence for the links (iterative process).
Explore mechanisms initiated by TR antagonism	SG2 THSD	An assay for TR antagonism was included in the current JRC-EU-NETVAL validation study. However, AOPs initiated by TR antagonism are few and have not been fully developed. This has been highlighted as a priority by Task 6.1.1.b IATA-ED. (relevance to human and environmental health)	Literature review and use of partners' data including knockout and knockdown data from different vertebrate species and relevant chemical exposures to explore evidence for linking this MIE to downstream KEs.	Preparatory work in progress	Preparatory work in advanced stage as currently a shortlist of TR inhibitors are being tested in the tFET assay (enhanced to include TR specific endpoints). Animal experiments planned for spring 24 and relevant licence submitted to UK HO.

Initiate investigation on AOP's for thyroid-like hormone system disruption in invertebrates with mollusks as example.	SG2 THSD	Focus on invertebrate AOPs need to be initiated. There is increasing evidence that mollusks have a thyroid-like hormone system with hormones and receptors, though different from the vertebrate THS in respect to function and receptor ligands. This needs to be explored to understand the effects of THSD on mollusks. (environmental health)	Literature study to identify possible MIEs, KEs and AOs related to mollusk thyroid-like hormone system disruption.	Preparatory work in progress	Literature study initiated
SG3 Adult and developmental neurotoxicity					
Support AOP(s) network addressing the link between environmental exposures and Alzheimer's Disease	SG3 (Adult NeuroToxicity, ANT)	The development of these AOP(s) will support the AOP network in AOP-Wiki, which addresses chronic neurodegenerative diseases that also develop some common MIEs and KEs (e.g. overactivation of glutamatergic ion receptors, synaptic dysfunction, proteostasis). This will contribute to the identification of nodes relevant for chronic neurodegenerative diseases potentially linked to environmental contaminants exposure.	Literature study to identify biologically plausible MIEs/KEs/AOs to expand the existing AOP network. Use of existing metabolomics data from patients when relevant.	Preparatory work in progress	Stages that have been developed: Problem formulation, planning for the methods and drafting an a priori protocol, development of an AOP network addressing ANT based on AOP-Wiki and derivation of a putative AOP addressing Alzheimer's Disease, prioritization of MIEs and KEs to be systematically reviewed. Preparatory work for the systematic review: identification of the most suitable platform, preparation of the search strings, definition of the eligibility criteria for literature selection.

					Development of automatic tools to scan and map the evidence, and to support in the systematic review process.
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<p>Develop an AOP that will provide evidence for the dysregulation of glycolysis after early childhood exposure to EDCs.</p>	<p>SG3 DNT</p>	<p>Glucose is the primary energy substrate in the brain, as it is the principal source of ATP. Whereas energy function in the aging brain and their related neurodegenerative diseases has been explored in some detail, there is limited knowledge about molecular mechanisms and brain networks of energy metabolism during infancy and childhood (Oyarzabal et al, 2021).</p>	<p>Literature study to identify biologically plausible KEs/AOs to expand the existing AOP network. Use of existing omics data from epidemiological and in vitro studies</p>	<p>Preparatory work in progress</p>	<p>We have initiated a comprehensive review of information available on the AOP-Wiki, focusing specifically on the DNT inventory for AOPs associated with neurodevelopmental disorders. This process began with a literature search employing Topic Modeling techniques, followed by the expert judgment-based screening of the resulting topics. We have pinpointed relevant topics and set eligibility criteria for an in-depth systematic literature review, utilizing text mining tools for efficiency. Looking ahead, our future efforts will concentrate on enhancing the DNT putative AOP framework and examine the possibility of constructing a DNT AOP Network.</p>
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<p>Develop an AOP for toxicants (e.g. L-BMAA) resembling natural amino acids</p>	<p>SG3 DNT</p>	<p>Toxicants that resemble endogenous amino acids, such as L-BMAA, can cause DNT (Myhre et al, 2018). It has been suggested that they: i) become incorporated into proteins, disrupting their function, and/or ii) act (excitotoxin) on neurotransmitter (glutamate) receptors, thus can lead to oxidative stress/glutathione depletion.</p>	<p>Literature study to identify biologically plausible KEs/AOs to expand the existing AOP network. In vitro study testing.</p>	<p>Preparatory work in progress</p>	<p>We are writing a protocol for a systematic review following EFSA's guideline. We have identified 9 non-proteinogenic amino-acids (NPaa) in the literature with known adult neurotoxicity that could potentially generate neurodevelopmental disorders. We have obtained a list of synonyms and identification numbers for these NPaa. We are further searching for other NPaa with potential developmental neurotoxicity using in silico prediction tools. We have created the search strings for the systematic search including part 1) the name and synonyms of each NPaa, and part 2) developmental neurotoxicity related terms. We have performed a preliminar search in PubMed for the first 9 NPaa. We are preparing the final search with all identified NPaa in PubMed and Web of Science to be performed by NIPH's library. Preparatory work has been conducted on the</p>
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					<p>use of reverse docking, aiming to obtain potential enzymatic targets for the 9 toxicants, compare them using Venn graphs, perform Gene Ontology and KEGG, and create neural networks in order to elucidate which enzymes should further be considered for the DNT AOPs development. In the next steps, we foresee the use of the QSAR Toolbox in order to find similar substances to the already identified 9 toxicants and the analysis of their impact on earlier found enzymatic targets via docking.</p>
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<p>Develop an AOP that will provide evidence for the dysregulation of the TCA cycle after early childhood exposure to EDCs.</p>	<p>SG3 DNT</p>	<p>Mitochondrial dysfunction, characterised by loss of the electron transport chain efficiency and reduction in the ability to generate adenosine triphosphate (ATP), is a common characteristic of neurodevelopmental and neurodegenerative diseases (Uittenbogaard et al, 2014). The abundance of different TCA cycle metabolites is essential for the function of the mitochondria, and even if there is evidence for its dysregulation after exposure to Eiv (Sarigiannis et al, 2021), the mechanism is not described yet.</p>	<p>Literature study to identify biologically plausible KEs/AOs to expand the existing AOP network. Use of existing omics data from epidemiological and in vitro studies</p>	<p>Preparatory work in progress</p>	<p>We have initiated a comprehensive review of information available on the AOP-Wiki, focusing specifically on the DNT inventory for AOPs associated with neurodevelopmental disorders. This process began with a literature search employing Topic Modeling techniques, followed by the expert judgment-based screening of the resulting topics. We've pinpointed relevant topics and set eligibility criteria for an in-depth systematic literature review, utilizing text mining tools for efficiency. Looking ahead, our future efforts will concentrate on enhancing the DNT putative AOP framework and examine the possibility of constructing a DNT AOP Network.</p>
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<p>Investigate whether KEs and KERs linking THSD to DNT in mammals are also applicable to fish</p>	<p>SG3 DNT/SG2 THSD</p>	<p>Whether KEs and KERs in the THSD AOPN leading to DNT apply to fish will support the development of both human and ecotoxicological IATAs for THSD in T6.1.1b IATA-ED.</p>	<p>KEs and KERs included in AOPs linking THSD to DNT in mammals (e.g., in AOPs 54, 42) will be selected to investigate their applicability to fish based on literature review and new data becoming available in T5.2.2.</p>	<p>Preparatory work in progress</p>	<p>Scoping effort based on literature and available information in the AOP-Wiki. Limited data availability for KEs leading to DNT in fish in the THSD-AOP network identified as potential issue. Scope of this priority broadened to any THSD-DNT effects in fish. This priority is shared with SG2. Development of search strings for systematic literature review and evaluation of available evidence as next steps.</p>
<p>AOPs developed in task 6.1 to support design of IATAs</p>					
<p>Draft an AOP network of genotoxic events leading to permanent DNA damage</p>	<p>IATA-Gentox</p>	<p>The draft AOP network for permanent DNA damage will help to identify which parts within the network need further development (qualitative/quantitative).</p>	<p>Collection of AOPs available in AOP-Wiki + Literature study</p>	<p>Draft AOP network for permanent DNA damage partially developed.</p>	<p>The draft AOP network has been reviewed by ESCA. Following the positive advice of ESCA, an SPSF for inclusion of the work on an AOP network for permanent DNA damage has been submitted to the WNT. The draft AOP network might still change during the course of the project.</p>

Provide quantitative data to support the biological plausibility of KERs included in our network	IATA-Gentox	There is a lack of quantitative data describing KER in genetic toxicology, and these data are useful for meeting regulatory needs. Initial efforts for the quantitative work will focus on the KERs within the AOP linking 'Alkylation of DNA' to 'Increase, gene mutations' as this AOP has already been endorsed at OECD level.	qAOP approaches, review all studies with different KEs quantification for qAOP in a same cell model/compound, data generation with NAMs to fill datagaps	Preparatory work in progress	Data for TK6 cells being exposed to EMS has been extracted from literature and initial data analysis performed, yet is still ongoing.
Characterize the different KEs and KERs in the AOP linking 'Bulky DNA adduct formation' to 'Increase, gene mutations' and 'Increase, structural chromosome aberrations'.	IATA-Gentox	Bulky DNA adduct formation is an important MIE for permanent DNA damage. The AOP on Bulky DNA adduct formation was previously introduced in the AOP-Wiki by another research team, but due to a lack of resources, the work was put on hold. This work will now be continued under PARC.	Literature study with systematic search	Preparatory work in progress.	Lessons learnt in the development of the AOP on Bulky DNA adduct formation will be used characterize other KEs and KERs in the AOP network on permanent DNA damage.

Explore missing MIEs or KEs from AOPs in AOP-Wiki leading to liver fibrosis	IATA-STOT	Initial exploratory analysis suggests that important MIEs and KEs may have been missed in currently available AOPs leading to liver fibrosis.	Text mining, bioinformatics, and literature study to identify biologically plausible MIEs/KEs to expand the existing AOP network.	Preparatory work in progress	Bioinformatics and text-mining have been initiated to propose potential missed KEs; A transcriptomics experiment comparing 4 liver cell models has been started, from which early KEs may emerge after further bioinformatic analysis; 1 new AOP has been submitted to AOP-Wiki (https://aopwiki.org/aops/494), while details still need to be filled in.
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Table 1. AOPs developed in 5.3.2a and 6.1

2.2. Status of the EMG work

General information about the EMG work

The overall aim for the Effect Marker Group (EMG) is to identify putative effect markers in the AOPs identified and developed by the Specialty Groups (SGs).

Effect markers are defined by WHO as “a measurable biochemical, physiologic, behavioral, or other alteration in an organism that, depending on the magnitude, can be recognized as associated with an established or possible health impairment or disease” (WHO, 1993). This definition was used in the HMB4EU project (Baken et al. 2019, Rodríguez-Carrillo et al. 2023, Zare Jeddi et al. 2021) and is also used by the EMG in PARC T5.3.2. The HMB4EU effect biomarker group further added five relevant criteria to be considered in the selection of effect biomarkers (Rodríguez-Carrillo et al. 2023) given in short below:

1. **Non/Low-invasive but predictive measured mainly in** peripheral blood, serum or urine
2. **Sensitive**, the biomarker of effect must change in response to the exposure to environmental chemical compounds to a degree that allows the alterations caused to be detected.
3. **Population variability and discriminative power** with sufficient population variability to enable the discrimination of healthy vs. unhealthy status of individuals and inter-individual variability to ensure that sensitive populations are identified.
4. **The analytical performance of the biomarker should** a) Provide specific and sensitive measurements, free of potential interferences, b) Be reproducible showing an adequate intra- and inter-assay coefficient of variation ensuring reproducibility of measurements.
5. **Analytical and clinical validation** studies must show that the effect biomarker is appropriate for its intended use.

Within the EMG, the work has been divided into 5 tasks related to the different SGs:

EMG Task 1: Effect biomarkers for endocrine disruption (related to SG2)

EMG Task 2: Effect biomarkers for immune toxicity and respiratory sensitization (related to SG1)

EMG Task 3: Effect biomarkers for metabolism (related to SG2)

EMG Task 4: Effect biomarkers for neurotoxicity (related to SG3)

EMG Task 5: Opportunities, databases, and challenges of epigenetic effect markers

In Year 1 (AD5.5 report, 2023), well-known effect marker for the inventoried AOPs were listed by EMG Task 1-4. In year 2, we continued the search for novel effect markers by literature searches in Task 1-4. In year 1 (AD5.5 report, 2023), EMG Task 5 inventoried existing human data sets with DNA methylation data. In year 2, EMG task 5 started the analyses of the first data set.

This D5.3 Year 2 (2024) EMG report has the following outline: a summary of the literature search and a conclusion is given for each task (1 to 5). Large tables and detailed information for each task are given in appendices.

References (General information about the EMG work)

- World Health Organization, Biomarkers and risk assessment : concepts and principles / published under the joint sponsorship of the United Nations environment Programme, the International Labour Organisation, and the World Health Organization. 1993, World Health Organization: Geneva.
- Baken, K.A., et al., A strategy to validate a selection of human effect biomarkers using adverse outcome pathways: Proof of concept for phthalates and reproductive effects. *Environmental Research*, 2019. 175: p. 235-256. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2019.05.013>

- Rodríguez-Carrillo, A., et al., Implementation of effect biomarkers in human biomonitoring studies: A systematic approach synergizing toxicological and epidemiological knowledge. International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health, 2023. 249: p. 114140. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2023.114140>
- Zare Jeddi, M., et al., Towards a systematic use of effect biomarkers in population and occupational biomonitoring. Environ Int, 2021. 146: p. 106257. DOI: [10.1016/j.envint.2020.106257](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2020.106257)

EMG Task 1: Endocrine disruption (AU-PH)

In year 2, we have continued the work from year 1 with identification of effect marker for thyroid and androgen related AOPs. The work is presented in this report (D5.3). We are planning to conduct writing of scientific papers on the obtained results in year 3-4. Moreover, in year 3, we will identify effect markers for the 15 estrogen related AOPs with rodents and/or humans applicability identified by SG2.

Thyroid (AU-PH)

In year 1, the SG2 identified 32 AOPs related to thyroid hormone pathways (listed in AD5.5.) of which most were still under development. Eleven AOPs were applicable to rodents and/or humans and included in the search for effect markers. A network of the included AOPs is shown in Figure 1. For several events known effect markers relevant for epidemiological studies were identified in the AD5.5 Year 1 report (boxes with orange border in Figure 1) and we have therefore mostly focused on events without identified markers in the further work. While some of the early events (yellow boxes in Figure 1) may be detectable before the upstream events (green boxes in Figure 1), they may not be specific for the adverse outcome.

Figure 1 Network of thyroid related AOPs with rodent/human applicability, divided into four groups (1: Hippocampal alterations related to loss of cochlear function and decreased cognitive function; 2: Reduced levels brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) and function of the neurons related to impaired learning and memory; 3: Increase in hypertrophy, occurrence of adenomas/carcinomas; 4: Occurrence of kidney toxicity).

proliferation, and hyperplasia in follicular cells related to Adenomas/carcinomas in follicular cells; 4: Event related to kidney toxicity). **Yellow boxes (n=15)** are early events, **green boxes (n=16)** are upstream events, and **blue boxes (n=5)** are the adverse outcomes. For events with boxes with **orange borders (n=18)**, a relevant effect marker was identified and listed in the AD5.5 report (Year 1 2023). No effect markers relevant for epidemiological studies were identified for events with **black borders (n=11)**.

Thus, our search of effect markers has focused on the more specific upstream events, but we suggest including some effect markers related to the thyroid disruption in epidemiological studies as well. We have not included information on measurement of the thyroid hormones (TH) in this work as several reviews and guidelines already exist for TH measurements in blood (D'Aurizio, Kratzsch et al. 2023, Van Uytfanghe, Ehrenkranz et al. 2023).

In the search of effect markers, the upstream events (**green boxes** in Figure 1) were divided into four groups based on the key event relationships and the related adverse outcome. We have made four appendixes on the searches and results for each group:

1. Hippocampal alterations related to loss of cochlear function and decreased cognitive function

See Annex - Effect marker for thyroid related AOPs (PARC 5.3.2 EMG) *Hippocampal alterations (gene expression, anatomy, and physiology)*

Summary of findings: One promising effect marker related to hippocampal alterations and cognitive decrease was identified. The brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) can be measured in serum and urine and has also been validated as an effect marker for neurological outcomes/behavioural function in HBM4EU (Mustieles, Rodríguez-Carrillo et al. 2022, Rodríguez-Carrillo, Mustieles et al. 2023). Several other possible effect markers, mostly at gene expression levels, were identified, but further studies are needed to validate the findings in non-/low invasive matrices and confirm the association with the key events and adverse outcome.

2.Reduced levels brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) and function of the neurons related to impaired learning and memory. (conducted by AUTH in EMG Task 4)

See Annex - Effect markers for DNT-Thyroid related AOPs.

Summary of findings: As the AOP 54 overlap between EMG Task 1 (AU-PH; endocrine disruption) and EMG Task 4 (AUTH; neurotoxicity), the search of effect markers was carried out by AUTH in EMG Task 4 (neurotoxicity). The brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) has already been validated as an effect marker for neurological outcomes/behavioural function in HBM4EU (Mustieles, Rodríguez-Carrillo et al. 2022, Rodríguez-Carrillo, Mustieles et al. 2023). In the search, several possible effect markers for the other key events in the AOP was identified by AUTH in EMG Task 4.

3.Increase in hypertrophy, proliferation, and hyperplasia in follicular cells related to adenomas/carcinomas in follicular cells.

See Annex - Effect marker for thyroid related AOPs (PARC 5.3.2 EMG) *Hypertrophy, proliferation and hyperplasia in follicular cells*

Summary of findings: Serum Calcitonin was identified as a promising effect marker, which has been described as an accurate measure of thyroid cancer tumour burden with high sensitivity (Costante and Meringolo 2020). Several potential effect markers were also identified such as blood interleukin-34 (IL-34) and differences in expression of genes between tumour tissue and normal non-cancerous tissues, however, further studies on these effect markers are needed to validate the findings in non-/low invasive matrices and the specificity needs to be determined.

4. Event related to kidney toxicity

See Annex - Effect marker for thyroid related AOPs (PARC 5.3.2 EMG) *Kidney function*

Summary of findings: Several effect markers for kidney toxicity were already identified in the EU-project HBM4EU (Zare Jeddi, Hopf et al. 2021, Rodríguez-Carrillo, Mustieles et al. 2023) and were also listed in the Year 1 (2023) PARC report AD5.5. Thus, no additional systematic literature searches were conducted, but information on the already identified effects markers were listed in the appendix. Several of the effect markers will be implemented in the PARC aligned studies conducted in WP4.

Conclusion: Promising or potential effect markers have been identified for all AOPs related to thyroid hormone disruption. Some effect markers are already validated and implemented in epidemiological studies, such as BDNF and the kidney markers. However, as seen in the appendices, several of the identified effect markers still need to be validated in humans and in non-/low-invasive matrices before they can be implemented in epidemiological studies.

References (EMG Task 1 Thyroid):

- Costante, G. and D. Meringolo (2020). "Calcitonin as a biomarker of C cell disease: recent achievements and current challenges." *Endocrine* **67**(2): 273-280.
- D'Aurizio, F., J. Kratzsch, D. Gruson, P. Petranović Ovcariček and L. Giovannella (2023). "Free thyroxine measurement in clinical practice: how to optimize indications, analytical procedures, and interpretation criteria while waiting for global standardization." *Critical Reviews in Clinical Laboratory Sciences* **60**(2): 101-140.
- Mustieles, V., A. Rodríguez-Carrillo, F. Vela-Soria, S. C. D'Cruz, A. David, F. Smagulova, A. Mundo-López, A. Olivas-Martínez, I. Reina-Pérez, N. Olea, C. Freire, J. P. Arrebola and M. F. Fernández (2022). "BDNF as a potential mediator between childhood BPA exposure and behavioral function in adolescent boys from the INMA-Granada cohort." *Science of The Total Environment* **803**: 150014.
- Rodríguez-Carrillo, A., V. Mustieles, E. Salamanca-Fernández, A. Olivas-Martínez, B. Suárez, L. Bajard, K. Baken, L. Blaha, E. C. Bonefeld-Jørgensen, S. Couderq, S. C. D'Cruz, J.-B. Fini, E. Govarts, C. Gundacker, A. F. Hernández, M. Lacasaña, F. Laguzzi, B. Linderman, M. Long, H. Louro, C. Neophytou, A. Oberemn, S. Remy, A. K. Rosenmai, A. T. Saber, G. Schoeters, M. J. Silva, F. Smagulova, M. Uhl, A. M. Vinggaard, U. Vogel, M. Wielsøe, N. Olea and M. F. Fernández (2023). "Implementation of effect biomarkers in human biomonitoring studies: A systematic approach synergizing toxicological and epidemiological knowledge." *International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health* **249**: 114140.
- Van Uytvanghe, K., J. Ehrenkranz, D. Halsall, K. Hoff, T. P. Loh, C. A. Spencer and J. Köhrle (2023). "Thyroid Stimulating Hormone and Thyroid Hormones (Triiodothyronine and Thyroxine): An American Thyroid Association-Commissioned Review of Current Clinical and Laboratory Status." *Thyroid* **33**(9): 1013-1028.
- Zare Jeddi, M., N. B. Hopf, S. Viegas, A. B. Price, A. Paini, C. van Thriel, E. Benfenati, S. Ndaw, J. Bessems, P. A. Behnisch, G. Leng, R. C. Duca, H. Verhagen, F. Cubadda, L. Brennan, I. Ali, A. David, V. Mustieles, M. F. Fernandez, H. Louro and R. Pasanen-Kase (2021). "Towards a systematic use of effect biomarkers in population and occupational biomonitoring." *Environ Int* **146**: 106257.

Androgen (AU-PH)

In year 1, the SG2 identified 29 AOPs related to androgen pathways (listed in AD5.5.) in which most were still under development. Twenty AOPs were applicable to rodents and/or humans and included in the search for effect markers. A network of the included AOPs is shown in Figure 2. For several events (**orange borders**), known effect markers relevant for epidemiological studies were identified in the Year 1 AD5.5 report (2023) and we have therefore mostly focused on events without identified markers in the further work. While some of the early events (**yellow boxes** in Figure 2) may be detectable before the upstream events (**green boxes** in Figure 2), they may not be specific for the adverse outcome. Thus, our search of effect markers has focused on the more specific upstream events, but we suggest including some effect markers related to the androgen disruption in epidemiological studies as well. We have not included information on measurement

of the androgen hormones in this work as several reviews and guidelines already exist for measurements in blood (Bhasin, Brito et al. 2018, Heijboer and Hannema 2023).

Figure 2 Network of androgen related AOPs with rodent/human applicability, divided into four groups (1.

Alteration in Wnt pathway and Feminization or incomplete development in male sex organs related to impairment of reproductive capacity; 2. Proliferation, Hyperplasia in Leydig cells related to impaired fertility and Leydig cell tumours; 3. Leydig cell proliferation/hyperplasia and malformation of male reproductive tract related to impaired or decreased fertility; 4. Androgen receptor initiating proliferation in hepatocytes related to hepatocellular adenomas and carcinomas). Yellow boxes are early events, green boxes are upstream events, and blue boxes are the adverse outcomes. For events with orange borders, a relevant effect marker was identified and listed in the Year 1-2023 AD5.5 report, while no effect markers relevant for epidemiological studies were identified for events with black borders.

In the search of effect markers, the upstream events (green boxes with black border in Figure 2) were divided into four groups based on the key event relationships and the related adverse outcome (blue boxes, Figure 2). We have made four appendixes on the searches and results for each group:

1. Alteration in Wnt pathway and Feminisation or incomplete development of male sex organs

See Annex - Effect markers for androgen related AOPs (PARC 5.3.2 EMG) *Alteration in Wnt pathway and Feminisation or incomplete development of male sex organs*

Summary of findings: Most studies addressed androgen receptor activity and expression and further confirm the crucial role of androgens in male fertility and impaired virilisation. Three proteins (4HPPD, ALDOB, and MMA) can be measured in blood serum as the markers of biological androgen activity (Giwercman, Sahlin et al. 2022). However, further research is needed to understand the clinical value of such a test in men. The role of Wnt pathway in the male reproductive organ development is explored in some articles, and all are at the RNA level with an array of genetic markers. As the measurements of Wnt pathway are based on testis samples, more studies are needed to validate in non-/low invasive matrices such as seminal fluid, semen, blood, and urine for epidemiology study.

2. Proliferation, Hyperplasia in Leydig cells related to impaired fertility and increased Leydig cell tumours.

Effect markers for androgen related AOPs (PARC 5.3.2 EMG) *Proliferation, Hyperplasia in Leydig cell*

Summary of findings: One promising effect marker, insulin-like factor 3 (INSL3), is identified and this marker can be measured either in blood or staining in the testis and is associated to fertility and can be useful for distinction of the Leydig cell hyperplasia and Leydig cell tumour (Lakis, Lombardo et al. 2019, Ivell, Heng et al. 2022). Several possible effect markers were identified or suggested, and some are at gene expression level as well as imaging marker and the matrices are tissues. Further epidemiology studies are needed to validate the findings in non-/low invasive matrices and confirm the association and specificity with the KEs and AOs of interest.

3. Proliferation, Hyperplasia in Leydig cells and malformation of male reproductive tract related to impaired or decreased fertility.

See Annex - Effect markers for androgen related AOPs (PARC 5.3.2 EMG) *Biomarkers related to male fertility and malformation of male reproductive tract*

Summary of findings: We identified one promising effect marker (INSL3) which can be measured in blood and is associated to fertility (Panagidis, Kostopoulou et al. 2020, Abbara, Koysombat et al. 2022). Several possible effect markers were identified or suggested, and most

are at gene expression level and the matrix are tissues. Thus, further studies are necessary to validate the finding in non-/low invasive matrices and confirm the association and specificity with the related KEs and AOs.

4. Androgen receptor initiating proliferation in hepatocytes related to hepatocellular adenomas and carcinomas.

See Annex - Effect markers for androgen related AOPs (PARC 5.3.2 EMG) *Proliferation in hepatocytes*.

Summary of findings: Four possible effect markers are suggested (lysozyme, MicroRNA 155, Toll-like receptor 3 and DNA repair). As all are measured in the tissue in vitro at gene expression level, further studies are needed to validate these markers in non-/low invasive matrices and confirm the association and specificity with the hepatocyte's proliferation and carcinoma.

Conclusion: Promising or potential effect markers have been identified for all AOPs related to androgen pathway. Some effect markers are already validated and implemented in epidemiological studies, such as INSL3 (Chang, Li et al. 2015, Chang, Wu et al. 2017). However, several of the identified/suggested effect markers still need to be validated in humans and in non-/low-invasive matrices before they can be implemented in epidemiological studies.

References (EMG Task 1 androgen)

- Abbara, A., K. Koysoombat, M. Phylactou, P. C. Eng, S. Clarke, A. N. Comninou, L. Yang, C. Izzi-Engbeaya, S. Hanassab, N. Smith, C. N. Jayasena, C. Xu, R. Quinton, N. Pitteloud, G. Binder, R. Anand-Ivell, R. Ivell and W. S. Dhillon (2022). "Insulin-like peptide 3 (INSL3) in congenital hypogonadotropic hypogonadism (CHH) in boys with delayed puberty and adult men." *Front Endocrinol (Lausanne)* **13**: 1076984.
- Bhasin, S., J. P. Brito, G. R. Cunningham, F. J. Hayes, H. N. Hodis, A. M. Matsumoto, P. J. Snyder, R. S. Swerdloff, F. C. Wu and M. A. Yialamas (2018). "Testosterone Therapy in Men With Hypogonadism: An Endocrine Society Clinical Practice Guideline." *J Clin Endocrinol Metab* **103**(5): 1715-1744.
- Chang, W. H., S. S. Li, M. H. Wu, H. A. Pan and C. C. Lee (2015). "Phthalates might interfere with testicular function by reducing testosterone and insulin-like factor 3 levels." *Hum Reprod* **30**(11): 2658-2670.
- Chang, W. H., M. H. Wu, H. A. Pan, P. L. Guo and C. C. Lee (2017). "Semen quality and insulin-like factor 3: Associations with urinary and seminal levels of phthalate metabolites in adult males." *Chemosphere* **173**: 594-602.
- Giwercman, A., K. B. Sahlin, I. Pla Parada, K. Pawlowski, C. Fehninger, Y. Lundberg Giwercman, I. Leijonhufvud, R. Appelqvist, G. Marko-Varga, A. Sanchez and J. Malm (2022). "Novel protein markers of androgen activity in humans: proteomic study of plasma from young chemically castrated men." *Elife* **11**.
- Heijboer, A. C. and S. E. Hannema (2023). "Androgen Excess and Deficiency: Analytical and Diagnostic Approaches." *Clin Chem* **69**(12): 1361-1373.
- Ivell, R., K. Heng, K. Severn, L. Antonio, G. Bartfai, F. F. Casanueva, I. T. Huhtaniemi, A. Giwercman, M. Maggi, D. B. O'Connor, T. W. O'Neill, M. Punab, G. Rastrelli, J. Slowikowska-Hilczler, J. Tournoy, D. Vanderschueren, F. C. W. Wu and R. Anand-Ivell (2022). "The Leydig cell biomarker INSL3 as a predictor of age-related morbidity: Findings from the EMAS cohort." *Front Endocrinol (Lausanne)* **13**: 1016107.
- Lakis, N. S., K. A. Lombardo, S. Mangray, G. J. Netto, D. Salles and A. Matoso (2019). "INSL3 Expression in Leydig Cell Hyperplasia and Leydig Cell Tumors." *Appl Immunohistochem Mol Morphol* **27**(3): 203-209.
- Panagidis, A., E. Kostopoulou, A. P. Rojas Gil, X. Sinopidis, H. Kourea, S. Skiadopoulos, G. Georgiou and B. E. Spiliotis (2020). "Correlation between insulin-like peptide 3 and appendix testis length in congenital cryptorchidism." *J Paediatr Child Health* **56**(8): 1283-1289.

EMG Task 2: Immune (NIPH / NCPHP/UGent)

In SG1 for immunotoxicity there are three working groups established (1. Respiratory sensitization; 2. Immunosuppression; 3. Inflammation for Non-genotoxic carcinogens (NGTxC)). The AOP-Wiki

inventory has been mapped for these three endpoints in year 1 and an overview of existing markers was given. Three related sub-tasks are ongoing to further describe existing and potential novel effect markers: 1. Respiratory Sensitization task, 2. Immunosuppression task, and 3. Marine toxin task.

Respiratory Sensitization (NCPHP)

Main activities in Year 2:

We identified one AOP related to respiratory sensitization available in AOP-Wiki: AOP 39: Covalent Binding, Protein, leading to Increase, Allergic Respiratory Hypersensitivity Response (OECD status: under development; applicable to humans and rodents). In year 2, we created a list of relevant KEs related to the process of respiratory sensitization from AOP-Wiki and extracted information on the suggested measurement methods described in those KEs. We made an inventory of measurement methods (traditional diagnostic tests of occupational asthma and novel promising assays) with the potential to be adapted as effect markers. We used the following sources for that: a) KEs of AOP 39, b) other relevant KEs included in other AOPs, and c) other methods that were found in the literature (reviews and research papers) based on a PubMed search performed in Year 1. We focused our search on the upstream KEs (KE2: Activation, dendritic cells; KE3: Activation/proliferation, T-cells) and AO (Increase, allergic respiratory hypersensitivity response) of AOP 39. We categorized measurement methods as either recommended (44%: non-/minimally invasive method, human sample collection) or not recommended as an effect marker (56%: invasive method, in vitro method). In the literature search, we found 2181 papers matching the search terms in PubMed. Abstract screening and data extraction from selected literatures started and it is still in progress.

Summary of findings:

Bronchial provocation test (Beach et al. 2007, Üzmezoğlu 2021) and basophil activation test (Vera-Berrios et al. 2019) were identified as known, valuable effect markers related to the increased allergic hypersensitivity response. They can be measured from breath or blood, respectively. Other promising effect markers were also identified, such as eosinophil-derived neurotoxin level that can be measured from serum, sputum, urine and nasal lavage fluid (Rodriguez del Rio et al. 2022), exhaled air volatile organic compound composition (Ogular et al. 2021) and miRNA ratios in the blood or breath (Fujita et al. 2014). It needs to be noted that many potential effect markers become detectable only after the disease appears. Therefore they are not suitable for early detection. A single test will probably will not be sufficient for a specific and sensitive assessment. Still, a combination of suitable assays (a battery of tests of several KEs) could be used in an integrated testing strategy. They need to be validated before they can be applied in epidemiological studies.

See Annex – Respiratory sensitization

Plans for Year 3:

We plan to continue screening the abstracts and reading the full texts of included papers. We will extract relevant information (biological matrix, assay method, advantages, limitations, sensitivity, specificity, etc.) of potential effect markers of respiratory sensitization to further complete the inventory. We intend to write a review paper, complete gaps in AOP-Wiki and make suggestions for validation of selected effect markers.

Immunosuppression and modulation (NIPH)

In the AOP working group the focus is currently on updating the AOP14 “Glucocorticoid Receptor Activation Leading to Increased Disease Susceptibility”. Machine-Learning (ML)-assisted and conventional literature reviews are ongoing in the AOP group. A description and documentation of both existing and potential novel KE will be performed with the aim of enhancing this AOP. We anticipate also capturing additional and potentially novel effect markers in this process. In addition, a targeted literature search was performed, and a review of the data is ongoing. The search was performed in PubMed and in Embase and will be further described in year 3. In short, we searched for key words for markers of effect in combination with keywords for immunosuppression. The search

was limited to the years 2019-2023. We got 106 unique articles in PubMed and 364 in Embase when overlapping publications were removed. An evaluation of the best documented markers will be performed.

Marine toxins (UGent)

One of the stressors we focused on are **marine algal toxins**. Marine toxins are a significant human health concern because they can cause severe and potentially life-threatening conditions, such as paralytic shellfish poisoning and ciguatera fish poisoning, through the consumption of contaminated seafood. These toxins can affect multiple organ systems, leading to symptoms ranging from gastrointestinal distress to neurological impairments, and their increasing prevalence due to climate change and ocean pollution heightens the risk of exposure.

Identifying **effect markers in humans for marine aquatic toxins** is crucial for early detection and treatment of toxin exposure, ensuring timely medical intervention. It enhances public health safety by allowing authorities to assess exposure levels and prevent outbreaks. Effect markers provide essential data for regulatory bodies to establish safety standards and permissible limits for marine toxins in seafood. Understanding these markers helps scientists uncover the mechanisms of toxicity, aiding in the development of therapeutic strategies.

It is reported in literature that marine toxins have immunomodulatory activities (e.g. Keeler et al., 2019, doi:10.3390/md17030184). During year 2 we performed an extensive literature study on the mode-of-action and immune-modulating effects of marine toxins. The table in appendix (See Annex – Marine toxins and their immunomodulating effects) gives an overview of the in vivo and in vitro effects for the ten main groups of marine toxins.

Moreover, we queried the AOP-Wiki for AOPs linked to immune functioning. We used ‘immune’ as search term, resulting in 30 AOPs. By manually screening these AOP’s, we removed one. Based on the remaining 29 AOPs, a list of 128 molecular initiating events, key events and adverse outcomes was made. An AOP-helpFinder search was done with this list of 128 events and 14 marine toxins as stressors. We will fine tune the resulting table and study it into more detail during year 3. Based on this AOP-helpFinder result and literature search, we will put forward potential effect markers for marine toxins in year 3.

Gene expression analysis serves as a potent tool for unveiling the molecular pathways and mechanisms targeted by toxicants. Therefore, we searched the NCBI database for gene expression data for marine toxins. We found gene expression data for azaspiracid in Jurkat T cells, for okadaic acid in different cell lines, ciguatoxin in whole blood of patients and homoyessotoxin in A549 cells. In year 3, an analysis of these gene expression data and gene set enrichment analysis for hallmark gene sets from the Molecular Signature Database and KEGG pathways (data from Asselman et al., 2019, doi:10.1038/s41598-018-36866-3) should give more insights into the mode-of-action and immunomodulating properties of these toxins. Moreover, we will compare the enriched hallmark gene sets and KEGG pathways to gene sets targeted by well-known immunosuppression agents, such as cyclosporin A. In this way, we make a link with our work within WP 5.3.1a (*Ab initio* group).

References (EMG Task 2 Immune)

- Beach, J., Russell, K., Blitz, S., Hooton, N., Spooner, C., Lemiere, C., ... & Rowe, B. H. (2007). A systematic review of the diagnosis of occupational asthma. *Chest*, 131(2), 569-578.
- Fujita, Y., Yoshioka, Y., Ito, S., Araya, J., Kuwano, K., & Ochiya, T. (2014). Intercellular communication by extracellular vesicles and their microRNAs in asthma. *Clinical Therapeutics*, 36(6), 873-881.
- Ogulur, I., Pat, Y., Ardici, O., Barletta, E., Cevhertas, L., Fernandez-Santamaria, R., ... & Akdis, C. A. (2021). Advances and highlights in biomarkers of allergic diseases. *Allergy*, 76(12), 3659-3686.
- Rodriguez del Rio, P., Liu, A. H., Borres, M. P., Södergren, E., Iachetti, F., & Casale, T. B. (2022). Asthma and allergy: unravelling a tangled relationship with a focus on new biomarkers and treatment. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 23(7), 3881.

- Üzmezoğlu, B. A. (2021). Inhalation Challenge Tests in Occupational Asthma: Why Are Multiple Tests Needed?. *Turkish Thoracic Journal*, 22(2), 154.
- Vera-Berrios, R. N., Feary, J., & Cullinan, P. (2019). Basophil activation testing in occupational respiratory allergy to low molecular weight compounds. *Current Opinion in Allergy and Clinical Immunology*, 19(2), 92-97.

EMG Task 3: Metabolism (INSERM)

At the beginning of the project, the work of "SG2 on metabolism" consisted of inventorying the AOPs related to disrupted metabolic pathways.

As a reminder and to summarize, for year 1, our aim was to list well-known effect markers (EM) for molecular initiating events (MIEs) and key events (KEs) in the inventoried AOPs from the AOP-Wiki database (<https://aopwiki.org>). We crossed the information from AOP-Wiki and the one from ICD-11 (<https://icd.who.int/en>). The ICD-11 is the eleventh revision of the International Classification of Diseases (ICD) and is the global standard for recording health information and causes of death. For information, this classification has not been updated since last year (The ICD is normally annually updated by the World Health Organization, WHO).

A classification by strata (category, sub-category) was carried out, focusing on metabolic pathologies; these were certainly varied, but far from covering all metabolic pathologies (including major ones in terms of worldwide incidence):

- Decreased, Body Weight (AOP 6)
- Obesity (AOP 72)
- Liver Steatosis (AOP 34,)
- Increased, Liver Steatosis (AOP 36, 58, 60, 61, 318)
- Accumulation, Liver lipid (AOP 57,
- Increased, steatosis (AOP 232,
- Steatohepatitis (AOP 213, 401)

with many redundancies between AOPs (ex: Increased liver steatosis). Moreover, most AOPs were still in development.

Regarding Effect Markers (EM), we focused on MIE (Molecular Initiating Events) and KE (Key Events). This includes for MIE mostly a change in the function of nuclear receptors (PPARs, LXR, FXR, GR), some of them being xenobiotic receptors (CAR, PXR) and one, a bHLH/PAS receptor (AhR, another xenobiotic receptor). Regarding key events (KEs), many of them are related to metabolic processes (fatty acid beta oxidation), dysregulated expression of metabolic genes (CEBPA) or correspond to the prementioned MIEs (activation of PPAR).

During the year 2-3 period, a literature search has been conducted to state the potential relevance of these KEs as possible effect (clinical) biomarkers:

- none of the MIEs so far, could be assigned to an EM
5. several KEs could be considered as 'classical EM related to metabolic diseases'; they are typically measured during medical examinations:
 6. Increased adipogenesis (AO: obesity, AOP 72)
 7. Suppression VLDL secretion (AO: accumulation, liver lipid, AOP 57)
 8. Increase LDL uptake (AO: accumulation, liver lipid, AOP 57)
 - Several KEs could be consider as 'specific EM related to metabolic diseases'; they are specifically measured during medical examinations to clarify diagnosis classification
 9. Production of ketone bodies (AO: decreased body weight, AOP 6)
 10. Accumulation triglyceride (AO: liver steatosis, AOP 34) (AO: increased liver steatosis, AOP 318)

11. Increase triglyceride formation (AO: increased liver steatosis, AOP 58 & 60)
12. Decreased ketogenesis (AO: increased liver steatosis, AOP 60)
13. Increase triglyceride (AO: increased liver steatosis, AOP 61)

Several additional activities were conducted: we identified 2 major gaps in the representativeness of AOPs relating to metabolic diseases: diabetes and the progression of chronic liver disease. Two AOPs have therefore begun to be developed including potential new KEs that could constitute biomarkers of clinical and metabolic effect.

These AOPs are:

- **AhR activation leading to liver fibrosis** (AOP 494: <https://aopwiki.org/aops/494>)
- 14. **ERα inactivation alters mitochondrial functions and insulin signaling in skeletal muscle and leads to insulin resistance and metabolic syndrome** (AOP 497: <https://aopwiki.org/aops/497>)

They cover both:

- The evolution of chronic liver disease, with hepatic fibrosis as AO, an intermediate stage of progression between steatosis (included as KE) and hepatic cirrhosis.
- 15. Type 2 diabetes: at this stage, only AOP 431 (Increased tumor necrosis factor (TNF) leading to increased risk of gestational diabetes mellitus) refers to diabetes in its title. **We believe this constitutes a major gap in the AOP-Wiki AO list, given the worldwide incidence of type 2 diabetes in particular.**

Moreover, we are in contact with OECD for coaching on these AOPs. OECD is interested by this aspect as they are pushing towards the development of regulatory assays involving liver organoids (NAMs).

Regarding EMs, the following KEs could be included in the list above.

16. KE 1494 Recruitment/activation des leucocytes (AOP 494)
17. KE 1501 Increased, extracellular matrix deposition (AOP 494)
18. AO 2018 Insulin Resistance ((that can be a KE as it is a clinical EM) (AOP 497)

These two AOPs are under development, and the fibrosis AOP was presented at a STOT (Specific Target Organ Toxicity) meeting in March 2024.

Perspectives - Year 2+

19. to list well-known effect markers for molecular initiating events (MIEs) and key events (KEs) in the **new** inventoried AOPs from the AOP-Wiki database (<https://aopwiki.org>) (~410 -> 524)
- to develop both new metabolic related AOPs (494, 497).

EMG Task 4: Neurotoxicity (AUPh)

The initiation of the work on identifying effect markers for neurotoxicity related-AOPs commenced later in the past year when AUPh was enrolled as coordinator in Task 4. During year 1, SG3 used the SPARQL tool to identify and extract all AOPs from AOP-Wiki that refer to Developmental Neurotoxicity (DNT) and Adult Neurotoxicity (ANT). Two separate excel files (one for developmental neurotoxicity and one for adult neurotoxicity) were created, including all information of the respective AOPs (AOP IDs, titles, MIEs, KEs, AOs, modulators, chemical stressors associated to the AOP, AOP status and graphical representation). Subsequently, and based on these two files, two groups were formed, one for developmental neurotoxicity and one for adult neurotoxicity, which created two "human readable" files, respectively, depicting thoroughly all the pathways of AOPs and including all related information,

found in AOP-Wiki. Based on the declared interest of all partners, to participate in either group, two groups were formed, with the subsequent allocation of the partners. All information from the “human readable” files were used to develop the graphical visualization for the networks of the DNT and ANT AOPs, with the use of Cytoscape. Lastly, based on the existing knowledge and the DNT and ANT AOPs inventories, Priorities were established for advancing new and already existing AOPS, based on certain criteria for each group. The DNT group concluded with the establishment of 4 Priorities, which include the development of AOPs to provide evidence for the dysregulation of glycolysis (Priority 1) and the TCA cycle (Priority 2), after early childhood exposure to EDCs, and an AOP for toxicants resembling natural amino acids (Priority 3). Additionally, the group will investigate whether KEs and KERs linking THSD to DNT in mammals are also applicable to fish (Priority 4). Glucose is the primary energy substrate in the brain, as it is the principal source of ATP. In the brain, glucose is taken up from the bloodstream by specific glucose transporters to be metabolized through glycolysis. A few articles indicate that cerebral energy metabolism involving glucose, ketone body, and amino acid metabolism is dysfunctional in persons with AD and PD brains, but there is a lack of a fully described mechanism (Butterfield et al., 2022), which Priority 1 aims to investigate. Mitochondrial dysfunction, characterized by loss of the electron transport chain efficiency and reduction in the ability to generate adenosine triphosphate (ATP), is a common characteristic of neurodevelopmental and neurodegenerative diseases (Uittenbogaard et al., 2014). The abundance of different TCA cycle metabolites is essential for the function of the mitochondria, and even if there is evidence for its dysregulation after exposure to EDCs (Sarigiannis et al., 2021), the mechanism is not described yet and will be investigated by Priority 2. For human health, DNT is considered one of the most important adverse outcomes related to THSD, and AOPs have been developed for mammals. In models used for the assessment of environmental health consequences of THSD, such as fish, this has received much less attention. Therefore, determining whether KEs and KERs in the THSD AOPN leading to DNT apply to fish will improve the exchange of knowledge between human and environmental health and will support the development of both human and ecotoxicological IATAs for THSD in T6.1.1b IATA-ED. The investigation will be held under Priority 3, which is a shared Priority of the SG3 DNT and the SG3 groups.

Several animal studies have shown that β -Methylamino-L-alanine (BMAA) is a neurodevelopmental toxicant (Cox et al., 2016; Dawson et al., 1998; Karlsson et al., 2009; Karlsson et al., 2012). The suggested mechanism(s) are through either i) glutamate receptor overactivation (excitotoxin) on neurons, or ii) protein misincorporation in place of L-serine, leading to toxicity. Based on knowledge derived from the search in AOP Wiki, these mechanisms do not exist and their investigation is prioritized by the DNT group (Priority 4). The development of a new AOP or the further development of an already existing one, with the identification of additional events (MIEs and/or KEs), could be relevant for several chemicals with similar structures and potential neurodevelopmental toxicity.

In the context of developing an AOP for adult neurotoxicity, the criteria driving the development of an AOP or network were aimed at addressing unresolved questions in the regulatory assessment of adult neurotoxicity. Based on an EFSA report (EFSA Journal 2013;11(7):3293) and a systematic review with meta-analysis of epidemiological studies (Yan, D., Zhang, Y., Liu, L. et al. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep32222>), the working group prioritised the development of an AOP/AOP network specifically focused on Alzheimer’s disease (AD) as a neurological disorder potentially linked to long-term pesticide exposure.

For this assessment, an initial putative AOP network for AD was developed based on: (i) existing AOPs related to adult neurotoxicity from the AOP wiki, incorporating AOs and events relevant to AD according to different ontology data sources focusing on phenotype, (ii) expert knowledge, and (iii) literature text mining.

In total, the DNT team identified 12 AOPs that refer to developmental neurotoxicity and the ANT team identified 16 AOPs that refer to adult neurotoxicity. Research in order to list all known effect markers for neurotoxicity was carried out using AOP-Wiki, aiming to identify markers for MIEs/KEs that have been identified in AOP-Wiki.

In total, for the 12 DNT AOPs identified in AOP-Wiki, after exclusion of duplicate MIEs/KEs, a total of 10 molecular initiating events (MIEs), 41 key events (KEs) and 4 adverse outcomes (AOs) were identified.

For the 16 ANT AOPs identified in AOP-Wiki, in total, 17 molecular initiating events (MIEs), 65 key events (KEs) and 14 adverse outcomes (AOs) were identified. For one AOP (429) no MIEs were reported.

Developmental neurotoxicity

In year 2 we focused on identifying KEs with no effect markers and proceeded with an initial categorization of those KEs into aspects of developmental neurotoxicity, from molecular interactions affecting thyroid and neurotransmitter systems, to cellular responses impacting synaptic function and plasticity, neurotrophin signaling, and lipid metabolism. Tissue and system level changes that lead to adverse developmental outcomes are also outlined [Table NT1.pdf](#). This structured approach can help in identifying more precise effect markers and understanding the mechanisms underlying developmental neurotoxicity. An initial literature research allowed an overview of potential biomarkers that could be used to assess the impact of various neurotoxic agents on neurodevelopmental processes. These biomarkers include both biochemical indicators (such as levels of specific proteins or enzymes) and functional tests (such as cognitive tests or imaging) that can indicate alterations in neurodevelopment. Initial mapping revealed that biomarkers vary widely across different subcategories, reflecting the complexity of the neurodevelopmental processes affected by toxicity (See Annex - Table NT1. Initial categorization and search of DNT MIEs, KEs and AOs with no EMs described in the AOPwiki)

Adult neurotoxicity

Similar work has been undertaken for the adult neurotoxicity (See Annex - Table NT2. Initial categorization and search of ANT MIEs, KEs and AOs with no EMs described in the AOPwik). Initial categorization and research for potential effect markers depicted those disruptions in calcium transport and NMDA receptor activity, influencing calcium levels and neural function, while alterations in GABA and metabotropic glutamate receptors impacting neurotransmission which could be assessed by GABA receptor function and chloride influx assays, and identification of downstream signalling pathways. Metabolic inhibition affects mitochondrial function, observed through changes in ATP concentration and energy metabolism biomarkers such as ADP/ATP ratio. Decompartmentalization poses a threat to membrane integrity, detectable via various enzyme assays assessing cytosolic enzyme levels. Cellular responses involve synaptic function, neuronal integrity, cellular stress, oxidative stress, and nitric oxide signalling. Loss of drebrin and synaptic dysfunction impede neuronal communication, and mitochondrial impairment disrupts energy flow, possibly reflected in altered ATP levels measured by mitochondrial respiration assays. Intracellular calcium increases and cell membrane depolarization signify changes in neuronal excitability, observed through electrophysiological assays assessing ion channel function. Cellular stress, including endoplasmic reticulum stress and calpain signalling activation, influences protein folding and degradation pathways, can be indicated by ER stress markers and calpain activity assays. Oxidative stress and reduced nitric oxide signalling lead to neuronal damage, evident through reactive oxygen species assays and nitric oxide production measurements. At the tissue and system level, protein aggregation

involving toxic tau oligomers and phosphorylation disturbances contribute to neurodegenerative diseases, observable through tau aggregation assays and phospho-tau assays. Impaired axonal transport disrupts neuronal function and health, reflected in axonal flow rates and imaging of dynein/kinesin function. Adverse outcomes include neurodegeneration, oxidative damage, sensory dysfunction, and cognitive impairment. Necrosis and increased oxidative damage signify neurodegeneration, whereas anosmia and memory loss indicate sensory and cognitive deficits, identifiable through specific biomarkers such as lactate dehydrogenase activity, lipid peroxidation assays, olfactory threshold tests, and cognitive assessments.

Additionally, efforts are being made to assess the effectiveness of current effect markers for their applicability in epidemiological research. Overlaps have been identified with Task 1 and Thyroid in particular. In this context, we initiated our research from AOP 54 focusing on downstream KEs: KE 851: Decrease of GABAergic interneurons, KE 385: Decrease of synaptogenesis and KE 386: Decrease of neuronal network function. (See Annex - Effect markers for DNT-Thyroid related AOPs)

Summary of the findings:

KE 851: Decrease of GABAergic interneurons

A number of research studies have been identified aiming to assess the suitability of effect markers for the decrease of GABAergic interneurons. In total 7 research articles and review studies have been found to focus on the identification of the respective effect markers with the use of non-invasive and invasive methods, thus recommending their use for human epidemiological studies or not. In 2021, Kantrowitz et al., published an article on the use of glutamate, glutamine and gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) as effect markers towards the diagnosis of major depressive disorder. According to the results of the study, the use of ¹H MRS is an appropriate method for the examination of Glx, Glu and GABA levels, linked to MDD cases. Two other studies published in 2023 and 2024, respectively, investigated the use of perineuronal nets (PNNs) as effect markers, towards the development of neurological diseases, although they proved to be invasive and thus not recommended for human epidemiological studies, as they required collection of brain samples (Dong et al., 2023; Morphett et al., 2024). In 2024, Gillespie et al., published a study focusing on Dlx1, Dlx2 and Nkx2.1 genes, alterations of which can impact the migration and maturation of the GABAergic interneurons. The maternal immune activation (MIA) model was used for the identification of GABAergic markers, disruptions of which coincided with distinct behavioural phenotypes, including memory, sensorimotor gating, anxiety, and sociability. In 2019, Kaar et al., reported that the reduction of the density of parvalbumin interneurons in the frontal context is associated with patients with schizophrenia. Changes in the parvalbumin cell density proved to be an appropriate effect marker, although the methodology followed in this study is not recommended for human epidemiological studies as it requires the collection of brain samples, which is considered to be an invasive method. In 2023, Richard et al., reported an association between GABAergic maturation and thyroid hormone action, aiming to move toward the prevention and treatment of neurological disorders. According to the results of this study, changes in the expression levels of genes relevant to GABAergic neuron development and function, such as those involved in GABA synthesis, metabolism, release, reuptake, and receptor expression, can serve as markers of alterations. Alterations in the expression of genes, including Dlx1, Dlx2, and Nkx2.1 could indicate disruptions. The methodology used in this study is also considered to be invasive with the collection of blood samples, and thus not recommended for human epidemiological studies.

KE 385: Decrease of synaptogenesis

In assessing the suitability of effect markers for decreased synaptogenesis, various studies offer insights into different methodologies and markers. A comprehensive range of neurochemical markers, including those measured via in vivo ¹H MR spectroscopy, alongside inflammatory and structural markers, are presented (Ennis-Czerniak et al., 2022). Plasma proteins associated with

cognitive stimulation are explored as potential biomarkers for cognitive health and dementia risk (Kivimäki et al., 2021), particularly suitable for large-scale epidemiological studies due to their non-invasive measurement in blood samples. Immunostaining of neuronal and synaptic markers, mRNA expression profiling, and electrophysiological assessments in cerebral organoids have also been employed, better suited for controlled experimental settings or specific clinical assessments given their invasive nature or complex methodologies involved (Logan et al., 2020).

KE 386: Decrease of neuronal network function

A number of research articles and review studies have been published aiming to investigate the suitability of effect markers for decreased neuronal network function. Various published articles have been identified, among which only 2 reported non-invasive methods, thus being able to be recommended for human epidemiological studies. The first study was published in 2018 by Woodworth et al. and reported the investigation of six urinary proteins as potential biomarkers for Urological Chronic Pelvic Pain Syndrome (UCPPS), with the use of the Bradford method and monospecific enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays. Diffusion tensor imaging (DTI) was also used in order to identify localized changes associated with corresponding changes in urinary protein levels in UCPPS, where it was shown that elevated MMP9 or MMP9/NGAL might be related to degenerative neuronal changes in brainstem nuclei through excitotoxicity. Furthermore, another article published in 2018 by Dyrba et al., reported the changes in mean amyloid load, glucose metabolism, and grey matter volume as biomarkers for Alzheimer's disease, detected with different neuroimaging methods. This study is also recommended for human epidemiological studies as it does not report invasive methods. Four more articles published between 2019 and 2022 identified cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) as a biomarker for Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease (sCJD) and Alzheimer's disease, with various methods, including the IQ-CSF RT-QuIC assay, neuroimaging techniques, genetic analysis and ELISA (Rübsamen et al., 2022; Fagan et al., 2021; Ng et al., 2021; Blennow et al., 2019). All these studies are considered to use invasive methods with the collection of CSF samples and are not recommended for human epidemiological studies. APP metabolism genes, tau protein binding, lipid metabolism and immune response have also been identified as effect markers for Alzheimer's disease with the use of eQTL analysis, in blood and brain tissue types (Kunkle et al., 2019).

Plans for Year 3:

We intend to carry out comprehensive literature reviews, mainly targeting MIEs, KEs, and AOs that lack identified effect markers for DNT and ANT. Our approach will start with examining later KEs and AOs to find effect markers that can be used in epidemiological studies. Additionally, we will persist in our current research efforts to discover effect markers for MIEs, KEs, and AOs that have already been associated with effect markers but are deemed unsuitable for epidemiological research.

References (EMG Task 4 neurotoxicity)

20. Blennow, K., Diaz-Lucena, D., Zetterberg, H., Villar-Pique, A., Karch, A., Vidal, E., ... & Llorens, F. (2019). CSF neurogranin as a neuronal damage marker in CJD: a comparative study with AD. *Journal of Neurology, Neurosurgery & Psychiatry*, 90(8), 846-853.
21. Butterfield, D. A., Favia, M., Spera, I., Campanella, A., Lanza, M., & Castegna, A. (2022). Metabolic features of brain function with relevance to clinical features of Alzheimer and Parkinson diseases. *Molecules*, 27(3), 951.
22. Cox, P. A., Davis, D. A., Mash, D. C., Metcalf, J. S., & Banack, S. A. (2016). Dietary exposure to an environmental toxin triggers neurofibrillary tangles and amyloid deposits in the brain. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 283(1823), 20152397.
23. Dawson Jr, R., Marschall, E. G., Chan, K. C., Millard, W. J., Eppler, B., & Patterson, T. A. (1998). Neurochemical and neurobehavioral effects of neonatal administration of β -N-methylamino-l-alanine and 3, 3'-Iminodipropionitrile. *Neurotoxicology and teratology*, 20(2), 181-192.
- Dong, Y., Zhao, K., Qin, X., Du, G., & Gao, L. (2023). The mechanisms of perineuronal net abnormalities in contributing aging and neurological diseases. *Ageing Research Reviews*, 102092.
24. Dyrba, M., Grothe, M. J., Mohammadi, A., Binder, H., Kirste, T., Teipel, S. J., & Alzheimer's Disease Neuroimaging Initiative. (2018). Comparison of different hypotheses regarding the spread of Alzheimer's disease using Markov random fields and multimodal imaging. *Journal of Alzheimer's Disease*, 65(3), 731-746.

- Ennis-Czerniak, K., WH, F. I., Tkac, I., & Rao, R. B. (2022). Intranasal Insulin Attenuates the Long-term Adverse Effects of Neonatal Hyperglycemia on the Hippocampus in Rats. *Developmental Neuroscience*.
- Fagan, A. M., Henson, R. L., Li, Y., Boerwinkle, A. H., Xiong, C., Bateman, R. J., ... & Lott, I. T. (2021). Comparison of CSF biomarkers in Down syndrome and autosomal dominant Alzheimer's disease: a cross-sectional study. *The Lancet Neurology*, 20(8), 615-626.
- Gillespie, B., Panthi, S., Sundram, S., & Hill, R. A. (2023). The Impact of Maternal Immune Activation on GABAergic Interneuron Development: A Systematic Review of Rodent Studies and their Translational Implications. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, 105488.
- Kaar, S. J., Angelescu, I., Marques, T. R., & Howes, O. D. (2019). Pre-frontal parvalbumin interneurons in schizophrenia: a meta-analysis of post-mortem studies. *Journal of Neural Transmission*, 126, 1637-1651.
- 25. Kantrowitz, J. T., Dong, Z., Milak, M. S., Rashid, R., Kegeles, L. S., Javitt, D. C., ... & John Mann, J. (2021). Ventromedial prefrontal cortex/anterior cingulate cortex Glx, glutamate, and GABA levels in medication-free major depressive disorder. *Translational psychiatry*, 11(1), 419.
- 26. Karlsson, O., Roman, E., Berg, A. L., & Brittebo, E. B. (2011). Early hippocampal cell death, and late learning and memory deficits in rats exposed to the environmental toxin BMAA (β -N-methylamino-L-alanine) during the neonatal period. *Behavioural brain research*, 219(2), 310-320.
- 27. Karlsson, O., Berg, A. L., Lindström, A. K., Hanrieder, J., Arnerup, G., Roman, E., ... & Andersson, M. (2012). Neonatal exposure to the cyanobacterial toxin BMAA induces changes in protein expression and neurodegeneration in adult hippocampus. *Toxicological sciences*, 130(2), 391-404.
- 28. Kivimäki, M., Walker, K. A., Pentti, J., Nyberg, S. T., Mars, N., Vahtera, J., ... & Lindbohm, J. V. (2021). Cognitive stimulation in the workplace, plasma proteins, and risk of dementia: three analyses of population cohort studies. *Bmj*, 374.
- 29. Kunkle, B. W. et al. Genetic meta-analysis of diagnosed Alzheimer's disease identifies new risk loci and implicates A β , tau, immunity and lipid processing. *Nat. Genet.* 51, 414-430 (2019).
- Logan, S., Arzua, T., Yan, Y., Jiang, C., Liu, X., Yu, L. K., ... & Bai, X. (2020). Dynamic characterization of structural, molecular, and electrophysiological phenotypes of human-induced pluripotent stem cell-derived cerebral organoids, and comparison with fetal and adult gene profiles. *Cells*, 9(5), 1301.
- Morphett, J. C., Whittaker, A. L., Reichelt, A. C., & Hutchinson, M. R. (2024). Perineuronal net structure as a non-cellular mechanism contributing to affective state: A scoping review. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, 105568.
- Ng, K. P., Pascoal, T. A., Mathotaarachchi, S., Chan, Y. H., Jiang, L., Therriault, J., ... & Dominantly Inherited Alzheimer Network. (2021). Neuropsychiatric symptoms are early indicators of an upcoming metabolic decline in Alzheimer's disease. *Translational Neurodegeneration*, 10, 1-11.
- Richard, S., Ren, J., & Flamant, F. (2023). Thyroid hormone action during GABAergic neuron maturation: The quest for mechanisms. *Frontiers in Endocrinology*, 14, 1256877.
- 30. Rübsem, N., Pape, S., Königorski, S., Zapf, A., Rücker, G., & Karch, A. (2022). Diagnostic accuracy of cerebrospinal fluid biomarkers for the differential diagnosis of sporadic Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease: a (network) meta-analysis. *European journal of neurology*, 29(5), 1366-1376.
- 31. Sarigiannis, D. A., Papaioannou, N., Handakas, E., Anesti, O., Polanska, K., Hanke, W., ... & Karakitsios, S. (2021). Neurodevelopmental exposome: The effect of in utero co-exposure to heavy metals and phthalates on child neurodevelopment. *Environmental Research*, 197, 110949.
- 32. Uittenbogaard, M., & Chiaramello, A. (2014). Mitochondrial biogenesis: a therapeutic target for neurodevelopmental disorders and neurodegenerative diseases. *Current pharmaceutical design*, 20(35), 5574-5593.
- Woodworth, D. C., Dagher, A., Curatolo, A., Sachdev, M., Ashe-McNalley, C., Naliboff, B. D., ... & MAPP Research Network. (2018). Changes in brain white matter structure are associated with urine proteins in urologic chronic pelvic pain syndrome (UCPPS): A MAPP Network study. *PloS one*, 13(12), e0206807.

EMG Task 5: Opportunities, databases, and challenges of epigenetic effect markers in humans (KULeuven)

Summary

We have grouped about six partners with interest in epigenetic biomarkers and listed a set of existing large human data bases to perform association studies on environmental chemicals. We rolled out a design to implement a combination of machine learning methods that can be useful in a next analytic phase, after exploration of other covariates or confounders in our models. Our concept has been

presented at DIOXIN2023 as a poster presentation, and it was published as a short paper in *Organohalogen Compounds*, 2023 (Liefoghe et al. 2023). We are currently studying a first data set to increase our understanding on malleability of the human epigenome in relation to exposure to endocrine disruptors or other environmental chemicals.

Methodology, screening and first output:

We selected existing human datasets that can serve as a starting point to generate new epigenetic biomarkers. These novel effect biomarkers could help develop the next-generation risk assessment tools or increase our understanding of adverse outcome pathways (AOPs) or networks of AOPs.

Selected datasets included studies with available individual information of subjects and at least two of the following requirements:

1. measured metabolites of environmental chemicals to which populations are exposed to on a daily basis, such as endocrine disruptors (EDCs) or OPEs (e.g., flame retardants or plasticizers)
2. measured epigenetic factors in human specimens that could be linked to inheritance from one generation to the next (e.g., male germ cells and/or in children)
3. diseases outcomes or risk assessment in children.

In our selected data sets genome-wide epigenetic measurements were mainly obtained through the Infinium HumanMethylation450 array (450K array). This technique uses bisulfite treatment to convert unmethylated cytosines, but not methylated cytosines, to uracils, generating a C/T polymorphism at CpG sites after DNA amplification; this is readily measurable with the Infinium technology. Below, we describe our first approach in a first data set (but more data will be integrated in the following years).

In a first study, including nearly 90 young male subjects, we have measurements of OPEs metabolites (TDCIPP, TCIPP, TPHP, ipPDPP and tbPDPP) in urine. Most men (>90%) have been exposed to at least three of these OPEs. DNA methylation was measured in sperm at 485,512 CpGs using the 450K array. These results have been pre-processed. OPEs have been detected in human matrices via liquid chromatography tandem mass-spectrometry. The following metabolites of OPEs will be explored: bis(1,3-dichloro-2-propyl) phosphate (BDCIPP), bis(1-chloro-2-propyl) phosphate (BCIPP), diphenyl phosphate (DPHP), isopropylphenyl phenyl phosphate (ipPDPP), terbutylphenyl phenyl phosphate (tbPDPP), and Tris(2-chloroethyl) phosphate (TCEP).

We performed data preprocessing of the 450K array raw data as described earlier (Maksimovic et al. 2012, Pidsley et al. 2013, Teschendorff et al. 2013, Aryee et al. 2014, Liefoghe et al. 2023), including sample quality control, filtering of probes with low intensities, and normalization (Subset-quantile Within Array Normalization (SWAN) versus Beta Mixture Quantile (BMIQ) Normalization).

Additional health-related determinants such as lifestyle, exercising, medical and semen condition, age, etc. have also been included. In the first approach of our design, we will control for confounding. First, we will estimate the effects on the epigenome by analysing them one-by-one, before we perform more advanced methods. We are currently preparing manuscripts for publication on potential variations in the epigenome among human populations. Our overall concept has been published in September 2023 in *Organohalogen Compounds*, 2023 (Liefoghe et al. 2023).

In brief, in the next year, we will perform exposure-outcome correlation analyses, including potential confounding and accurate selection of differentially DNA methylated genes by the exposure of interest.

Future work (next years):

1. Continue data analyses of studies above. One of our challenges in human studies is the effect of mixtures of exposures (different types of chemicals combined with lifestyle, diet, age, etc) in human populations, and the multitude of health-related effects in human (the individual, the unborn child, the next generation(s), ...).

- Both supervised and unsupervised machine learning (ML) algorithms will be implemented for data integration. Available data from the arrays, associated meta data, and chemical information will be integrated using a naïve vertical integration after standardization to generate a single unified dataset. ML models, that try to identify patterns within the data, will be used to identify key multivariate components leading to the observed adverse outcome or to the chemical concentration highlighting the methylation sites affected by these chemicals. Network based approaches may further allow us to identify potential combinations of genes and metadata that associate more strongly with specific outcomes leading to new knowledge on longer-term effects of the exposure of interest. Probabilistic graphical modelling, such as a Bayesian network, will be explored and could be beneficial, opening new opportunities to link a specific exposure to toxicological effects in humans.

Relevance: This concept and its first results will direct future research and guide the design of new study cohorts (also beneficial for WP4), needed to further evaluate accuracy and precision of the selected epigenetic biomarkers. Novel effect biomarkers could help develop the next-generation risk assessment tools or increase our understanding of adverse outcome pathways (AOPs) or networks of AOPs (cfr. WP7).

References (EMG Task 5 Epigenetic):

- Aryee, M.J., et al., Minfi: a flexible and comprehensive Bioconductor package for the analysis of Infinium DNA methylation microarrays. *Bioinformatics*, 30(10): p. 1363-9, 2014.
- F. Liefoghe, E. Casella, M. Butynets, V. Kumar, D. Deepika, A.F. Hernandez, M. Lacasaña, P. Antczak, T. Puzyn, K. Ciura, A. Spyropoulou, I. Theologidis, T. Price, C. Hoyo, S.K. Murphy, H. M. Stapleton, and A. Soubry; Intergenerational chemical risk assessment in humans using epigenetic epidemiology studies and machine learning approaches, *Organohalogen Compounds*, p.42, Vol.2023.
- Maksimovic, J., L. Gordon, and A. Oshlack, *SWAN: Subset-quantile within array normalization for illumina infinium HumanMethylation450 BeadChips*. *Genome Biol*, 13(6): p. R44, 2012.
- Pidsley, R., et al., A data-driven approach to preprocessing Illumina 450K methylation array data. *BMC Genomics*, 14: p. 293. 2013.
- Teschendorff, A.E., et al., A beta-mixture quantile normalization method for correcting probe design bias in Illumina Infinium 450 k DNA methylation data. *Bioinformatics*, 29(2): p. 189-96; 2013.

3. Follow-up actions for regulatory acceptance

AOPs can support regulatory-decision making in multiple ways:

- Structuring available knowledge by mapping it to the different MIEs/KEs/AOs within the AOP and identifying knowledge gaps; this process could provide regulators with a stronger basis to decide whether there is sufficient evidence to take a scientifically sound decision;
- Providing insights in the modes of action underlying the adverse outcome of chemicals; by using AOPs, regulators could obtain more certainty in a chemical's modes of action, and consequently, in the likeliness that an adverse outcome might occur (e.g. EDCs);
- Supporting read across as compounds sharing common KEs might have similar modes of action; this could be used as evidence to justify grouping/read-across;
- Selecting biomarkers of effects; biomarkers of effect are currently not (routinely) used by regulators in the decision-making process; by linking biomarkers of effects to KEs within AOPs, regulators could obtain more confidence in integrating this type of information when making decisions;

- Guiding the interpretation of data from NAMs by linking it to a MIE/KE within the AOP; data generated with NAMs do generally not provide direct information on the adverse outcome but instead on more upstream events; by linking NAMs to KEs within an AOP/AOP network, regulators can better understand the relevance of the data provided by a NAM and its link to a specific AO;
- Designing IATAs based on NAMs; AOPs can provide a framework to select NAMs to be used within an IATA in a scientifically sound way (e.g. IATA for skin sensitisation).

Within PARC, the developed AOPs will be used for NAM development in T5.2. and the design of IATAs in T6.1. across different domains of applicability, including human and environmental health protection. Indeed, the development of AOPs, NAMs and IATAs are closely interlinked. On one hand, AOPs can help to identify gaps in testing and guide NAM development. In this context they connect classical *in vivo* studies with mechanistic effects that can be observed *in vitro* or in alternative species (e.g. *Danio*, *Xenopus embryos*). On the other hand, they also provide an excellent framework for IATA development. Moreover, simultaneous development of IATAs can help identify which (parts of the) AOPs need to be further developed. Such a process can provide additional data to other AOP developers further driving AOP development and acceptance. A good interaction between T5.3 and T6.1 is thus crucial. Currently, this interaction is already in place for the endpoint 'thyroid disruption' as AOPs are being further developed in T5.3 whereas IATAs are being designed under T6.1. The possibility of applying a similar strategy for the most advanced AOPs will be explored. Moreover, as the developed AOPs can be important tools to support read across, interaction is also foreseen with the read across work that is being done within the context of the Systems Toxicology project in T5.3.

In order to stimulate the regulatory acceptance of AOPs by the community outside PARC, where relevant and possible, links are being established with the OECD AOP Development Programme. Within this context, it is important to note that several partners are members of the OECD Advisory Group on Emerging Science in Chemicals Assessment (ESCA) that oversees the essential elements of the OECD AOP Programme. While these partners cannot be expected to have expertise in all fields of emerging technologies and their utilisation within regulatory actions, they help to align AOP development with regulatory needs and bridge the work of PARC with ongoing activities at OECD level. All AOPs developed as part of the OECD AOP Development Programme can be found in the AOP-Wiki database. The database contains information on the different AOPs in a qualitative and narrative way and, as outlined in this document, this is an important information source/tool for AOP development under PARC. Recently, the AOP-Wiki has been redesigned using a completely new data model, which aims to increase FAIRness of AOPs, improve user experience and optimize the user interface to allow for improved data entry and visualisation of AOPs. However, much additional work in this area is needed. Therefore, the FAIRification of AOPs has been undertaken collaboratively by WP7 (Task 7.2) and WP5 (Task 5.3.2), in conjunction with external initiatives i.e., the FAIR AOP Cluster. A dedicated working group has been established to address this objective, which has led to the FAIR-AOPs case study, aimed at assessing the current state of the AOP-Wiki data model in terms of its adherence to FAIR principles. The culmination of this collaboration is a conceptual paper on the FAIRification of AOPs (accessible at <https://www.altex.org/index.php/altex/article/view/2664>). Additionally, the 3PFF training provided for WP7 by the GoFairFoundation (GFF), has led to the development of an early version of the FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP). The developed AOP-FIP lays the groundwork for further advancement and implementation of FAIR principles within the domain of AOPs. It establishes a collection of FAIR practices and choices, made by a specific FAIR Community, and delineates a set

of FAIR Enabling Resources (FERs). Furthermore, recent activities of the group include the development of a metadata schema for the AOP-Wiki, the identification of gaps therein, and an assessment of third-party needs and requirements to the utilization of AOP-Wiki data and its services. Moreover, as the number of AOPs grows, also within PARC, it is of utmost importance to establish and maintain a suitable ontology that standardises the framing and description of every MIE, KE, and AO. While efforts in this direction exist, it will be necessary to ensure that AOPs developed within PARC are aligned with regulatory language. Also within this context, establishing links with the OECD AOP Development Programme will help to address this issue.

Importantly, many of the AOPs in the AOP-Wiki (i.e. 65%) are not included in the OECD work plan. This does not necessarily imply that these AOPs are of poor quality but it might hinder their regulatory application. Within this context, it is important to continue discussions with regulators to obtain more insights into the level of maturity that they require. If regulators need endorsed AOPs, it is essential to identify relevant AOPs early in time and ensure that they move to the more advanced stages of AOP development. Within PARC, efforts are made to include as much as possible newly developed AOPs in the AOP-Wiki database and to submit the ongoing AOP work for inclusion in the OECD work plan. For example, the AOP network leading to permanent DNA damage was submitted to ESCA for review. Following a positive advice of ESCA, the work was successfully submitted to the WNT and is now included in the OECD work plan. It should be noted that submission of AOP work for inclusion in the OECD work plan can in principle be done at any stage. There are no clear instructions on this as the relevance of the AOPs for regulators may change over time. Nevertheless, early inclusion can help to focus the work on regulatory needs. Discussions with regulators are thus key and in PARC, these interactions are ensured, amongst others, by organizing workshops (cfr. first AOP workshop organized in June 2024). Additionally, ECHA and EFSA are closely following several of the AOP/IATA activities.

Overall, the AOPs developed under PARC will be useful tools for regulators as they will facilitate the interpretation of data generated with NAMs either as standalone or as part of an IATA. Moreover, one particular strength of AOPs is that they are chemical agnostic and inclusive in biology. Consequently, AOPs are excellent tools to bridge traditional *in vivo* data, *in vitro* data and whole organism data collected in alternative models and consequently, to bridge environmental and human health protection. The latter will also be addressed under PARC.

4. Conclusion

Within WPs 5-6, 25 AOPs are presently being developed in the areas of immunotoxicity and non-genotoxic carcinogenesis (SG1), endocrine disruption and metabolic disruption (SG2), and neurotoxicity (SG3). For most of these, literature reviews and text mining are in progress. Three of them are partially developed (developing pathways leading to insulin resistance/obesity/type 2 diabetes, implementation of a taxonomic domain of applicability study results from ERGO (EURION) in AOP-Wiki, AOP network of genotoxic events leading to permanent DNA damage).

Promising effect markers have also been identified in relation to thyroid hormone disruption, the androgen pathway, respiratory sensitization, neurotoxicity, as well as epigenetic effect markers.

The regulatory acceptance and use of the AOPs developed in WP5-6 will be fostered through (i) links with the OECD AOP Development Programme to align AOP development with regulatory needs, (ii) the simultaneous development of IATAs in Task 6.1 of PARC, as is currently being done for the endpoint “thyroid disruption”, and (iii) the FAIRification of AOPs, which has been undertaken in collaboration with WP7.

5. References

Duarte Hospital C, Tête A, Debizet K, Imler J, Tomkiewicz-Raulet C, Blanc EB, Barouki R, Coumoul X, Bortoli S. SDHi fungicides: An example of mitotoxic pesticides targeting the succinate dehydrogenase complex. *Environ Int.* 2023 Oct;180:108219. doi: 10.1016/j.envint.2023.108219. Epub 2023 Sep 19. PMID: 37778286.

Jaylet T, Coustillet T, Smith NM, Viviani B, Lindeman B, Vergauwen L, Myhre O, Yarar N, Gostner JM, Monfort-Lanzas P, Jornod F, Holbech H, Coumoul X, Sarigiannis DA, Antczak P, Bal-Price A, Fritsche E, Kuchovska E, Stratidakis AK, Barouki R, Kim MJ, Taboureau O, Wojewodzic MW, Knapen D, Audouze K. Comprehensive mapping of the AOP-Wiki database: identifying biological and disease gaps. *Front Toxicol.* 2024 Mar 8;6:1285768. doi: 10.3389/ftox.2024.1285768. PMID: 38523647; PMCID: PMC10958381.

Myhre O, Låg M, Villanger GD, Oftedal B, Øvrevik J, Holme JA, Aase H, Paulsen RE, Bal-Price A, Dirven H. Early life exposure to air pollution particulate matter (PM) as risk factor for attention deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD): Need for novel strategies for mechanisms and causalities. *Toxicol Appl Pharmacol.* 2018 Sep 1;354:196-214. doi: 10.1016/j.taap.2018.03.015. Epub 2018 Mar 14. PMID: 29550511.

Oyarzabal A, Musokhranova U, Barros Lf, Garcia-Cazorla. Energy metabolism in childhood neurodevelopmental disorders. *EBioMedicine.* 2021 Jul;69:103474. doi: 10.1016/j.ebiom.2021.103474. Epub 2021 Jul 10. PMID: 34256347; PMCID: PMC8324816.

Uittenbogaard M, Chiaramello A. Mitochondrial biogenesis: a therapeutic target for neurodevelopmental disorders and neurodegenerative diseases. *Curr Pharm Des.* 2014;20(35):5574-93. doi: 10.2174/1381612820666140305224906. PMID: 24606804; PMCID: PMC4823001.

Wittwehr, C., Clerbaux, L.-A., Edwards, S., Angrish, M., Mortensen, H., Carusi, A., Gromelski, M., Lekka, E., Virvilis, V., Martens, M., Bonino da Silva Santos, L. O. and Nymark, P. (2024) "Why adverse outcome pathways need to be FAIR", ALTEX - Alternatives to animal experimentation, 41(1), pp. 50–56. doi: 10.14573/altex.2307131.

6. Annex

Effect marker for thyroid related AOPs (PARC 5.3.2 EMG)

Authors: Maria Wielsøe, Manhai Long, Eva Cecilie Bonefeld-Jørgensen – Department of Public Health, Aarhus University (AU-PH), Denmark

Hippocampal alterations (gene expression, anatomy, and physiology)

Five AOPs (8, 42, 134, 152, 300) with similar key events (KEs) on alterations of the hippocampal were identified as thyroid related AOPs (Figure 1). The hippocampal key events were altered hippocampal gene expression (KE 756), altered hippocampal anatomy (KE 757), and altered hippocampal physiology (KE 758). The five AOPs had two common adverse outcomes (AOs): Loss of cochlear function (AO 319) and decreased cognitive function (AO 402).

Figure 1: Network of AOP 8, 42, 134, 152, and with common events on alterations in hippocampal. **Yellow boxes** are early events (mostly related to thyroid hormones), **green boxes** are upstream events, and **blue box** is the adverse outcome. For events with **orange borders**, a relevant effect marker was identified and listed in the AD5.5 report (Year 1 – 2023), while no effect markers relevant for epidemiological studies were identified for events with **black borders**.

Methods:

Some measurement methods for the three KEs (KE 756, 757, 758) have been suggested in the AOPwiki, however, many are not suitable as effect markers in epidemiological studies as they require brain tissue, e.g. immunohistochemical staining, in situ hybridization, electrical field potentials and gene expressions on hippocampus slides and tissue.

In our search, we have focused on effect markers which could be measure by non/low invasive methods. We searched PubMed for potential effect markers using the search string in Text box 1 on the January 23, 2024.

("effect marker"[Title/Abstract] OR "biomarker"[Title/Abstract] OR "gene expression"[Title/Abstract] OR "transcriptomic"[Title/Abstract] OR "measurement"[Title/Abstract]) AND ("Hippocampal alteration"[Title/Abstract] OR "Hippocampal change"[Title/Abstract] OR "Hippocampal gene expression"[Title/Abstract] OR "Hippocampal anatomy"[Title/Abstract] OR "Hippocampal Physiology"[Title/Abstract]) AND (humans[Filter])

Text box 1: Search string used on PubMed

We focused on articles published in 2018 or later, as the aim is to find new novel effect marker, furthermore the articles must have information on the relevant KEs/AO. Of the 56 studies, 8 studies [1-8] were published in 2018 or later, relevant and included information of possible effect marker for hippocampal alterations (gene expression, anatomy, and physiology) (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Flow chart of literature search and selection.

Results and discussion:

The information on possible effect marker in the 8 included studies are listed in Table 1 (page 4-7). Two AOs (decrease cognitive function and loss of cochlear function) were included in the 5 AOPs relevant for this search (Figure 1), however, all the included studies focused on the decreased cognitive function and especially Alzheimer's disease.

One study [1] measured the hippocampal grading with magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) using Scoring by Nonlocal Image Patch Estimator (SNIPe) and were able to accurately classify persons with normal cognitive function from persons with cognitive impairment and Alzheimer's disease. The tool could be promising for detecting early/mild cognitive impairment in a clinical setting, however, using MRI in larger epidemiological studies may be too inconvenient and logistically challenging [1]. The seven other studies measured gene expression levels in postmortem brain / hippocampus tissue, in either humans [2-5] or mice [6-8] (Table 1, page 4-7). Before the possible effect marker can be used in epidemiological studies, they need to be validated in non-/low invasive human matrices such as blood, urine, or saliva.

One of the most promising effect markers identified is the BDNF, which was also identified in HBM4EU as an effect marker for neurological outcomes/behavioural function [9, 10]. It has already been verified in several epidemiological studies that BDNF can be measured in serum, plasma, and urine. High serum BDNF level have also recently been associated with decreased risk of poststroke cognitive impairment after 3 months [11]. However, to our knowledge, there are no studies investigating if the BDNF level in blood and urine is correlated with the level in the hippocampus, but it is likely that the levels are correlated.

Many of the included studies [1-4, 6] utilized samples from Alzheimer's patients or from mouse models for Alzheimer's disease. Alzheimer's is known for its impact on the hippocampus. It's important to note that some of the effect markers might only emerge after Alzheimer's disease has become evident. Therefore, these markers may not be effective in early detection of cognitive impairment.

Conclusion:

In this literature review, we searched for effect markers for hippocampal alterations in relation to cognitive function and cochlear function (AOP [8](#), [42](#), [134](#), [152](#), [300](#)). We identified one promising effect marker (BDNF), which can be measured in blood and urine and is linked to cognitive function. Several other possible effect markers, mostly gene expression levels, were identified, but further studies are needed to validate the findings in non-/low invasive matrices and confirm the association and specificity with the KEs and AOs of interest.

Table 1 Possible effect markers for hippocampal alterations (gene expression, anatomy, and physiology)

Effect marker	Matrix	Measurement methods	Description of association with key event or adverse outcome in humans or if stated validation of measurement/effect marker.	Developmental status of the effect marker	Comments / Recommended for human epidemiological studies (Why, why not)	Authors
Hippocampal grading using Scoring by Nonlocal Image Patch Estimator (SNIFE)	Magnetic resonance imaging of brain in intact human body	Participants were scanned with magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), memory and cognition were measured with Wechsler Memory Scale and Mini Mental Status Examination (MMSE) or Clinical Dementia Rating (CDR).	<p>The MRI were evaluated with Scoring by Nonlocal Image Patch Estimator (SNIFE): SNIFE computes the similarity of every voxel in the hippocampus of each person to a library of manually segmented MRI datasets from healthy cognitively intact older adults and patients with Alzheimer's disease. The SNIFE score of -1 equal similarity with Alzheimer's disease and +1 equal similarity with healthy control</p> <p>The SNIFE grading had a higher classification accuracy than other methods (SNIFE volume and Freesurfer volume) when classifying 1) normal persons versus Alzheimer's patients, 2) normal persons versus and early mild cognitive impairment persons; 3) early mild cognitive impairment persons versus late mild cognitive impairment persons, and 4) late mild cognitive impairment persons versus Alzheimer's patients.</p> <p>The method was validated in an independent cohort with good results, suggesting that the classification model is generalizable and replicable in other datasets.</p>	<p>Some validation needed.</p> <p>The method is validated and accurately classified normal persons from persons with cognitive impairment and Alzheimer's disease.</p>	For epidemiological studies the effect marker may not be very useful, as the MRI measurement is very inconvenient and time-consuming.	[1] Morrison et al. 2023
BDNF and TrkB gene expression	Postmortem human CA1 pyramidal neurons and regional	PCR and hybridization	In CA1 pyramidal neurons BDNF expression was reduced in persons with mild cognitive impairment compared to persons with no cognitive impairment. TrkB expression were also effect-dependent reduced in persons with no cognitive impairment and Alzheimer's	<p>Some validation needed.</p> <p>BDNF methylation and serum levels have been identified and validated as a marker of</p>	Promising effect marker, if the effects on BDNF and TrkB in the brain can be found in non-/low invasive matrices as well.	[2] Ginsberg et al. 2019

	hippocampal dissections		<p>patients compared to no cognitive impairment.</p> <p>In hippocampus BDNF were reduced in persons mild cognitive impairment compared to persons with no cognitive impairment, however the expression was higher in Alzheimer's patients than with mild cognitive impairment. The hippocampal TrkB effect-dependent reduced in persons with no cognitive impairment and Alzheimer's patients compared to no cognitive impairment.</p> <p>BDNF and its receptor, TrkB regulate many key brain functions involved in survival, neurogenesis, neuroplasticity, and learning and memory.</p>	<p>neurological function in epidemiological studies.</p> <p>Studies on correlation between the effects in the hippocampal and serum/urine is wanted.</p>		
QPCTL, APOE, and ERCC2 gene expression	Postmortem human hippocampus samples	Whole genome sequencing and RNA sequencing	<p>Hippocampal expression of QPCTL and ERCC2 were different in Alzheimer's patients (n=599) and cognitively normal elderly individuals (n=317)</p> <p>QPCTL associated positively and ERCC2 associated negatively with hippocampal volume.</p> <p>QPCTL is involved in the modification of proteins by converting N-terminal glutamine to pyroglutamate, which is important for protein stability and function. ERCC2 is involved in DNA repair.</p>	<p>Some validation needed.</p> <p>Studies on correlation between the effects in the hippocampal and non-/low invasive matrices is wanted.</p>	<p>Possible future effect marker if the altered gene expression can be found in non/low invasive matrices. Furthermore, association with the AOs (cochlar function and cognitive function) have to be confirmed, as only association with Alzheimer's disease is shown in this study.</p>	[3] Liu et al. 2021
ATL2 gene expression	Postmortem human brain samples	real-time qPCR	<p>Based on data from in-vitro and mice studies, ATL2 expression in brain tissue were suggested as a possible marker of dementia/cognitive function.</p> <p>The ATL2 expression level was significantly elevated in Alzheimer's patients (n=3) compared to controls (n=3).</p> <p>The results were confirmed with data from the</p>	<p>Some validation needed.</p> <p>Studies on correlation between the effects in the hippocampal and non-/low invasive matrices is wanted.</p>	<p>Possible future effect marker if the altered gene expression can be found in non/low invasive matrices. Furthermore, association with the AOs (cochlar function and cognitive function)</p>	[4] Han et al. 2021

			Allen Institute for Brain Science, including 57 controls and 33 alzheimer's patients. ATL2 regulates endoplasmic reticulum structure and plays a critical role in endoplasmic reticulum membrane fusion and tethering.		have to be confirmed, as only association with Alzheimer's disease is shown in this study.	
GAS6 expression	Postmortem human brain samples	In situ hybridization of hippocampus (dentate gyrus) tissue	Based on data from rodent studies, GAS6 expression in hippocampus tissue were suggested as a possible marker of microglial developmental and brain function after early-life stress. Microglia are innate immune cells in the brain that respond to environmental exposures by cytokine release and phagocytosis and are critical for brain development and function. In human hippocampus tissue from depressed suicides with a history of child abuse had increased numbers of microglia and microglia with GAS6 expression compared to matched sudden-death controls.	Some validation needed. Studies on correlation between the effects in the hippocampal and non-/low invasive matrices is wanted.	Possible future effect marker if the altered gene expression can be found non/low invasive matrices. Furthermore, association with the AOs (cochlear function and cognitive function) have not been shown and further studies are needed to confirm this association.	[5] Reemst et al. 2022
Clock gene expression (Bmal1, Bmal2, Cry1, Cry2, Per1, Per2, and Rev-erb α)	Postmortem mice hippocampus samples	real-time qPCR	An Alzheimer's mouse model (Tg-SwDI) had reduced clock gene expression in hippocampus compared to controls. Alzheimer's patients often have disrupted circadian activity (day/night cyclus), and the day/night cyclus may be important for the cognitive function. The clock genes are regulating the molecular clock and the circadian rhythms.	The effect marker needs to be validated in humans, and it needs to be tested if the altered gene expression can be found in non/low invasive matrices	Possible future effect, if validated in humans, and if the altered gene expression can be found non/low invasive matrices.	[6] Fusilier et al. 2021
Fez1, Fez2, Bcap31 and Kmt2a gene expression	Postmortem mice hippocampus samples	qPCR and RNA-sequencing	Heart failure mouse model (CamkII δ c TG) had reduced cognitive function and hippocampus-dependent memory impairment compared to the controls. 1,780 genes were upregulated and 2,014 genes were down-regulated in the CamkII δ c TG mice compared to the control	The effect marker needs to be validated in humans, and it needs to be tested if the altered gene expression can be	The effect is found in a heart failair mouse model, and it need to be investigated if the same effect is seen in	[7] Islam et al. 2021

			<p>group. Especially the endoplasmic reticulum stress related genes Fez1, Fez2, and Bcap31 were increased and the H3K4-methyltransferase Kmt2a were decreased. Then CamkIIδc TG mice were treated with the histone deacetylase inhibitor Vorinostat had better hippocampus-dependent memory than non-treated mice, and the gene expression of Kmt2a were higher and non-significant compared to the control. Confirming that the cognitive function and hippocampus-dependent memory impairment is mediated through Kmt2a.</p>	found in non/low invasive matrices	other models with cognitive impairment.	
circRNA cdh9 and Trpc6 expression	Postmortem mice samples of hippocampus, cerebellum, prefrontal cortex, and amygdala	real-time qPCR Sanger sequencing	A mouse model for Autism spectrum disorder (BTBR) were used. Several genes were found to differ between autism mice and control, most convincing was the downregulation of Cdh9 and Trpc6, which both are implicated in neuronal development and maintenance, and are associated with ASD.	The effect marker needs to be validated in humans, and it needs to be tested if the altered gene expression can be found in non/low invasive matrices	It needs to be investigated if the effect markers are only associated with autism or with cognitive function in general.	[8] Gasparini et al. 2020

References:

1. Morrison, C., et al., *Hippocampal grading provides higher classification accuracy for those in the AD trajectory than hippocampal volume*. Hum Brain Mapp, 2023. **44**(12): p. 4623-4633. DOI: 10.1002/hbm.26407
2. Ginsberg, S.D., et al., *Brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) and TrkB hippocampal gene expression are putative predictors of neuritic plaque and neurofibrillary tangle pathology*. Neurobiol Dis, 2019. **132**: p. 104540. DOI: 10.1016/j.nbd.2019.104540
3. Liu, N., et al., *Hippocampal transcriptome-wide association study and neurobiological pathway analysis for Alzheimer's disease*. PLoS Genet, 2021. **17**(2): p. e1009363. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pgen.1009363
4. Han, J., et al., *Alzheimer's disease-causing presenilin-1 mutations have deleterious effects on mitochondrial function*. Theranostics, 2021. **11**(18): p. 8855-8873. DOI: 10.7150/thno.59776
5. Reemst, K., et al., *Early-life stress lastingly impacts microglial transcriptome and function under basal and immune-challenged conditions*. Transl Psychiatry, 2022. **12**(1): p. 507. DOI: 10.1038/s41398-022-02265-6
6. Fusilier, A.R., et al., *Dysregulated clock gene expression and abnormal diurnal regulation of hippocampal inhibitory transmission and spatial memory in amyloid precursor protein transgenic mice*. Neurobiol Dis, 2021. **158**: p. 105454. DOI: 10.1016/j.nbd.2021.105454
7. Islam, M.R., et al., *Epigenetic gene expression links heart failure to memory impairment*. EMBO Mol Med, 2021. **13**(3): p. e11900. DOI: 10.15252/emmm.201911900
8. Gasparini, S., et al., *Differential Expression of Hippocampal Circular RNAs in the BTBR Mouse Model for Autism Spectrum Disorder*. Mol Neurobiol, 2020. **57**(5): p. 2301-2313. DOI: 10.1007/s12035-020-01878-6
9. Mustieles, V., et al., *BDNF as a potential mediator between childhood BPA exposure and behavioral function in adolescent boys from the INMA-Granada cohort*. Science of The Total Environment, 2022. **803**: p. 150014. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.150014>
10. Rodríguez-Carrillo, A., et al., *Implementation of effect biomarkers in human biomonitoring studies: A systematic approach synergizing toxicological and epidemiological knowledge*. International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health, 2023. **249**: p. 114140. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2023.114140>
11. Chang, X., et al., *High-Serum Brain-Derived Neurotrophic Factor Levels Are Associated With Decreased Risk of Poststroke Cognitive Impairment*. Stroke, 2024. DOI: 10.1161/strokeaha.123.044698

Effect markers for DNT-Thyroid related AOPs

In total, for the 11 DNT AOPs identified in AOPwiki, after the exclusion of duplicate MIEs/KEs, a total of 9 molecular initiating events (MIEs), 36 key events (KEs) and 4 adverse outcomes (AOs) were identified.

AOP 54: “Inhibition of Na⁺/I⁻ symporter (NIS) leads to learning and memory impairment” includes a MIE, 9 KE, and an AO and is WPHA/WNT Endorsed (OECD project 1.28), of which

- MIE (ID: 424) also included in AOP 134
- 3 KEs (ID: 277, 281, 280) are common (shared) with AOP 134,
- 3 KEs (ID: 277, 281, 280) are common (shared) with AOP 42,
- 2 KEs (ID: 281, 280) are common (shared) with AOP 152,
- 1 KEs (ID: 381) is common (shared) with AOP 12,
- 2 KEs (ID: 281,280) are common (shared) with AOP 8,
- 2 KEs (ID: 385,386) are common (shared) with AOP 13,
- 1 KEs (ID: 386) are common (shared) with AOP 17
- 2 KEs (ID 425, 851) only in AOP 54

We initiated our research from AOP 54 focusing on downstream KEs

- KE 851: Decrease of GABAergic interneurons
- KE 385: Decrease of synaptogenesis
- KE 386: Decrease of neuronal network function

KE 851: Decrease of GABAergic interneurons

Methods:

One of the identification criteria for GABAergic interneurons is their molecular markers including Ca-binding proteins such as Parvalbumin (PV). Methods described in the AOPwiki assess as main markers for GABAergic interneurons Parvalbumin (PV) and GABA (or GAD). They are typically assessed via immunohistochemistry techniques. PV is identified through immunohistochemistry staining, while GABA (or GAD) is detected using anti-GABA antibodies in immunohistochemistry assays. Protein levels on interneurons can be measured using ELISA kits, Western blotting, immunohistochemistry, and immunofluorescence methods. Those are mostly applied in in vitro and in vivo settings, not suitable for epidemiological studies.

Directly studying GABAergic interneurons in humans for epidemiological purposes would require non-invasive or minimally invasive methods such as neuroimaging (e.g., MRI, fMRI), electrophysiological measurements (e.g., EEG, MEG), or perhaps analysis of peripheral markers (e.g., blood biomarkers) associated with GABA function.

We searched PubMed for potential effect markers using the search string in Text box 1 on the 27-02- 2024.

Search: (GABAergic interneurons) AND (biomarker OR marker OR (effect marker) OR parvalbumin)
(("gabaergic"[All Fields] OR "gabaergics"[All Fields]) AND ("interneuron s"[All Fields] OR "interneuronal"[All Fields] OR "interneuronal"[All Fields] OR "interneurone"[All Fields] OR "interneurones"[All Fields] OR "interneurons"[MeSH Terms] OR "interneurons"[All Fields] OR "interneuron"[All Fields]) AND ("biomarker s"[All Fields] OR "biomarkers"[MeSH Terms] OR "biomarkers"[All Fields] OR "biomarker"[All Fields] OR ("marker"[All Fields] OR "markers"[All Fields]) OR ("effect"[All Fields] OR "effecting"[All Fields] OR "effective"[All Fields] OR "effectively"[All Fields] OR "effectiveness"[All Fields] OR "effectivenesses"[All Fields] OR "effectives"[All Fields] OR "effectivities"[All Fields] OR "effectivity"[All Fields] OR "effects"[All Fields]) AND ("marker"[All Fields] OR "markers"[All Fields])) OR ("parvalbumins"[MeSH Terms] OR "parvalbumins"[All Fields] OR "parvalbumin"[All Fields])) AND ((bookdocs))

Filters applied: Books and Documents, Case Reports, Classical Article, Clinical Study, Clinical Trial, Clinical Trial Protocol, Clinical Trial, Phase I, Clinical Trial, Phase II, Clinical Trial, Phase III, Clinical Trial, Phase IV, Clinical Trial, Veterinary, Comparative Study, Controlled Clinical Trial, Meta-Analysis, Observational Study, Observational Study, Veterinary, Randomized Controlled Trial, Humans, Other Animals, English, from 2018 - 2025

Retrieved 7 results.

Results and discussion:

Table 1

Effect marker	Matrix	Measurement methods	"Description of association with KE or AO in humans or if stated validation of measurement/effect marker"	"Recommended for human epidemiological studies (Why, why not) "	Reference
Perineuronal nets (PNNs)	brain	immunohistochemical or immunofluorescent staining with the lectin Wisteria floribunda agglutinin (WFA) and Vicia villosa agglutinin (VVA) that recognise the N-acetyl-galactosamine (GalNAc) residues within chondroitin sulfate chains. Quantification of PNNs is typically determined through 1) number counts of PNNs, 2) intensity of PNNs, and 3) colocalization of PNNs and parvalbumin (PV) neurons.	PNNs, intricate extracellular matrix structures composed of chondroitin sulfate proteoglycans, affect the firing rates of cortical inhibitory interneurons. They play a pivotal role in mood disorders like depression, impacting social memory and the balance between excitatory and inhibitory signals. These nets, formed by both neurons and nearby glial cells, envelop neurons to provide protection, regulate synaptic plasticity, and maintain the excitatory/inhibitory balance crucial for efficient brain function. Microglia contribute to PNN structure maintenance through MMP9 secretion, suggesting a link between chronic stress and alterations in PNN architecture.	Invasive requires incisions of the brain or intracranial injection, not recommended for human epidemiological studies	Morphett, J. C., et al., 2024
Dlx1, Dlx2, and Nkx2.1 genes	brain	RNA extraction and 96.96 Fluidigm integrated fluidic circuit with TaqMan assays	Changes in the expression of certain genes linked to GABAergic interneurons, like Dlx1, Dlx2, and Nkx2.1, can affect the migration and maturation of these neurons. This disruption can disturb the balance between excitatory and inhibitory signaling in the brain, potentially heightening vulnerability to obstetric complications in the fetus. Altered gene expression may also lead to an imbalance in GABAergic neuron subtypes, such as PV and SST, disrupting the regulation of inhibitory input across different neuron regions. GABAergic markers exhibit gestationally-specific, region-specific, and sometimes sex-specific patterns. Disruptions in GABAergic markers correlate with distinct behavioral traits, including memory, sensorimotor gating, anxiety, and sociability.	Invasive method as it requires RNA extraction, not recommended for human epidemiological studies	Gillespie, B., et al., 2023
Expression of GABA-related Genes: Dlx1, Dlx2, and Nkx2.1,	blood	RT-pcr	Changes in the expression levels of genes related to GABAergic neuron development and function, including those governing GABA synthesis, metabolism, release, reuptake, and receptor expression, can act as indicators of alterations. Significant changes in genes like Dlx1, Dlx2, and Nkx2.1, vital for GABAergic neuron migration and maturation, may signal disruptions.	Invasive method as it requires blood samples, not recommended for human epidemiological studies	Richard, S., et al., 2023
Perineuronal nets (PNNs), including protein tyrosine	brain		Perineuronal nets (PNN) are predominantly located in GABAergic interneurons with Parvalbumin, vital for synaptic functions and neuroprotection. Their regulation involves	Invasive method as it requires brain samples, not recommended for	Dong, Y., et al., 2023

phosphatase α (PTP α), orthodenticle homeo-box 2 (Otx2), erb-b2 receptor tyrosine kinase 4 (ErbB4), and Glycosaminoglycan (GAG)			factors like PTP α , Otx2, ErbB4, and glycosaminoglycan (GAG). PNN abnormalities correlate with aging and neurological diseases like Alzheimer's, Parkinson's, schizophrenia, autism, and multiple sclerosis, yet their relationship with aging and related diseases remains underexplored.	human epidemiological studies	
Glu and Glx (combination of glutamate and glutamine in MDD) and gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA)	brain	1H MRS	Glu and GABA are involved in major depressive disorder (MDD), with MDD often showing decreased GABA levels or fewer GABAergic interneurons, potentially resulting in excessive Glu release. Whether Glu release or turnover increases in depression is still uncertain.	Recommended for human epidemiological studies as the methods examined (1H MRS) are non-invasive and are recommended for human epidemiological studies	Kantrowitz, J. T., et al., 2021
Parvalbumin cell density and parvalbumin mRNA levels	brain	Quantitative meta-analysis of the data on parvalbumin cell density and parvalbumin mRNA levels in pre-frontal regions in the brains of patients with schizophrenia compared with healthy controls.	Parvalbumin interneurons, characterized by their fast-spiking and GABAergic nature, play a critical role in inhibiting cortical and subcortical circuits. They are considered a central point in the pathophysiology of schizophrenia.	Invasive method as it requires brain samples, not recommended for human epidemiological studies	Kaar, S. J., et al., 2019
Neuropeptide Y (NPY) expressed in GABAergic and calretinin-immunoreactive (-ir) amacrine cells	retina	Immunohistochemistry, confocal microscopy and 3D reconstructions	Neuropeptide Y (NPY), a widely present peptide neurotransmitter in the mammalian retina, plays roles in both development and modulation during the prenatal and perinatal periods. In adults, NPY is suggested to modify neurotransmission, including inhibiting Ca ²⁺ influx in neurons and affecting spatial tuning and spiking activity in ganglion cells. The detailed distribution and connections of NPY-ir cells underline NPY's significant role in retinal functionality.	Not recommended for human epidemiological studies as immunohistochemistry is an invasive method	Christiansen, A. T., et al., 2019

Morphett et al., (2024): Investigates the use of Perineuronal Nets (PNNs) as effect markers, towards the development of neurological diseases. PNNs in the brain can be considered as effect markers, which can be identified with the use of various methods, including immunohistochemistry and immunofluorescence. The suggested methods presented in this study are considered to be invasive as they require incisions of the brain or intracranial injection.

Gillespie, B., et al., (2024): Focuses on Dlx1, Dlx2 and Nkx2.1 genes, alterations of which can impact the migration and maturation of the GABAergic interneurons. To this aim, this study reviews current literature focusing on GABAergic interneuron changes in the maternal immune activation (MIA) on the prefrontal cortex and hippocampus. Changes in GABAergic markers were revealed, concurrent with distinct behavioral phenotypes. According to the results of the study, the maternal immune activation model proved to be a valid tool for testing novel therapeutics designed to recover GABAergic function. The methods presented in this study require RNA extraction, which is an invasive method, not recommended for human epidemiological studies.

Richard, S., et al., (2023): Aims to unravel the mechanisms of action of thyroid hormone in the developing brain which would assist the prevention and treatment of several neurological disorders, including autism and epilepsy. An association between GABAergic maturation and thyroid hormone action is reported, aiming to move toward the prevention and treatment of neurological disorders. According to the results of this study, changes in the expression levels of genes relevant to GABAergic neuron development and function, such as those involved in GABA synthesis, metabolism, release, reuptake, and receptor expression, can serve as markers of alterations. Alterations in the expression of genes, including *Dlx1*, *Dlx2*, and *Nkx2.1* could indicate disruptions. The methodology used in this study is also considered to be invasive with the collection of blood samples, and thus not recommended for human epidemiological studies.

Dong, Y., et al., (2023): On the same track with Morphett et al., this study aims to investigate the use of perineuronal nets (PNNs) as effect markers, towards the development of neurological diseases. According to the results, PNN plays a pivotal role in aging and neurological disorders. The methodology reported in this study proved to be invasive and thus not recommended for human epidemiological studies, as they required the collection of brain samples.

Kantrowitz et al., (2021): Focuses on the use of glutamate, glutamine and gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) as effect markers towards the diagnosis of major depressive disorder, using the ^1H MRS method. According to the results of the study, the use of ^1H MRS is an appropriate method for the examination of Glx, Glu and GABA levels, linked to MDD cases. The methodology presented in this study is recommended for human epidemiological studies as the methods reported (^1H MRS) are non-invasive and are recommended for human epidemiological studies.

Kaar, S.J., et al., (2019): Focuses on the reduction of the density of parvalbumin interneurons in the frontal cortex associated with patients with schizophrenia. According to the results of the study, changes in the parvalbumin cell density proved to be an appropriate effect marker, although the methodology followed in this study is not recommended for human epidemiological studies as it requires the collection of brain samples, which is considered to be an invasive method.

Christiansen, A.T., et al., (2018): Focuses on the evaluation and comparison of NPY-expressing cells of human and porcine retina. Neuropeptide Y (NPY) was found to be expressed in GABAergic and calretinin-immunoreactive (-ir) amacrine cells. According to the results of this study, NPY-expressing cells were highly comparable in both human porcine retina. The methodology presented in this study is not recommended for human epidemiological studies as immunohistochemistry is an invasive method

Conclusion

For epidemiological studies in humans, where a non-invasive, large-scale application is necessary, the examination of Glu, Glx and GABA with the use of prefrontal proton magnetic resonance spectroscopy (^1H MRS) studied in Kantrowitz, J.T., et al. (2021) could be the most promising. The levels of Glu and Glx can be easily measured with ^1H MRS, while Glx could be a marker of depression severity.

References:

1. Morphett, J. C., Whittaker, A. L., Reichelt, A. C., & Hutchinson, M. R. (2024). Perineuronal net structure as a non-cellular mechanism contributing to affective state: A scoping review. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, 105568.
2. Gillespie, B., Panthi, S., Sundram, S., & Hill, R. A. (2023). The Impact of Maternal Immune Activation on GABAergic Interneuron Development: A Systematic Review of Rodent Studies and their Translational Implications. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, 105488.
3. Richard, S., Ren, J., & Flamant, F. (2023). Thyroid hormone action during GABAergic neuron maturation: The quest for mechanisms. *Frontiers in Endocrinology*, 14, 1256877.
4. Dong, Y., Zhao, K., Qin, X., Du, G., & Gao, L. (2023). The mechanisms of perineuronal net abnormalities in contributing aging and neurological diseases. *Ageing Research Reviews*, 102092.
5. Kantrowitz, J. T., Dong, Z., Milak, M. S., Rashid, R., Kegeles, L. S., Javitt, D. C., ... & John Mann, J. (2021). Ventromedial prefrontal cortex/anterior cingulate cortex Glx, glutamate, and GABA levels in medication-free major depressive disorder. *Translational psychiatry*, 11(1), 419.
6. Kaar, S. J., Angelescu, I., Marques, T. R., & Howes, O. D. (2019). Pre-frontal parvalbumin interneurons in schizophrenia: a meta-analysis of post-mortem studies. *Journal of Neural Transmission*, 126, 1637-1651.
7. Christiansen, A. T., Kiilgaard, J. F., Klemp, K., Woldbye, D. P. D., & Hannibal, J. (2018). Localization, distribution, and connectivity of neuropeptide Y in the human and porcine retinas—A comparative study. *Journal of Comparative Neurology*, 526(12), 1877-1895.

KE 385: Decrease of synaptogenesis

Methods:

Synaptogenesis markers described in the AOPwiki, consist of VGLUTs, PSD-95, VGAT, VIAAT, gephyrin, MAP-2, synaptophysin, Bassoon, and ProSAP1/Shank2. They are assessed through immunostaining, commercial assay kits, electron microscopy, and high-content image analysis, incorporating RNAi screening protocols. Immunostaining detects VGLUTs and PSD-95 for excitatory synapses, VGAT, VIAAT, and gephyrin for inhibitory synapses. MAP-2, PSD-95, and synaptophysin are utilized in commercial kits. Bassoon and ProSAP1/Shank2 are indicative of ultrastructural studies. Electron microscopy provides detailed evaluation. High-content image analysis, including RNAi screening, facilitates synaptic punctae analysis.

We searched PubMed for potential effect markers using the search string on the 27-02-2025

Search: synaptogenesis AND (biomarker OR marker OR (effect marker))
 ("synaptogenesis"[All Fields] AND ("biomarker s"[All Fields] OR "biomarkers"[MeSH Terms] OR "biomarkers"[All Fields] OR "biomarker"[All Fields] OR ("marker"[All Fields] OR "markers"[All Fields]) OR ("effect"[All Fields] OR "effecting"[All Fields] OR "effective"[All Fields] OR "effectively"[All Fields] OR "effectiveness"[All Fields] OR "effectivenesses"[All Fields] OR "effectives"[All Fields] OR "effectivities"[All Fields] OR "effectivity"[All Fields] OR "effects"[All Fields]) AND ("marker"[All Fields] OR "markers"[All Fields]))) AND ((booksdocs))

applying the following filters
 Filters applied: Books and Documents, Case Reports, Classical Article, Clinical Study, Clinical Trial, Clinical Trial Protocol, Clinical Trial, Phase I, Clinical Trial, Phase II, Clinical Trial, Phase III, Clinical Trial, Phase IV, Clinical Trial, Veterinary, Comparative Study, Controlled Clinical Trial, Meta-Analysis, Observational Study, Observational Study, Veterinary, Randomized Controlled Trial, Humans, Other Animals, English, from 2018 - 2025

Results and discussion:

Table 2

Effect marker	Matrix	Measurement methods	Description of association with KE or AO in humans or if stated validation of measurement/effect marker	Recommended for human epidemiological studies (Why, why not)	Reference

alanine (Ala), ascorbate (Asc), aspartate (Asp), creatine (Cr), phosphocreatine (PCr), γ -aminobutyric acid (GABA), glucose (Glc), glutamine (Gln), glutamate (Glu), glutathione (GSH), glycine (Gly), myo-inositol (Ins), lactate (Lac), N-acetylaspartate (NAA), N-acetylaspartylglutamate (NAAG), phosphoethanolamine (PE), taurine (Tau), and glycerophosphocholine + phosphocholine (GPC + PC). In addition, PCr/Cr and Glu/Gln concentration ratios were determined.		H MRS and histochemical analysis. In vivo 1H MR spectroscopy (MRS) was performed in spontaneously breathing rats. Multi-slice fast spin-echo MRI was used for precise positioning of the volume of interest (VOI) in the dorsal hippocampus. LASER localization sequence (TE = 15 ms, TR = 5 s, number of transients = 160) combined with VAPOR water suppression was used to acquire MRS data. Metabolites were quantified using LCModel with the spectrum of fast relaxing macromolecules included in the basis set	Neurochemical Markers: Changes in like N-acetylaspartate (NAA), glutamate (Glu), and gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) indicated disruptions in neuronal health and neurotransmission, essential for synapse formation and maintenance, suggesting impaired neuronal function and potential decreases in synaptogenesis. Energy Metabolism Markers: Abnormalities in phosphocreatine (PCr) to creatine (Cr) ratios and glucose levels highlighted disturbances in energy metabolism within the hippocampus. Since synaptic activity and plasticity are energy-dependent, these abnormalities suggested that hyperglycemia might impair the processes critical for synaptogenesis. Inflammatory Markers: Elevated levels of ionized calcium-binding adapter molecule 1 (Iba1) pointed to increased microglial activation and inflammation in the hippocampus. Given that inflammation can negatively impact neuronal function and synaptic development, this suggested a link between increased inflammation and reduced synaptogenesis.	possibly, non-invasive imaging technique, time consuming	McClure Yauch, L., et al., 2022
	brain	Synaptogenesis assessed through immunohistochemical analysis, microglial activation determined using ionized calcium binding adapter molecule 1 (Iba1) histochemistry, and dendritic structure in the hippocampus is evaluated by staining for microtubule-associated protein-2 (MAP2), with the mean integrated density of MAP-2 in CA1, CA3, and dentate gyrus quantified using software.	Structural Markers: Alterations in dendritic structure, as indicated by microtubule-associated protein-2 (MAP2) staining, directly reflected changes in the framework necessary for forming synaptic connections. The observed impairments in dendritic arborization due to neonatal hyperglycemia were indicative of decreased synaptogenesis.	invasive	
Cognitive stimulation		questionnaire indicators of cognitive stimulation at work: job demands and job control.	two-stage approach to investigate the association of cognitively stimulating work with dementia risk. Analysis 1 employed Cox regression and meta-analysis techniques to examine associations, stratified by various factors such as gender, age, and dementia onset. They also assessed the robustness of findings and potential biases through alternative analyses. Analysis 2 focused on the association of plasma proteins with cognitive stimulation levels, utilizing logistic regression and adjusting for ethnicity and APOE genotype. Analysis 3 investigated the association between proteins surviving correction and dementia risk using Cox proportional hazards models, addressing potential survival bias. Post hoc analyses examined the effect of cognitive stimulation across the life course on incident dementia. The statistical analyses were conducted using SAS and Stata software packages.	indirect marker. Multicohort study with three sets of analyses.	Kivimäki, M. et al., 2021
proteins	plasma	SomaScan version 4 assay	A multicohort study involving over 100,000 participants indicates that individuals in cognitively stimulating occupations are less likely to develop dementia in later life compared to those in less stimulating roles. This correlation may be due to cognitive stimulation's link to reduced plasma protein levels, which could otherwise hinder axon and synapse formation and elevate the risk of dementia in old age.	indirect marker. Multicohort study with three sets of analyses.	
Immunostaining analysis involved staining for specific		For iPSC colony staining, cells were fixed and then incubated with primary	Overall, these comprehensive approaches allowed for the measurement of synaptogenesis in iPSC-derived cerebral	neurotransmitter currents and functional response of channel	Logan, S. et al., 2020

<p>neuronal markers such as MAP2 and PAX6, as well as synaptic markers like synapsin I.</p>		<p>antibodies against OCT4 (a pluripotent stem cell marker) and MAP2 (a neuron-specific marker). Subsequently, secondary antibodies conjugated with Alexa Fluor dyes were applied. The stained cells were visualized and imaged using laser scanning confocal microscopy. For cerebral organoids, similar procedures were followed, staining for markers such as PAX6 (a neural stem cell marker), MAP2 (a neuron-specific marker), S100B (an astrocyte marker), synapsin I (a synaptic marker), smooth muscle actin (a smooth muscle cell marker), and CD31 (an endothelial cell marker).</p>	<p>organoids at various levels, including structural, molecular, and functional aspects.</p>	<p>activities observed in cerebral organoids, hold some promise for epidemiological studies on synaptogenesis effects. The ability to measure these biomarkers in a controlled laboratory setting, using a model system that closely mimics human brain development and function, provides an opportunity to study synaptogenesis in a more clinically relevant manner. Additionally, the comparison of these biomarkers between human iPSC-derived cerebral organoids and samples from human fetal and adult brains enhances the credibility and applicability of this model for understanding brain development, physiology, and disorders, making it a valuable tool for epidemiological investigations into synaptogenesis effects.</p>	
<p>Electron microscopy was employed to analyze synapse structure within the cerebral organoids.</p>		<p>fixed cerebral organoids were processed for electron microscopy to examine the ultrastructure of synapses. The organoids were fixed, dehydrated, embedded in epoxy resin, and sectioned into 60 nm thick slices. These slices were then stained with lead citrate and uranyl acetate. Finally, the samples were imaged using an electron microscope to visualize the synaptic structures.</p>			
<p>mRNA expression profiling using microarray analysis and ingenuity pathway analysis (IPA) bioinformatic analysis provided insights into gene expression related to synaptic development and function.</p>		<p>Total RNA was isolated from cerebral organoids, and cDNA was synthesized using reverse transcription. Quantitative real-time PCR (qRT-PCR) was performed using specific primers targeting genes of interest related to synaptogenesis, including MAP2, OCT4, S100B, and various sodium channel genes. The expression levels of these genes were measured and normalized to a housekeeping gene (GAPDH). The fold change in gene expression was determined compared to iPSCs.</p>			
<p>Electrophysiology analysis assessed action potential and channel activities, including recording glutamate, NMDA, and GABA currents, which are indicative of synaptic transmission.</p>		<p>Cerebral organoids were sliced and prepared for whole-cell patch clamp recordings to measure neuronal activity and synaptic function. Patch pipettes filled with specific solutions were used to record various currents, including Na⁺ and K⁺ currents, glutamate currents, NMDA currents, and GABA currents. These</p>			

		recordings were performed under specific voltage or current clamp conditions, and data were acquired and analyzed using patch clamp amplifiers and software.			
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McClure Yauch, L., et al. (2022): Uses a comprehensive range of neurochemical markers measured by in vivo ¹H MR spectroscopy (MRS), including N-acetylaspartate (NAA), glutamate (Glu), and gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA), along with energy metabolism markers like phosphocreatine (PCr) to creatine (Cr) ratios. Also, inflammatory markers indicated by ionized calcium-binding adapter molecule 1 (Iba1), and structural markers highlighted by microtubule-associated protein-2 (MAP2) are utilized to assess changes in the hippocampus that correlate with synaptogenesis.

Kivimäki, M., et al. (2021): Focuses on cognitive stimulation and the association with plasma proteins, suggesting a relationship between cognitive activities and the levels of plasma proteins that might inhibit axonogenesis and synaptogenesis, potentially serving as biomarkers for cognitive health and risk of dementia.

Logan, S., et al. (2020): Uses immunostaining of specific neuronal and synaptic markers like MAP2 and synapsin I, mRNA expression profiling of genes related to synaptogenesis, and electrophysiological assessments of synaptic transmission in cerebral organoids. These markers provide a multi-level assessment of synaptogenesis in a controlled laboratory setting.

Conclusion

For epidemiological studies in humans, where non-invasive, large-scale application is necessary, the plasma proteins associated with cognitive stimulation levels studied in Kivimäki, M., et al. (2021) could be the most promising. These proteins can be easily measured in blood samples and may offer insight into cognitive health and the brain's synaptic activity. Given that this study involves a multicohort with a large number of participants, it aligns well with the requirements for epidemiological assessments.

In contrast, while comprehensive and informative, the markers used in McClure Yauch, L., et al. (2022) and Logan, S., et al. (2020) might be more suited to controlled experimental settings or specific clinical assessments rather than large-scale epidemiological studies due to their invasive nature or the complex methodologies involved.

References:

1. McClure Yauch, L., Ennis-Czerniak, K., Frey li, W. H., Tkac, I. & Rao, R. B. Intranasal Insulin Attenuates the Long-Term Adverse Effects of Neonatal Hyperglycemia on the Hippocampus in Rats. *Dev. Neurosci.* 44, 590–602 (2022).
2. Kivimäki, M. et al. Cognitive stimulation in the workplace, plasma proteins, and risk of dementia: three analyses of population cohort studies. *BMJ* 374, n1804 (2021).
3. Logan, S. et al. Dynamic Characterization of Structural, Molecular, and Electrophysiological Phenotypes of Human-Induced Pluripotent Stem Cell-Derived Cerebral Organoids, and Comparison with Fetal and Adult Gene Profiles. *Cells* 9, (2020).

KE 386: Decrease of neuronal network function

Methods:

The decrease of neuronal network function as described in the AOPwiki can be measured using in vivo and in vitro methodologies. In vivo methodologies include the recording of brain activity by using electroencephalography (EEG), electrocorticography (ECoG) and local field potentials (LFP) to assist in the collection of signals generated by multiple

neuronal cell networks. In vitro methodologies require the use of Microelectrode array (MEA) recordings which can be applied in high throughput platforms to facilitate screening of numerous chemical compounds. Additionally, the patch clamping technique can also be used to measure neuronal network activity.

We consider only in vivo methods described in AOPwiki, potentially appropriate for epidemiological studies.

We searched PubMed for potential effect markers using the search string on the 27-02-2025

Search: (neuronal network function) AND (biomarker OR marker OR (effect marker) OR synaptic) AND epidemiological)

((("neuron s"[All Fields] OR "neuronal"[All Fields] OR "neuronally"[All Fields] OR "neuronal s"[All Fields] OR "neurone s"[All Fields] OR "neurones"[All Fields] OR "neuronic"[All Fields] OR "neurons"[MeSH Terms] OR "neurons"[All Fields] OR "neuron"[All Fields] OR "neurone"[All Fields]) AND ("network"[All Fields] OR "network s"[All Fields] OR "networked"[All Fields] OR "networker"[All Fields] OR "networkers"[All Fields] OR "networking"[All Fields] OR "networks"[All Fields]) AND ("functional"[All Fields] OR "functional s"[All Fields] OR "functionalities"[All Fields] OR "functionality"[All Fields] OR "functionalization"[All Fields] OR "functionalizations"[All Fields] OR "functionalize"[All Fields] OR "functionalized"[All Fields] OR "functionalizes"[All Fields] OR "functionalizing"[All Fields] OR "functionally"[All Fields] OR "functionals"[All Fields] OR "functioned"[All Fields] OR "functioning"[All Fields] OR "functionings"[All Fields] OR "functions"[All Fields] OR "physiology"[MeSH Subheading] OR "physiology"[All Fields] OR "function"[All Fields] OR "physiology"[MeSH Terms]) AND ("biomarker s"[All Fields] OR "biomarkers"[MeSH Terms] OR "biomarkers"[All Fields] OR "biomarker"[All Fields] OR "marker"[All Fields] OR "markers"[All Fields]) OR (("effect"[All Fields] OR "effecting"[All Fields] OR "effective"[All Fields] OR "effectively"[All Fields] OR "effectiveness"[All Fields] OR "effectivenesses"[All Fields] OR "effectives"[All Fields] OR "effectivities"[All Fields] OR "effectivity"[All Fields] OR "effects"[All Fields]) AND ("marker"[All Fields] OR "markers"[All Fields])) OR ("synaptic"[All Fields] OR "synaptical"[All Fields] OR "synaptically"[All Fields])) AND ("epidemiologically"[All Fields] OR "epidemiology"[MeSH Terms] OR "epidemiology"[All Fields] OR "epidemiologic"[All Fields] OR "epidemiological"[All Fields]))

applying the following filters

Filters applied: Books and Documents, Case Reports, Classical Article, Clinical Study, Clinical Trial, Clinical Trial Protocol, Clinical Trial, Phase I, Clinical Trial, Phase II, Clinical Trial, Phase III, Clinical Trial, Phase IV, Clinical Trial, Veterinary, Comparative Study, Controlled Clinical Trial, Meta-Analysis, Observational Study, Observational Study, Veterinary, Randomized Controlled Trial, Humans, Other Animals, English, from 2018 - 2025

Results and discussion:

Table 3

Effect marker	Matrix	Measurement methods	Description of association with KE or AO in humans or if stated validation of measurement/effect marker	Recommended for human epidemiological studies (Why, why not)	Reference
Three brain tissues: the frontal cortex, the striatum, and the substantia nigra	brain	Selection of sex-labeled transcriptomic data from three relevant brain tissues: the frontal cortex, the striatum, and the substantia nigra. Performing differential expression analysis on each study chosen and summary of the individual differential expression results with three tissue-specific meta-analyses and a global all-tissues meta-analysis. Finally, results from the meta-analysis were functionally characterized using different functional profiling approaches.	Parkinson's disease significantly affects the frontal cortex, striatum tissue, and substantia nigra, leading to the degeneration of dopaminergic neurons and formation of Lewy bodies. This results in motor symptoms and non-motor impairments like cognitive and mood disorders, with about a third of advanced-stage patients developing dementia.	Invasive method, not recommended for human epidemiological studies as it requires the collection of brain samples.	López-Cerdán, A., et al., 2022
Cerebrospinal fluid biomarkers (protein 14-3-3) for sporadic Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease (sCJD).	Cerebrospinal fluid	IQ-CSF RT-QuIC assay in six out of seven studies.	the CSF prion real-time quaking-induced conversion (RT-QuIC) assay has shown superior diagnostic value, boasting near-perfect specificity (99–100%) along with satisfactory to excellent sensitivity.	Invasive method, not recommended for human epidemiological studies as it requires collections of CSF samples.	Rübsamen, N., et al., 2022
Cerebrospinal fluid biomarkers in Down	Cerebrospinal fluid	Neuropsychological, neuroimaging, genetic,	Studies on Down syndrome have	Invasive method, not	Fagan, A. M., et al., 2021

Syndrome and autosomal dominant Alzheimer's disease		and fluid biomarker measures	reported biomarkers of Alzheimer's disease, including amyloid (measured by CSF amyloid β 1–42 [A β 1–42] and PET imaging), phosphorylated tau processes (via CSF tau phosphorylated at threonine 181 [p-tau181] and tau PET imaging), neuronal damage (through CSF total tau and neurofilament light chain [NFL]), and brain atrophy (assessed with MRI).	recommended for human epidemiological studies as it requires collections of CSF samples.	
Integrating expression quantitative trait locus data implicated 15 genes robustly linked to bipolar disorder via gene expression, encoding druggable targets such as HTR6, MCHR1, DCLK3 and FURIN	Brain and whole blood sample	GWAS, TWAS, eQTL integrative analysis	isk alleles for bipolar disorder are mainly found in genes related to synaptic signaling and specific to neurons in the prefrontal cortex and hippocampus, with a strong link to genes targeted by medications like antipsychotics. Analysis combining genetic data highlights 15 genes strongly connected to bipolar disorder, offering potential targets such as HTR6, MCHR1, DCLK3, and FURIN	Invasive method, not recommended for human epidemiological studies as it requires collections of brain and blood samples.	Mullins, N., et al., 2021
Genes: LRRC55, PCDH9, NALCN, RYR3, ELAVL2, CDH13, ATP1A2, SLC17A5, ANO3, PCDH19, EFNA5	DNA	Single-nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) microarray to detect copy-number variations (CNVs).	Severe motor and developmental encephalopathy syndromes with unclear causes may arise from the phenotypic convergence due to multiple genetic mutations in genes linked to neurological pathogenic processes.	Invasive method, not recommended for human epidemiological studies as it requires DNA extraction.	García-Hernández, J. L., et al., 2021
AD Cerebrospinal fluid	Cerebrospinal fluid	Genetic analysis, CSF analysis, PET and MRI methods, neuropsychiatric assessments	Neuropsychiatric symptoms (NPS) in cognitively intact carriers of DIAD mutations could signal future metabolic decline in brain networks susceptible to Alzheimer's disease (AD), reinforcing the idea that NPS are early indicators of neuronal damage in AD..	Invasive method, not recommended for human epidemiological studies as it requires collections of CSF samples.	Ng, K. P., et al., 2021
Serum 25-hydroxyvitamin-D (25(OH)D), cotinine (smoking biomarker), and anti-Epstein-Barr virus nuclear antigen 1 (EBNA-1) immunoglobulin G (IgG)	Serum	ELISA	Reduced vitamin D levels and smoking following the clinical onset of multiple sclerosis (MS) have been linked to poorer long-term cognitive function and neuronal health.	Invasive method, not recommended for human epidemiological studies as it requires collections of serum samples.	Cortese, M., et al., 2020
CSF neurogranin, total tau, neurofilament light (NFL) and 14-3-3 protein	Cerebrospinal fluid	Neurogranin and NFL were quantified using two in-house ELISA, monoclonal neurogranin antibody Ng2 was used (1:400) for immunohistochemistry (IHC), brain homogenates,	Neurogranin has emerged as a novel biomarker for prion pathogenesis, offering diagnostic and prognostic capabilities by indicating the extent of neuronal damage in brain tissue, specific to	Invasive method, not recommended for human epidemiological studies as it requires collections of CSF samples.	Blennow, K., et al., 2019

		subcellular fractionation, and western blot.	different subtypes of Creutzfeldt-Jakob Disease (CJD).		
APP metabolism/A β formation, tau protein binding, lipid metabolism, immune response	Brain and blood tissue types, including all immune-related cell types, most specifically myeloid cells (macrophages and monocytes) and B-lymphoid cells	eQTL analysis, SNP-wise gene analysis, GWAS meta-analysis	Pathway analysis highlights the roles of immunity, lipid metabolism, tau binding proteins, and amyloid precursor protein (APP) metabolism, indicating that genetic variations influencing APP and A β processing are linked to both early-onset autosomal dominant Alzheimer's disease and late-onset Alzheimer's disease (LOAD).	Invasive method, not recommended for human epidemiological studies as it requires collections of tissue samples, including brain tissue.	Kunkle, B. W., et al., 2019
Six non-invasive urinary proteins including vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) and its receptor VEGFR1, matrix metalloproteinase-2 (MMP2), MMP9, neutrophil gelatinase-associated lipocalin (NGAL, Lipocalin 2), and the MMP9/NGAL complex	Urine	Total protein concentration was assessed using the Bradford method, and monospecific enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays (ELISAs; Quantikine; R&D Systems, Inc., Minneapolis, MN). Additionally, an MRI technique called Diffusion tensor imaging (DTI) was conducted.	Higher MMP9 or MMP9/NGAL in UCPPS may contribute to neuronal damage in brainstem nuclei through excitotoxicity and enhance synaptic plasticity in sensorimotor regions.	Non invasive method, recommended for human epidemiological studies as it requires only collection of urine samples	Woodworth, D. C., et al., 2018
ITGA9 and NRXN3	Blood	Analysis of single-nucleotide polymorphism (SNP)	ITGA9 is responsible for coding a neurotrophin receptor on cell membranes, and NRXN3 functions as a neuronal adhesion transmembrane receptor crucial for the development of synapses..	Invasive method, not recommended for human epidemiological studies as it requires collections of blood samples.	Fabbi, C., et al., 2018
Mean amyloid load, glucose metabolism, and gray matter volume		AV45-PET, FDG-PET, MRI and the additional use of Multimodal Markov random field models	The posterior cingulate cortex is recognized as the central hub connected to multiple regions, supporting the "wear-and-tear" hypothesis of disease susceptibility.	Non invasive method, recommended for human epidemiological studies as it requires the use of AV45-PET, FDG-PET, MRI and the additional use of Multimodal Markov random field models	Dyrba, M., et al., 2018

López-Cerdán, A., et al., (2022): Focuses on three brain tissues, including the frontal cortex, the striatum, and the substantia nigra for their use as effect markers for Parkinson's disease, based on gender. Based on the results reported in this study, sex proves to play a pivotal role in differential mechanisms known for Parkinson's disease, including inflammation, mitochondrial dysfunction and oxidative stress. The methodology presented in this study is considered to be invasive as it requires collection of brain samples, and thus cannot be recommended for human epidemiological studies.

Four studies published between 2019 and 2022 identified cerebrospinal fluid as a biomarker for Creutzfeldt–Jakob disease (sCJD) and Alzheimer's disease, with various methods, including the IQ-CSF RT-QuIC assay, neuroimaging techniques, genetic analysis and ELISA (Rübsamen et al., 2022; Fagan et al., 2021; Ng et al., 2021; Blennow et al., 2019). All these studies are

considered to use invasive methods with the collection of CSF samples and are not recommended for human epidemiological studies.

Woodworth, et al., (2018): Focuses on the investigation of six urinary proteins as potential biomarkers for UCPPS, with the use of various non-invasive assays. Diffusion tensor imaging (DTI) was also used in order to identify localized changes linked with changes in protein levels in Urological Pelvic Pain Syndrome, where it was shown that elevated MMP9 or MMp9/NGAL might be related to degenerative neuronal changes in brainstem nuclei through excitotoxicity. The methodology reported in this study is not invasive and is recommended for use in human epidemiological studies.

Dyrba, et al., (2018): Focuses on the investigation of the changes in mean amyloid load, glucose metabolism, and gray matter volume as biomarkers for Alzheimer's disease, detected with different neuroimaging methods, including AV45-PET, FDG-PET, MRI and Multimodal Markov random field models. This study is also recommended for human epidemiological studies as it does not report invasive methods.

Conclusion

For epidemiological studies in humans, where non-invasive, large-scale application is necessary, the urinary proteins associated with UCPPS reported in Woodworth, et al., (2018) could be the most promising. This study exhibits the use of various non-invasive assays and Diffusion tensor imaging (DTI), which are non-invasive methods. Additionally, according to the results reported in the Dyrba, et al., study (2018), changes in mean amyloid load, glucose metabolism, and gray matter volume can be used as biomarkers for AD. The non-invasive neuroimaging methods used in this study are and are highly recommended for use in human epidemiological studies.

References:

1. López-Cerdán, A. et al. Unveiling sex-based differences in Parkinson's disease: a comprehensive meta-analysis of transcriptomic studies. *Biol. Sex Differ.* 13, 68 (2022).
2. RübSamen, N. et al. Diagnostic accuracy of cerebrospinal fluid biomarkers for the differential diagnosis of sporadic Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease: a (network) meta-analysis. *Eur. J. Neurol.* 29, 1366–1376 (2022).
3. Fagan, A. M. et al. Comparison of CSF biomarkers in Down syndrome and autosomal dominant Alzheimer's disease: a cross-sectional study. *Lancet. Neurol.* 20, 615–626 (2021).
4. Mullins, N. et al. Genome-wide association study of more than 40,000 bipolar disorder cases provides new insights into the underlying biology. *Nat. Genet.* 53, 817–829 (2021).
5. García-Hernández, J. L. et al. Pathogenic convergence of CNVs in genes functionally associated to a severe neuromotor developmental delay syndrome. *Hum. Genomics* 15, 11 (2021).
6. Ng, K. P. et al. Neuropsychiatric symptoms are early indicators of an upcoming metabolic decline in Alzheimer's disease. *Transl. Neurodegener.* 10, 1 (2021).
7. Cortese, M. et al. Vitamin D, smoking, EBV, and long-term cognitive performance in MS: 11-year follow-up of BENEFIT. *Neurology* 94, e1950–e1960 (2020).
8. Blennow, K. et al. CSF neurogranin as a neuronal damage marker in CJD: a comparative study with AD. *J. Neurol. Neurosurg. Psychiatry* 90, 846–853 (2019).
9. Cade, B. E. et al. Associations of variants in the hexokinase 1 and interleukin 18 receptor regions with oxyhemoglobin saturation during sleep. *PLoS Genet.* 15, e1007739 (2019).
10. Kunkle, B. W. et al. Genetic meta-analysis of diagnosed Alzheimer's disease identifies new risk loci and implicates A β , tau, immunity and lipid processing. *Nat. Genet.* 51, 414–430 (2019).
11. Woodworth, D. C. et al. Changes in brain white matter structure are associated with urine proteins in urologic chronic pelvic pain syndrome (UCPPS): A MAPP Network study. *PLoS One* 13, e0206807 (2018).
12. Fabbri, C. et al. New insights into the pharmacogenomics of antidepressant response from the GENDEP and STAR*D studies: rare variant analysis and high-density imputation. *Pharmacogenomics J.* 18, 413–421 (2018).

13. Dyrba, M. et al. Comparison of Different Hypotheses Regarding the Spread of Alzheimer's Disease Using Markov Random Fields and Multimodal Imaging. *J. Alzheimers. Dis.* 65, 731–746 (2018).

Effect marker for thyroid related AOPs (PARC 5.3.2 EMG)

Authors: Maria Wielsøe, Manhai Long, Eva Cecilie Bonefeld-Jørgensen – Department of Public Health, Aarhus University (AU-PH), Denmark

Hypertrophy, proliferation and hyperplasia in follicular cells

Three AOPs ([110](#), [119](#), [162](#)) with increase in adenomas/carcinomas in follicular cells as adverse outcome (AO: [741](#)) were identified, and included several identical key events (Figure 1). We have focused our search of effect markers on the two upstream key events (KEs) on increase in hypertrophy and proliferation (KE: [739](#)) and increase in hyperplasia (KE: [740](#)) in follicular cells.

Figure 1: Network of AOP 110, 119, and 162 with increase in adenomas/carcinomas in follicular cells as adverse outcome. **Yellow boxes** are early events (mostly related to thyroid hormones), **green boxes** are upstream events, and **blue box** is the adverse outcome. For events with **orange borders**, a relevant effect marker was identified and listed in the AD5.5 report (Year 1 - 2023), while no effect markers relevant for epidemiological studies were identified for events with **black borders**.

Methods:

The two KEs (KE [739](#) and [740](#)) are not well described in AOPwiki and is still under development. We searched PubMed for potential effect markers using the search string in Text box 1 on the December 15, 2023.

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("effect marker"[Title/Abstract] OR "biomarker"[Title/Abstract] OR "gene expression"[Title/Abstract] OR "transcriptomic"[Title/Abstract] OR "measurement"[Title/Abstract]) AND ("Hypertrophy"[Title/Abstract] OR "Proliferation"[Title/Abstract] OR "Hyperplasia"[Title/Abstract] OR "hypergenesis"[Title/Abstract]) AND ("Follicular cells"[Title/Abstract] OR "Thyroid Gland"[MeSH]) AND (humans[Filter])
```

Text box 1: Search string used on PubMed

We focused on articles published in 2018 or later, as the aim is to find new novel effect marker, furthermore the articles must have information on the relevant KEs/AO. Of the 115 hits in the PubMed search, 14 studies [1-14] were published in 2018 or later, relevant and included information on possible effect markers for increase in hypertrophy, proliferation, and hyperplasia in follicular cells and/or adenomas/carcinomas in follicular cells (Figure 2).

Results and discussion:

The information on possible effect marker in the 14 included studies are listed in Table 1 (page 4-8). One study [1] describes serum Calcitonin as an accurate measure of thyroid cancer tumour burden with high sensitivity, even though the positive predictive value is low due to a proportion of false positives and the high frequency of C cell hyperplasia in the absence of thyroid carcinoma. Serum Calcitonin is also suggested as a marker of relapse after operation with the doubling time of Calcitonin as a prognostic factor [1]. As an effect marker, Calcitonin has the advantage that it can be measured in the blood with commercially available immunoassays (Table 1, page 4-8). Serum Calcitonin has not

been linked with many other diseases and could be a relatively specific marker of thyroid cancer; however, some studies have found an association with bronchogenic cancer [15, 16].

Figure 2 Flow chart of literature search and selection

Another potential effect marker in blood is interleukin-34 (IL-34), which is increased in both tumour tissue and serum of papillary thyroid cancer patients compared with age-matched controls [2] (Table 1, page 4-8). The expression of serum IL-34 was also significantly associated with tumour size, tumour stage, and lymph node metastasis [2]. IL-34 have also been found to play a role in many other cancer types, such as hepatocarcinoma, osteosarcoma, multiple myeloma, colon cancer, and lung cancer [17] (Table 1, page 4-8). Furthermore, IL-34 have been linked to several over disease types including autoimmune disorders, infections, neurological disorders and metabolic diseases, indicating that IL-34 is not very specific as an effect marker [18].

Two other effect markers (oxidative stress [3] and reverse T3 [4]) measurable in serum have been identified in the literature (Table 1, page 4-8). They are, however, too unspecific to be effect markers alone on increase in hypertrophy, proliferation, and hyperplasia in follicular cells and/or adenomas/carcinomas in follicular cells but might serve as effect markers in combination with other markers (Table 1, page 4-8).

Eight studies [5-12] have identified differences between tumour tissue and matched adjacent or normal non-cancerous tissues in expression of genes, microRNA and circularRNA, as well as slicing variants and AMPase activity (Table 1, page 4-8). These may serve as future effect markers, if the

difference can be detected in blood samples or other easily available matrixes which can be collected in larger epidemiological studies. Validation of these suggested effect markers needs future studies.

The last two identified studies [13, 14] found somatic and germline DNA variations present in the thyroid tumours compared to non-cancerous tissues (Table 1, page 4-8). The somatic variation might serve as future effect markers if detectable in blood samples. Both studies found relations to the RTK/RAS pathway [13, 14], which could be relevant to investigate more in relation to effect markers, as well as the hippo pathway identified by Qu et al. [14] (Table 1, page 4-8).

Conclusion:

In this literature review, we identified one promising effect marker (serum Calcitonin), as well as other potential future effect markers for AOP [110](#), [119](#), and [162](#) in relation to increase in hypertrophy, proliferation, and hyperplasia in follicular cells and/or adenomas/carcinomas in follicular cells. The effect markers need to be validated further before they can be used in epidemiological studies.

Table 1 Possible effect markers for increase in hypertrophy, proliferation, and hyperplasia in follicular cells and/or adenomas/carcinomas in follicular cells

Effect marker	Matrix	Measurement methods	Description of association with key event or adverse outcome in humans or if stated validation of measurement/effect marker.	Developmental status of the effect marker	Comments / Recommended for human epidemiological studies (Why, why not)	Reference
Calcitonin, cut-off at >100 pg/mL suggested by the American Thyroid Association	Serum	Commercial assays available with some variations. Two-site immunoassays using monoclonal antibodies recognizing distinct segments of the bioactive monomer allow accurate determination of mature Calcitonin concentrations.	<p>Based on retrospective, non-randomized studies, evidence indicates that circulating Calcitonin sensitivity for diagnosing thyroid C cell disease is approximately 100%.</p> <p>The Positive Predictive Value is low (10–40%), due to both the proportion of false positives and the high frequency (30–75%) of C cell hyperplasia in the absence of medullary thyroid carcinoma.</p> <p>Serum Calcitonin is associated with thyroid C cell hyperplasia and medullary thyroid carcinoma</p>	<p>Serum Calcitonin is an accurate biomarker of thyroid cancer tumour burden with high sensitivity; however, the Positive Predictive Value is low.</p> <p>Validation in epidemiological studies is needed.</p>	<p>Calcitonin could be relevant as an effect marker.</p> <p>The effect marker has also been suggested as prognostic marker and marker of relapse.</p>	[1] Costante et al. 2020
IL-34	Serum Papillary thyroid cancer tissue and matched adjacent tissues	ELISA for serum IL-34 Western blot of proteins from tumour tissue	<p>IL-34 was overexpressed (mRNA and protein) in the tumour tissue compared to matched adjacent tissue and normal tissue from non-cancer patients.</p> <p>Serum levels of IL-34 were significantly increased in papillary thyroid cancer patients compared with age-matched controls.</p> <p>Overexpression of IL-34 was significantly associated with tumour size, tumour TNM stage, and lymph node metastasis.</p>	Serum IL-34 might serve as a diagnostic biomarker for papillary thyroid cancer	Serum IL-34 is also related to several other diseases and is not specific for thyroid cancer.	[2] Zhang et al. 2020
Oxidative stress (total antioxidant status (TAS), total oxidant status (TOS), oxidative stress	Serum / Whole Blood	Commercial kits, Electronic paramagnetic resonance measurements	<p>Analysis of oxidative status in sera showed that oxidant levels were significantly increased, and antioxidant levels were decreased in thyroid cancer patients compared to controls.</p> <p>High concentration of malondialdehyde (MDA), an oxidized lipid-derived aldehyde, and associated with a decrease in</p>	Possible future effect in combination with other markers.	Oxidative stress in serum/blood is not specifically related to Adenomas/ carcinomas in follicular cell.	[3] Ameziane et al. 2019

index (ratio of TOS to TAS))			the antioxidative capacity of whole blood were found in thyroid cancer patients.			
Reverse T3	Serum	Mass-spectrometric methods	Increase proliferation with reverse T3 was also seen in vitro in human cancer cell lines	Not relevant as effect marker.	No, not specifically related to the KEs or AO	[4] Halsall et al. 2021
ARHGAP36 gene expression	Primary Papillary thyroid carcinoma tissue; metastasis lymph node tissue; precancerous normal tissue	Single-cell RNA-seq Immunohistochemistry staining; Real-time qPCR	ARHGAP36 was exclusively expressed in the malignant cells of primary and metastatic cancers, but not in the non-malignant and normal follicular epithelial cells in adjacent normal samples. Cell proliferation and migration were significantly suppressed in ARHGAP36 knockdown cell lines.	Not yet validated in blood samples / circulating tumour cells.	Possible future effect marker. The studies were conducted on thyroid tissue and lymph node, a matrix not normally available in large epidemiological studies.	[5] Yan et al. 2021
S100A12 gene expression	Papillary thyroid carcinoma tissue and adjacent non-cancerous tissue	Immunohistochemistry staining; Western blot assay	S100A12 was overexpressed in tumour tissue compared to adjacent non-cancerous tissue. Cell proliferation and migration were also significantly suppressed in S100A12 knockdown cell lines.			[6] Wang et al. 2020
Gene expression of GPER1, (DIO1, DIO2, DUOX1, DUOX2, PAX8, SLC26A4, SLC5A5, SLC5A8, TPO, and TG)	Thyroid tumour versus matched non-cancerous thyroid tissues	Real-time-qPCR Immunohistochemistry	By immunohistochemistry GPER1 was expressed in both tumours and adjacent non-malignant thyroid, but the stain was more diffuse in tumours. Lower expression of GPER1 in thyroid tumour tissue than in adjacent non-malignant thyroid tissue Gene expression of GPER1 correlated positively with DIO1, DIO2, DUOX1, DUOX2, PAX8, SLC26A4, SLC5A5, SLC5A8, TPO, and TG.			[7] Bertoni et al. 2021
DUXAP8	Tumour tissues and the adjacent normal tissues	qPCR Western blot	DUXAP8 was one of the most significantly upregulated long non-coding RNAs in patients with papillary thyroid carcinoma. The expression of DUXAP8 was associated with tumour size and TNM stage.			[8] Pang et al. 2021

			DUXAP8 knockdown inhibits cell proliferation and induces cell apoptosis in papillary thyroid carcinoma cell lines.			
miRNA "hsa-miR-200a-5p"	Papillary benign thyroid tumours with papillary hyperplasia versus thyroid carcinomas patients	qPCR Immunohistochemistry	hsa-miR-200a-5p expressive level was significantly increased in papillary thyroid cancer tumour tissue. hsa-miR-200a-5p is part of the miR-200 and high expression have been shown in several cancers, including colorectal cancer, pancreatic cancer, and esophageal adenocarcinoma.			[9] Wang et al. 2018
circular RNA "has_circ_0008274"	Papillary thyroid cancer tissue and matched adjacent tissues	qPCR Western blot	circRNAs "has_circ_0008274" was significantly up-regulated in tumour tissues compared with matched normal tissues in the microarray datasets. "has_circ_0008274" expression was significantly associated with TNM stage and lymph node metastasis, but not with age, gender, extra thyroidal extension, primary tumour and tumour size. has_circ_0008274 knockdown reduced proliferation, invasive cell number, and colony forming capabilities in papillary thyroid cancer cell lines.			[10] Zhou et al. 2018
Gene expression of TSP1 and slicing variants	Thyroid carcinoma tissue versus adjacent non-malignant thyroid tissue	Antibody array, Real-time-PCR	TSP1 is known for its cell-specific functions in cancer progression, such as proliferation and migration. TSP1 was highly expressed in the tumour tissue compared to adjacent normal tissue. Three forms of TSP1 transcripts were identified in thyroid cancer (TSP1W, TSP1V (major), and TSP1Vm (minor)). TSP1V levels were significantly lower in patients with differentiated thyroid carcinoma than in those with benign thyroid nodule, indicating its potential application as a diagnostic biomarker in tumour progression. In cell studies, TSP1V expression suppress cell growth and decreased cell migration and invasion compared to TSP1W.			[11] Hong et al. 2023

AMPase activity NT5E expression	Papillary thyroid carcinoma tissue versus adjacent non-malignant thyroid tissue	Enzymatic activities of ectonucleotidases by using AMP as substrates qPCR	AMPase activity was higher in papillary thyroid carcinoma. NT5E expression was higher in papillary thyroid carcinoma than in the adjacent non-malignant thyroid tissue. NT5E was positively associated with metastatic lymph nodes, risk of recurrence, tumour size, and nodular hyperplasia in the adjacent thyroid parenchyma, when compared to normal thyroid or lymphocytic thyroiditis.			[12] Bertoni et al. 2019
Variations in RAS, RET/PTC rearrangement and BRAF	Tissue from benign follicular adenoma, diffuse hyperplasia, thyroiditis, multinodular goiter, follicular thyroid carcinomas, follicular variant of papillary thyroid carcinomas, classic variant of papillary thyroid carcinomas, diffuse sclerosing variant of papillary thyroid carcinomas	qPCR	Variations in RAS were most frequently associated with follicular thyroid carcinomas, RET/PTC rearrangements with diffuse sclerosing variant of papillary thyroid carcinomas, and invasive follicular variant of papillary thyroid carcinomas, and BRAF with classic variant of papillary thyroid carcinomas	Not yet validated in blood samples / circulating tumour cells.	The somatic variations may serve as a future effect marker, if the variations could be detected in blood samples / circulating tumour cells. The germline variations could serve as predictors of risk, but not as effect markers as they will be present from birth.	[13] Mostoufi-Moab et al. 2018

<p>Somatic variations in RET (RTK/RAS pathway)</p> <p>FAT1 and FAT4 germline variations (Hippo pathway)</p>	<p>Primary thyroid tumour versus matched noncancerous thyroid tissues</p>	<p>Whole-exome sequencing on DNA extracted from tissue</p>	<p>RET variations found in 27.8% of the analysed tumours, while 50.0% of cases had somatic or germline variations in some genes in the RTK/RAS pathway.</p> <p>FAT1 germline variations found in 22.2% of cases, FAT4 germline variations found in 16.7% of cases, while 44.4 % of the cases had somatic or germline variations some genes in the hippo pathway.</p> <p>In in-vitro cell lines, FAT1 and FAT4 known-down increased the cell proliferation.</p>			<p>[14] Qu et al. 2020</p>
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Abbreviations: AMP: Adenosine Monophosphate; AMPase: adenosine 5¹-monophosphatase; IL-34: interleukin 34; MDA: malondialdehyde; PCR: Polymerase chain reaction; qPCR: Quantitative Polymerase chain reaction; T3: triiodothyronine; TAS: total antioxidant status; TNM: tumor, node, metastasis staging; TOS: total oxidant status

References

1. Costante, G. and D. Meringolo, *Calcitonin as a biomarker of C cell disease: recent achievements and current challenges*. Endocrine, 2020. **67**(2): p. 273-280. DOI: 10.1007/s12020-019-02183-6
2. Zhang, P., et al., *IL-34 is a potential biomarker for the treatment of papillary thyroid cancer*. J Clin Lab Anal, 2020. **34**(8): p. e23335. DOI: 10.1002/jcla.23335
3. Ameziane El Hassani, R., et al., *Oxidative stress in thyroid carcinomas: biological and clinical significance*. Endocr Relat Cancer, 2019. **26**(3): p. R131-r143. DOI: 10.1530/erc-18-0476
4. Halsall, D.J. and S. Oddy, *Clinical and laboratory aspects of 3,3',5'-triiodothyronine (reverse T3)*. Ann Clin Biochem, 2021. **58**(1): p. 29-37. DOI: 10.1177/0004563220969150
5. Yan, T., et al., *ARHGAP36 regulates proliferation and migration in papillary thyroid carcinoma cells*. J Mol Endocrinol, 2021. **66**(1): p. 1-10. DOI: 10.1530/jme-20-0230
6. Wang, X., et al., *S100A12 is a promising biomarker in papillary thyroid cancer*. Sci Rep, 2020. **10**(1): p. 1724. DOI: 10.1038/s41598-020-58534-1
7. Bertoni, A.P.S., et al., *The gene expression of GPER1 is low in fresh samples of papillary thyroid carcinoma (PTC), and in silico analysis*. Mol Cell Endocrinol, 2021. **535**: p. 111397. DOI: 10.1016/j.mce.2021.111397

8. Pang, R. and S. Yang, *lncRNA DUXAP8 inhibits papillary thyroid carcinoma cell apoptosis via sponging the miR-20b-5p/SOS1 axis*. *Oncol Rep*, 2021. **45**(5). DOI: 10.3892/or.2021.8015
9. Wang, X., et al., *A potential biomarker hsa-miR-200a-5p distinguishing between benign thyroid tumors with papillary hyperplasia and papillary thyroid carcinoma*. *PLoS One*, 2018. **13**(7): p. e0200290. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0200290
10. Zhou, G.K., et al., *Has_circ_0008274 promotes cell proliferation and invasion involving AMPK/mTOR signaling pathway in papillary thyroid carcinoma*. *Eur Rev Med Pharmacol Sci*, 2018. **22**(24): p. 8772-8780. DOI: 10.26355/eurev_201812_16644
11. Hong, Y., et al., *Novel thrombospondin-1 transcript exhibits distinctive expression and activity in thyroid tumorigenesis*. *Oncogene*, 2023. **42**(22): p. 1832-1842. DOI: 10.1038/s41388-023-02692-9
12. Bertoni, A.P.S., et al., *Activity of ecto-5'-nucleotidase (NT5E/CD73) is increased in papillary thyroid carcinoma and its expression is associated with metastatic lymph nodes*. *Mol Cell Endocrinol*, 2019. **479**: p. 54-60. DOI: 10.1016/j.mce.2018.08.013
13. Mostoufi-Moab, S., et al., *Molecular Testing for Oncogenic Gene Alterations in Pediatric Thyroid Lesions*. *Thyroid*, 2018. **28**(1): p. 60-67. DOI: 10.1089/thy.2017.0059
14. Qu, N., et al., *Genomic and Transcriptomic Characterization of Sporadic Medullary Thyroid Carcinoma*. *Thyroid*, 2020. **30**(7): p. 1025-1036. DOI: 10.1089/thy.2019.0531
15. Silva, O.L., et al., *Calcitonin as a marker for bronchogenic cancer: a prospective study*. *Cancer*, 1979. **44**(2): p. 680-4. DOI: 10.1002/1097-0142(197908)44:2<680::aid-cnrcr2820440240>3.0.co;2-j
16. Silva, O.L., et al., *Increased serum calcitonin levels in bronchogenic cancer*. *Chest*, 1976. **69**(4): p. 495-9. DOI: 10.1378/chest.69.4.495
17. Franzè, E., et al., *Role of Interleukin-34 in Cancer*. *Cancers (Basel)*, 2020. **12**(1). DOI: 10.3390/cancers12010252
18. Baghdadi, M., et al., *Interleukin-34, a comprehensive review*. *J Leukoc Biol*, 2018. **104**(5): p. 931-951. DOI: 10.1002/jlb.Mr1117-457r

Effect marker for thyroid related AOPs (PARC 5.3.2 EMG)

Authors: Maria Wielsøe, Manhai Long, Eva Cecilie Bonefeld-Jørgensen – Department of Public Health, Aarhus University (AU-PH), Denmark

Kidney function

One AOP (128) on kidney toxicity was identified as a thyroid related AOP (Figure 1). The AOP include two events related to thyroid hormone balance (MIE 277 and KE 281), increased serum creatinine (KE 813) and seven upstream key events related to levels kidney function including cystic dilatation (KE 823), cytoplasmic vacuolization (KE 818 and KE 824), decrease renal plasma flow (KE 820), sodium reabsorption (KE 821), ability to dilute urine (KE 825), and glomerular filtration (KE 819) (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Network of AOP 128 on kidney toxicity. Yellow boxes are early events, green boxes are upstream events, and blue box is the adverse outcome. For events with orange borders, a relevant effect marker was identified and listed in the AD5.5 report (Year 1 - 2023), while no effect markers relevant for epidemiological studies were identified for events with black borders.

Several effect markers of kidney function have already been identified in the EU-project HBM4EU [1, 2] and were also listed in the PARC report AD5.5 (Year 1 – 2023). Furthermore, several reviews exist on effect markers for kidney function [3-6]. Thus, we have not conducted additional systematic literature searches, due to the high number of already identified effect markers. Table 1 (page 2-4), however, comprises the information on the already identified effects markers, of which several will be implemented in the PARC aligned studies conducted in WP4.

The U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) have in 2018 assessed a panel of biomarkers for kidney tubular injury in clinical Phase 1 trails for drugs [7]. The six included biomarkers were clusterin (CLU), cystatin-C (CysC), kidney injury molecule-1 (KIM-1), N-acetyl-beta-d-glucosaminidase (NAG), neutrophil gelatinase-associated lipocalin (NGAL), and osteopontin (OPN), and the FDA determined that the Composite Measure (CM) composed of these six urinary biomarkers was qualified as a “safety composite biomarker panel to be used in conjunction with traditional measures to aid in the detection of kidney tubular injury in phase 1 trials in healthy volunteers when there is an a priori concern that a drug may cause renal tubular injury in humans” [7]. The biomarker panel may not only be relevant in clinical trials of drug kidney toxicity but could also be used in epidemiological studies. However, a validation of the sensitivity and specificity in epidemiological studies is needed.

Table 1: Effect markers identified for kidney toxicity.

Effect marker	Matrix	Measurement method	Developmental status of the effect marker	Comments	References
Creatinine	Serum / Urine	Kinetic alkaline picrate assay (Jaffe method) / ELISA	Fully developed for measurement in human epidemiological studies.	Creatinine is a commonly used as measure of kidney function. Included in PARC aligned studies (Urine).	[3, 5, 8]
α 1-microglobulin	Plasma / Urine	ELISA / nephrometric immunoassay	Fully developed for measurement in human epidemiological studies.	An early effect marker of tubular disorders. Included in PARC aligned studies (Urine).	[9, 10]
Retinol-binding protein 4 (RBP4)	Plasma / Urine	Mass-spectrometry / ELISA	Fully developed for measurement in human epidemiological studies.	Urine RBP4 is the most sensitive functional biomarker of proximal tubule. Included in PARC aligned studies (Urine).	[3, 11, 12]
Albumin	Urine	Immunological assays / turbidimetric assays. Albumin should be reported as a ratio to urinary creatinine concentration.	Fully developed for measurement in human epidemiological studies.	Urine albumin measurement provides a more specific and sensitive measure of changes in glomerular permeability than urinary total protein. Included in PARC aligned studies (Urine).	[6]
N-acetyl- β -D glucosaminidase (NAG)	Serum / Urine	ELISA / Fluorometric assay	Fully developed for measurement in human epidemiological studies.	Part of the FDA qualified biomarker panel for kidney tubular injury [7] NAG is an early effect marker of tubular damage useful for human biomonitoring purposes. Included in PARC aligned studies (Urine)	[13]

KIM-1 (kidney injury molecule-1)	Serum / Urine	ELISA / laminar-flow dipstick assay	Fully developed for measurement in human epidemiological studies.	Part of the FDA qualified biomarker panel for kidney tubular injury [7] Early biomarker for proximal tubular damage, expression is upregulated after kidney injury. Included in PARC aligned studies (Urine)	[3, 5, 14]
Neutrophil gelatinase-associated lipocalin (NGAL)	Serum / Plasma / Urine	ELISA / chemiluminescence immunoassay	Fully developed for measurement in human epidemiological studies.	Part of the FDA qualified biomarker panel for kidney tubular injury [7] Marker for Proximal and distal tubule disorders and an early marker for acute kidney injury as well as chronic kidney damage. May predict kidney disease progression independent of GFR, however data from larger studies are needed to confirm this.	[3, 5, 15]
Cystatin C (CysC)	Serum / Urine	ELISA / nephelometric immunoassay / immunoturbidimetry	Fully developed for measurement in human epidemiological studies.	Part of the FDA qualified biomarker panel for kidney tubular injury [7]. Urinary CysC is an early marker of acute kidney injury and early kidney dysfunction.	[3, 5, 16]
β 2-microglobulin (B2-MG)	Plasma / Serum / Urine	ELISA / nephelometric immunoassay	Fully developed for measurement in human epidemiological studies.	Marker of GFR, with declining GFR results in increased B2MG B2-MG is an early effect marker of tubular damage useful for human biomonitoring purposes.	[3, 13]
Clusterin (CLU)	Serum / Urine	ELISA	Fully developed for measurement in human epidemiological studies.	Part of the FDA qualified biomarker panel for kidney tubular injury [7] Urinary level changes are specific to kidney injury.	[17, 18]

				In a study on children undergoing allogeneic hematopoietic stem cell transplantation, clusterin seems more useful as a marker of subclinical acute kidney injury than the classical indices of tubular (KIM-1) and glomerular (cystatin C) damage analyzed separately.	
Osteopontin (OPN)	Serum / Urine	ELISA	Fully developed for measurement in human epidemiological studies.	Part of the FDA qualified biomarker panel for kidney tubular injury [7] Kidney is the organ with the highest OPN content, and following kidney damage, its expression is upregulated in all tubular segments and in the glomeruli. OPN is a suggested effect marker of chronic kidney disease.	[19, 20]
Protein carbonyls	Serum / plasma	Spectrophotometric assays / ELISA / Western blot. All relying on derivatization with 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (DNPH), which specifically reacts with protein carbonyls associated with aldehydes and ketones.	Fully developed for measurement in human epidemiological studies.	Effect marker of oxidative stress, which increases early in chronic kidney injury.	[4, 21]

Abbreviations:

AO: adverse outcome; **AOP:** Adverse outcome pathway; **B2-MG:** β 2-microglobulin; **CLU:** clusterin; **CM:** Composite Measure; **CysC:** cystatin-C; **DNPH:** 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine; **ELISA:** Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay; **FDA:** U.S. Food and Drug Administration; **GFR:** glomerular

filtration rate; **KE**: key event; **KIM-1**: kidney injury molecule-1; **MIE**: Molecular initiating event; **NAG**: N-acetyl-beta-d-glucosaminidase; **NGAL**: neutrophil gelatinase-associated lipocalin; **OPN**: osteopontin; **RBP4**: Retinol-binding protein 4

References:

1. Rodríguez-Carrillo, A., et al., *Implementation of effect biomarkers in human biomonitoring studies: A systematic approach synergizing toxicological and epidemiological knowledge*. International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health, 2023. **249**: p. 114140. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2023.114140>
2. Zare Jeddi, M., et al., *Towards a systematic use of effect biomarkers in population and occupational biomonitoring*. Environ Int, 2021. **146**: p. 106257. DOI: 10.1016/j.envint.2020.106257
3. Lopez-Giacoman, S. and M. Madero, *Biomarkers in chronic kidney disease, from kidney function to kidney damage*. World J Nephrol, 2015. **4**(1): p. 57-73. DOI: 10.5527/wjn.v4.i1.57
4. Fassett, R.G., et al., *Biomarkers in chronic kidney disease: a review*. Kidney Int, 2011. **80**(8): p. 806-21. DOI: 10.1038/ki.2011.198
5. Wasung, M.E., L.S. Chawla, and M. Madero, *Biomarkers of renal function, which and when?* Clin Chim Acta, 2015. **438**: p. 350-7. DOI: 10.1016/j.cca.2014.08.039
6. Kidney Disease: Improving Global Outcomes (KDIGO), *KDIGO 2012 clinical practice guideline for the evaluation and management of chronic kidney disease*, in *Kidney International Supplements*. 2013.
7. U.S. Food and Drug Administration. *Qualification of Biomarker: clusterin (CLU), Cystatin-C (CysC), Kidney Injury Molecule-1 (KIM-1), N-acetyl-beta-D-glucosaminidase (NAG), Neutrophil Gelatinase-Associated Lipocalin (NGAL), and osteopontin (OPN)*. 2020 [cited 2024 February]; Available from: <https://www.fda.gov/drugs/biomarker-qualification-program/reviews-qualification-biomarker-clusterin-clu-cystatin-c-cysc-kidney-injury-molecule-1-kim-1-n>.
8. Zhang, X., et al., *Tubular secretion of creatinine and kidney function: an observational study*. BMC Nephrology, 2020. **21**(1): p. 108. DOI: 10.1186/s12882-020-01736-6
9. Mustieles, V., et al., *List of effect biomarkers for the first set of prioritized substances*. HBM4EU Deliverable Report D14.2. 2018.
10. Penders, J. and J.R. Delanghe, *Alpha 1-microglobulin: clinical laboratory aspects and applications*. Clinica Chimica Acta, 2004. **346**(2): p. 107-118. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cccn.2004.03.037>
11. Ratajczyk, K., et al., *The Clinical Significance of Urinary Retinol-Binding Protein 4: A Review*. Int J Environ Res Public Health, 2022. **19**(16). DOI: 10.3390/ijerph19169878
12. Lapsley, M., K. Akers, and A.G.W. Norden, *Sensitive Assays for Urinary Retinol-Binding Protein and β -2-Glycoprotein-1 Based on Commercially Available Standards*. Annals of Clinical Biochemistry, 1998. **35**(1): p. 115-119. DOI: 10.1177/000456329803500116
13. Kim, Y.-D., et al., *Temporal changes in urinary levels of cadmium, N-acetyl- β -d-glucosaminidase and β 2-microglobulin in individuals in a cadmium-contaminated area*. Environmental Toxicology and Pharmacology, 2015. **39**(1): p. 35-41. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.etap.2014.10.016>
14. Yin, C. and N. Wang, *Kidney injury molecule-1 in kidney disease*. Renal Failure, 2016. **38**(10): p. 1567-1573. DOI: 10.1080/0886022X.2016.1193816
15. Turgut, D., et al., *Urinary neutrophil gelatinase-associated lipocalin as a biomarker in different renal problems*. Turk J Med Sci, 2020. **50**(6): p. 1566-1572. DOI: 10.3906/sag-2002-130
16. Spanaus, K.-S., et al., *Serum Creatinine, Cystatin C, and β -Trace Protein in Diagnostic Staging and Predicting Progression of Primary Nondiabetic Chronic Kidney Disease*. Clinical Chemistry, 2010. **56**(5): p. 740-749. DOI: 10.1373/clinchem.2009.138826
17. Dieterle, F., et al., *Urinary clusterin, cystatin C, β 2-microglobulin and total protein as markers to detect drug-induced kidney injury*. Nature Biotechnology, 2010. **28**(5): p. 463-469. DOI: 10.1038/nbt.1622

18. Musiał, K., et al., *Clusterin as a New Marker of Kidney Injury in Children Undergoing Allogeneic Hematopoietic Stem Cell Transplantation-A Pilot Study*. J Clin Med, 2020. **9**(8). DOI: 10.3390/jcm9082599
19. Sinha, S.K., et al., *Osteopontin as a Biomarker in Chronic Kidney Disease*. Biomedicines, 2023. **11**(5). DOI: 10.3390/biomedicines11051356
20. de Borst, M.H. and J.-J. Carrero, *Will osteopontin bridge the gap towards clinical application in chronic kidney disease?* Nephrology Dialysis Transplantation, 2023. **38**(6): p. 1352-1354. DOI: 10.1093/ndt/gfad057
21. Colombo, G., et al., *Plasma Protein Carbonyls as Biomarkers of Oxidative Stress in Chronic Kidney Disease, Dialysis, and Transplantation*. Oxid Med Cell Longev, 2020. **2020**: p. 2975256. DOI: 10.1155/2020/2975256

Effect markers for androgen related AOPs (PARC 5.3.2 EMG)

Authors: Manhai Long, Maria Wielsøe, Eva Cecilie Bonefeld-Jørgensen – Department of Public Health, Aarhus University (AU-PH), Denmark

Alteration in Wnt pathway and Feminisation or incomplete development of male sex organs

One AOP ([19](#)) linking to outcome of impairment of reproductive capacity ([AO 337](#)) was identified. This AOP includes several events including MIE [27](#) and KEs ([286, 240, 310](#)) (Fig. 1). The upstream key event for impaired reproductive capacity ([AO 337](#)) is feminisation or incomplete development in primary and accessory male sex organs (KE [240](#)) while alteration in Wnt pathway (KE [310](#)) links to KE [240](#). We therefore search the possible effect markers focusing on KE [240](#) and [310](#).

Fig. 1. Network of AOP [19](#) related to adverse outcome of impairment of reproductive capacity in males [AO 337](#). **Yellow boxes** are early events and **green boxes** are upstream key events. **Blue box** is adverse outcome. **Boxes with orange border** are for the events with relevant effect marker identified and listed in the Year 1 AD 5.5 report (2023). The events with **black border** are those where no effect markers relevant for epidemiological studies were identified.

Methods:

As there is no identified effect markers for events [240](#) and [310](#), and no measurement methods for these two events are available in the AOPwiki, we searched for potential effect markers in PubMed using the following search string box on the January 23, 2024.

(("effect marker"[Title/Abstract] OR "biomarker"[Title/Abstract] OR "gene expression"[Title/Abstract] OR "measurement"[Title/Abstract]) AND ("wnt pathway"[Title/Abstract] OR "Feminization"[Title/Abstract] OR "incomplete development "[Title/Abstract]) AND ("sex organs "[Title/Abstract]) AND (humans[Filter]))

Because the aim is to find novel effect markers for epidemiological studies, the search restricted to the last 5 years and the articles must be conducted in human with the information on the relevant KEs or AO. As shown in Fig. 2, of the 113 hits in the PubMed search, 16 articles are review articles including 2 meta-analyses. Four articles are clinical trial and/or randomized controlled trial (RCT) which are not relevant to reproductive capacity and thus were excluded. Among the remaining 93 original articles, 9 studies were relevant to human and included information on possible effect markers for impairment of reproductive capacity in male.

Fig. 2. Flow chart of literature search and selection for effect biomarkers relevant to impairment of reproductive capacity ([AO 337](#))

Results & Discussion

The information of the possible effect markers in the included 9 articles are listed in Table 1. The adverse outcome of impairment of reproductive capacity is related to one AOP. Most studies addressed androgen receptor activity and expression and further confirm the crucial role androgen in male fertility and impaired virilisation [1-6]. Giwercman et al [1] found three proteins (4HPPD, ALDOB, IGFBP6) measured in the blood as markers of biological androgen activity. They then validated these markers for testosterone deficiency by checking the levels of the three proteins in a separate group of 75 men with fertility problems. These newly discovered markers could be used to create a test for measuring testosterone activity. The candidate markers identified in their study are androgen dependent. This could help to identify deficiencies and finetune the amount of supplementary hormone given to men as treatment. However, further research is needed to understand the clinical value of such a test in men, as well as women and children. However, the absolute

values of quantifications for the potential markers were not reported, but the relative quantifications for comparing the protein expression between groups were reported. This kind of comparative proteomics is favourable in research studies, in which preliminary results of protein changes between groups are obtained. Also, the sample processing is complicated putting high demands on the laboratory. In proteomics, there can be a high variation between laboratories in reporting absolute concentration proteins in plasma, especially when small sample sizes are reported. Al-Sharkawi et al analysed the expression of steroidogenic markers and Leydig cell development and differentiation markers by immunohistochemistry in patients with defective androgen signalling such as complete androgen insensitivity syndrome and evidenced that androgen signalling may affect the differentiation of adults, but possibly not foetal Leydig cells, and may induce a shift of testosterone production from the tubular compartment in the foetal phase to the interstitial compartment in the adult phase [5].

Three articles explored the role of Wnt pathway in the male reproductive organs development and all are at the RNA level [4, 7, 8]. As the measurements of Wnt pathway are based on testis sample, more studies are needed to valid in non-/low invasive matrices such as seminal fluid, semen, blood, and urine for epidemiology studies.

Conclusion

In this literature review, the possible effect markers for the Wnt pathway and feminization of male sex organ in relation to impaired reproductive capacity (AOP [19](#)) were searched. Most studies addressed androgen receptor activity and expression and further confirm the crucial role androgen in male fertility and impaired virilisation. Three proteins can be measured in blood serum (4HPPD, ALDOB, and MMA) as the markers of biological androgen activity. However, further research is needed to understand the clinical value of such a test in men. The role of Wnt pathway in the male reproductive organ development is explored in some articles, and all are at the RNA level. As the measurements of Wnt pathway are based on testis sample, more studies are needed to valid in non-/low invasive matrices such as seminal fluid, semen, blood, and urine for epidemiology studies.

Table 1 Possible effect markers for Wnt pathway alteration and Feminisation or incomplete development of male sex organs

Effect marker	Matrix	Measurement methods	Description of association with key event or adverse outcome in humans or if stated validation of measurement/effect marker.	Developmental status of the effect marker	Comments/Recommended for human epidemiological studies (Why, why not)	Author [ref.]
Protein markers of biological androgen activity (4HPPD, ALDOB, and IGFB6)	Plasma and serum	- Proteomics for identifying protein biomarkers of testosterone activity include bicinchoninic acid (BCA) assay, automated Data Dependent Acquisition (DDA) method and Multiple Reaction Monitoring (MRM) method	- Proteomics is a technique aimed to study biological systems based on qualitative and quantitative measuring of proteins and, thereby, integrate the cellular output related to transcription as well as translation. - In infertile men, Multi Marker Algorithm (MMA) variable was created to predict the odds of suffering from low testosterone (T) or other medical conditions associated with low T levels. - 4-hydroxyphenylpyruvate Dioxygenase (4HPPD), insulin-like growth factor-binding protein 6 (IGFBP6), and fructose-bisphosphate aldolase (ALDOB), as well as the combined marker MMA (4HPPD + IGFBP6), were shown to be best predictors of low (<8 nmol/l) vs normal (>12 nmol/l) testosterone. - 4HPPD, ALDOB, and MMA showed a negative association with testosterone concentration, while IGFBP6 displayed a positive association. - In young healthy men, these three markers were strongly associated with testosterone levels. In a slightly older cohort of infertile men, these markers were indicative of testosterone deficiency that is both total and free serum testosterone was low.	More extensive testing is vital to elucidate the biological androgen activity potential these three proteins, not only in men but also in women and in prepubertal boys.	- Three plasma proteins (ALDOB, 4HPPD and IGFB6) are identified as potential markers of biological androgen activity. - These proteins – alone or in combination (MAA) are promising as useful parameters in the clinical diagnosis of male hypogonadism and in the prediction of its long-term sequelae, as well as in studying the biology of androgen action.	Giwercka et al. 2022 [1]
AR expression and activity	Genital skin fibroblasts	- AR activity: DHT-mediated induction of the endogenous AR target gene APOD (apolipoprotein D)	- Around 38% individuals with 45,X/46,XY mosaicism genital skin fibroblasts, AR mRNA expression and AR activity were significantly lower compared with those in the reference genital skin fibroblasts. No mutation in AR gene was observed.	Future research in disorder of sex development should consider the potential coexistence of factors that modify the degree of	- This study analysed AR gene mutation status, AR expression, and AR activity in genital skin fibroblasts and correlated these	Hornig NC et al 2019 [2]

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -AR sequencing (AR gene mutation): fluorescence in situ hybridization (FISH) -AR mRNA expression: Quantitative PCR -AR protein expression: Western blot 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All genital skin fibroblasts with reduced AR mRNA expression showed reduced AR protein expression and AR activity -A significantly positive correlation between AR activity and the external virilization scale was found. This is in line with the fact that the AR and, consequently, cellular AR function and androgen sensitivity are crucial for male external masculinization. But no association between AR mRNA expression and the genital phenotype was observed. - The level of reduction of AR activity in 45,X/46,XY-derived genital skin fibroblasts was comparable to the reduction previously documented in patients with molecularly proven androgen insensitivity syndrome - Correlating genital skin fibroblasts with reduced AR activity and expression with the degree of 45,X/46,XY mosaicism showed a positive trend toward greater AR mRNA expression in the cell cultures with greater XY content - The reduced AR expression (AR mRNA) and reduced AR activity (DHT-mediated induction of the androgen regulated gene APOD) were at the same level as in molecularly proven androgen insensitivity syndrome. 	<p>virilization (e.g., variations in androgen responsiveness of genital target tissues), in parallel with the primary specific disorder of sex development diagnosis (e.g., gonadal dysgenesis due to 45,X/46,XY mosaicism).</p>	<p>parameters with the degree of 45,X/46,XY mosaicism in the genital skin fibroblasts and the external virilization seen in the patients.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The results suggest that AR expression and AR activity might influence the phenotypic variability seen in patients with 45,X/46,XY mosaicism 	
Genetic marker: Gene expression of AR, Wnt	Penile skin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gene expression in penile skin: RNA microarray - Differential expression analysis: moderated Limma t-test in the standard fashion for microarray experiments - Pathway analysis and process enrichment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Androgen receptor expression of penil skin cells was significantly higher in post-finasteride syndrome patients compared to Controls - Gene expression of Post-finasteride syndrome patients: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) pathways related to sexual effects including tissue migration, angiogenesis, and vasculature development were up-regulated while pathways including blood vessel development, angiogenesis, and positive regulation of epithelial and endothelial cell migration and proliferation 	<p>Post-finasteride syndrome can exhibit sexual effects including penile atrophy, diminished ejaculatory volume and force. This study is not specific link to infertility</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The genes are differentially expressed in penile skin tissue between PFS symptoms patients and healthy controls - The identified upregulated or inhibited biological pathways may be relevant in the 	Howell et al. 2024 [3]

		analysis: Metascape for both gene sets	and pathways involving extracellular matrix regulation (including the “matrisome”), cell junction organization, and connective tissue health were down-regulated. b) The pathway of Wnt signalling was upregulated (but authors did not further discuss this)		development of Post-finasteride syndrome symptoms.	
Genetic marker	Sperm	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bulk RNA sequencing (RNA-seq) - Single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNA-seq) - Single-cell regulatory network inference and clustering (pySCENIC) - Single-cell assay for transposase-accessible chromatin sequencing (scATAC-seq) - Spatial transcriptomic analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Wnt pathway was enriched in the hub gene module, which suggested potential biological functions to induce the occurrence and promotion of Non-obstructive azoospermia (NOA). - Dysfunctional Wnt signalling pathway of spermatogonia in Non-obstructive azoospermia, i.e spermatogonia in Non-obstructive azoospermia had a lower spermatogenesis score and lower Wnt signalling score in the spermatogonia of NOA. The negative regulation of the Wnt signalling pathway was more intense in Non-obstructive azoospermia than in normal while there were more Wnt signalling interactions in normal spermatogonia. - There was decreasing expression of Wnt pathway genes in spermatogonia of Non-obstructive azoospermia. The expression of two proteins related to Wnt signalling (WNT3 and WNT5A) was decreased in NOA samples. - The study showed the levels of transcript factor (CTCF, AR, and ARNTL) were significantly positively correlated with hallmark WNT signalling in spermatogonia. 	This study is based on the public database.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The dysfunctional Wnt signalling of spermatogonia in NOA was observed, and three transcription factors may be involved in this dysfunctional Wnt signalling. These findings provide a new mechanism for NOA and new therapeutic targets for NOA patients. - The single-cell multi-omics analysis is advantageous for the comprehensive understanding of the role of transcription factors in normal spermatogonia. 	Zeng et al. 2023 [4]
Genetic marker	Testicular tissue	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNA-seq) - Immunohistochemistry - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hyperplastic Leydig cells are identified from their extensive expression of the steroidogenic cell marker CYP17A1 - AKR1C3 is an isoenzyme of HSD17B3. It is expressed in both normal testis and hyperplastic Leydig cells of complete androgen insensitivity 	The markers (i.e. antibodies for immunohistochemistry) are from manufactures. So the methods seems validated.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CYP17A1, HSD17B3 and AKR1C3 are steroidogenic marker - INSL3 and DLK1 are LC 	Al-Sharkawi et al 2023 [5]

			<p>syndrome gonadal tissues. AKR1C3 is expressed mainly in adult Leydig cells.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DLK1 is foetal/immature LC marker while INSL3 is adult/mature Leydig cells marker. DLK1 and INSL3 are expressed in subsets of Leydig cells in complete androgen insensitivity syndrome and CYP17A1-deficiency gonadal tissues. - The defective androgen signalling is associated with the persistence of some foetal testicular features in conjunction with developmental defects. From the immunohistochemical study and the reanalysis of scRNA-seq data of the foetal, neonatal, and adult human testes, Leydig cells in human testis might develop into distinct androgen-independent foetal and androgen-dependent adult Leydig cell populations. 		<p>developmental marker</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Androgen signalling may affect the differentiation of adults, but possibly not foetal Sertoli cells or Leydig cells, and may induce a shift of testosterone production from the tubular compartment in the foetal phase to the interstitial compartment in the adult phase 	
Genetic marker	testicular samples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Single-cell transcriptome profiling - scRNA-seq - immunohistochemistry (IHC) staining 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pathways linked to mechanisms potentially responsible for the condition of idiopathic germ cell aplasia. - Delta Like Non-Canonical Notch Ligand 1 (DLK1) gene is considered a marker of the immaturity of Leydig cells. Overexpression of DLK1 was observed in Leydig cells in idiopathic germ cell aplasia vs. adult testis. DLK1 overexpression and decreased IGF2 expression underpin two main pathways that might advocate for Leydig cell immaturity. - Lower expression of INSL3 at both gene and protein levels in idiopathic germ cell aplasia Leydig cells vs. adult testis. - Transcripts for HSD17B3, an enzyme that converts androstenedione to testosterone and is associated with virilization, were present with lower levels of expression only in a fraction of Leydig cells cells, further supporting the 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - This study reveals insights into idiopathic germ cell aplasia, such as the immature phenotype of Leydig cells stuck at the pre-puberal stage of development and expressing clear markers of senescence that might support the hypothesis of exhaustion in the somatic progenitor cell compartment, still needing an experimental validation. 	<p>This work provides a comprehensive transcriptional atlas of the testicular somatic cell populations associated with human idiopathic germ cell aplasia. A detailed picture on the immaturity of Leydig cells, senescence of the testicular somatic cells, defects in gene imprinting, and ongoing</p>	Alfano et al 2021[6]

			conclusion of a delayed Leydig cells maturation in idiopathic germ cell aplasia.		inflammation with an activated senescent secretory phenotype is shown.. - The deregulated expression of parentally imprinted genes in immature Leydig cells, and an active DNA damage response in Leydig are also indicative of senescence of the testicular niche.	
Genetic marker	Testis	- Single-cell RNA-sequencing (scRNA-seq) - Sparse decomposition of analysis (SDA)	- Signalling factors specific to Klinefelter syndrome (KS) Sertoli cells are dysregulated: WNTs (WNT3 and WNT5A) - It is observed numerous genes related to WNT signalling pathways downregulated in KS Sertoli cells compared to control SCs. Curiously, another scRNA-seq of KS testis showed that the WNT pathway was upregulated in individuals affected by idiopathic NOA, and treating Sertoli cells from individuals with NOA with a WNT inhibitor helped promote SC development and function [8]	The tool is on-line	The new transcriptional map of normal and abnormal human testis tissue is explorable through Shiny app tool, HISTA can provide a framework to uncover molecular pathology to understand cellular function and dysregulation in the human testis for the diagnosis and classification of individuals with infertility.	Mahyari et al 2021 [7]
Genetic marker	Testis	- Single-cell RNA-seq	- Wnt/ β -catenin signalling was activated in immature and idiopathic non-obstructive azoospermia Sertoli cells and was inhibited in	Need validation	- Wnt signalling may play role in the maturation of the	Zhao et al 2020 [8]

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Single-cell pseudotime trajectories - qPCR 	<p>normal mature Sertoli cells, suggesting the Wnt pathway may play an important role in the regulation of Sertoli cell maturation.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inhibition of the Wnt pathway could alleviate the maturation disorder of idiopathic non-obstructive azoospermia Sertoli cells and improve the supporting function of both idiopathic non-obstructive azoospermia and normal Sertoli cells in vitro. - Wnt/β-catenin signalling was activated in immature and idiopathic non-obstructive azoospermia Sertoli cells and was inhibited in normal mature Sertoli cells, suggesting the Wnt pathway may play an important role in the regulation of Sertoli cell maturation. - Inhibition of the Wnt pathway restored the maturation defects of Sertoli cells in idiopathic non-obstructive azoospermia patients. - Wnt/β-catenin, ephrin receptor, and integrin pathways may play a crucial role during Sertoli cell maturation. 		<p>spermatogenic microenvironment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A novel perspective on the development of diagnostic methods and therapeutic targets for non-obstructive azoospermia is suggested. - In addition, the evidence that the Wnt signaling pathway regulates the maturation of Sertoli cells in both normal and non-obstructive azoospermia patients is shown. 	
Genetic marker	Foreskins	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gene expression profile: RNA sequencing - Identification of rare coding variants: Whole exome sequencing (WES) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -The gene expression of androgen receptor (AR) and CYP19A1 were significantly decreased in severe hypospadias and mild hypospadias compared to non-hypospadiac foreskins. - The expression of other genes coding for steroidogenic enzymes (CYP3A4, HSD17B14, HSD3B7, HSD17B7, CYP11A1) were only significantly expressed in severe hypospadias. - The WES data further showed that the compound damaging variants of AR genes and other risk genes existed in severe hypospadias with the variable phenotypes. 	The role of AR expression as effect marker of hypospadias needs more studies	Dysregulation of AR and CYP19A1 could play a crucial role in the development of hypospadias. These findings complement the possible role of AR triggered mechanism in the development of hypospadias.	Chen et al. 2020 [9]

Reference

1. Giwercman, A., et al., *Novel protein markers of androgen activity in humans: proteomic study of plasma from young chemically castrated men*. Elife, 2022. **11**.
2. Hornig, N.C., et al., *Reduced Androgen Receptor Expression in Genital Skin Fibroblasts From Patients With 45,X/46,XY Mosaicism*. J Clin Endocrinol Metab, 2019. **104**(10): p. 4630-4638.
3. Howell, S., et al., *Differential Gene Expression in Post-Finasteride Syndrome Patients*. J Sex Med, 2021. **18**(9): p. 1479-1490.
4. Zeng, S., et al., *Single-cell multi-omics analysis reveals dysfunctional Wnt signaling of spermatogonia in non-obstructive azoospermia*. Front Endocrinol (Lausanne), 2023. **14**: p. 1138386.
5. Al-Sharkawi, M., et al., *Persistence of foetal testicular features in patients with defective androgen signalling*. Eur J Endocrinol, 2023. **188**(1).
6. Alfano, M., et al., *Aging, inflammation and DNA damage in the somatic testicular niche with idiopathic germ cell aplasia*. Nat Commun, 2021. **12**(1): p. 5205.
7. Mahyari, E., et al., *Comparative single-cell analysis of biopsies clarifies pathogenic mechanisms in Klinefelter syndrome*. Am J Hum Genet, 2021. **108**(10): p. 1924-1945.
8. Zhao, L., et al., *Single-cell analysis of developing and azoospermia human testicles reveals central role of Sertoli cells*. Nat Commun, 2020. **11**(1): p. 5683.
9. Chen, Z., et al., *Dysregulated expression of androgen metabolism genes and genetic analysis in hypospadias*. Mol Genet Genomic Med, 2020. **8**(8): p. e1346.

Effect markers for androgen related AOPs (PARC 5.3.2 EMG)

Authors: Manhai Long, Maria Wielsøe, Eva Cecilie Bonefeld-Jørgensen – Department of Public Health, Aarhus University (AU-PH), Denmark

Proliferation, Hyperplasia in Leydig cells

Three AOPs (AOP [51](#), [111](#), [120](#)) are linked to key events of Proliferation, Hyperplasia in Leydig cells (KE [415](#), [416](#) and [744](#)). These key events link to adverse outcomes of impaired fertility ([AO 406](#)) and increased Leydig cell tumors ([AO 745](#)) (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Network of AOP [51](#), AOP [111](#), AOP [120](#) relate to adverse outcome of impaired fertility ([AO 406](#)) and increased Leydig cell tumors ([AO 745](#)). Yellow boxes are early events and green boxes are upstream key events. Blue boxes are adverse outcomes. For the events with orange border, relevant effect marker was identified and listed in the AD 5.5 report. The events with black border are those no effect markers relevant for epidemiological studies were identified.

Methods

We searched PubMed for potential effect markers using the search string in following box on the January 23, 2024.

("effect marker"[Title/Abstract] OR "biomarker"[Title/Abstract] OR "gene expression"[Title/Abstract] OR "transcriptomic" [Title/Abstract] OR "measurement"[Title/Abstract]) AND ("Hyperplasia "[Title/Abstract] OR "Hypergenesis"[Title/Abstract] OR "proliferarion"[Title/Abstract] OR "Neoplasia"[Title/Abstract]) AND ("Leydig cell "[Title/Abstract] OR " testis"[Title/Abstract]) AND (humans[Filter])

As shown in Fig. 2, of the 59 hits in the PubMed search, 14 articles are review articles and 12 articles were published before 2014 and thus excluded. Among the remaining 23 original articles, one article is in Chinese while 1 article is non-mammal (zebrafish). Two articles involved non-human species while 9 studies were not relevant to the focused KE and AOs. Finally, 11 articles are included in our review of the possible effect markers for proliferation in Leydig cells (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Flow chart of literature search and selection for effect biomarker relevant to Proliferation, Hyperplasia in Leydig cells

Results & Discussion

Table 1 lists the included 11 studies regarding the possible effect markers of Leydig cell proliferation and hyperplasia. The adverse outcome of impaired fertility and increased Leydig cell tumour are included in three AOPs (AOP [51](#), [111](#), [120](#)) relevant for this search (Fig. 1).

Five studies addressed the role of Insulin-like factor 3 (INSL3) either in serum or in testis as marker of Leydig cell [1-5]. INSL3 is a peptide hormone secreted into the systemic circulation by the steroidogenic Leydig cells of the testes. INSL3 appears to be secreted in an acutely constitutive manner, simply reflecting the number and extant differentiation status of Leydig cells. It is independent of acute regulation by gonadotrophic hormones of the hypothalamic–pituitary–gonadal (HPG) axis. INSL3 immunostaining could be helpful in the differential diagnosis between Leydig cell hyperplasia and Leydig cell tumor [3]. Serum levels of INSL3 reflects hyponadal status and is associated with sexual function and has important predictive value as a clinical parameter [2].

The study by Lottrup et al [10] identified several novel markers specific for either foetal Leydig cells or adult Leydig cells and demonstrated that hyperplastic Leydig cells within micronodules exhibited the adult gene expression ‘signature’ [10].

Two studies evaluate the imaging marker such as ultrasound guided excisional biopsy and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) for detecting testicular masses [6, 7].

One study reported the phosphodiesterases (PDEs) expression was increased in Leydig cell tumor [8]. Another study suggested that prostein P501S might be a potential marker of testicular Leydig cell tumor [9].

Two studies identified several genes as potential markers of developmental stage-specific functions of Leydig cells or Leydig cell tumour development [10, 11].

Conclusion

In this literature search, the potential effect markers for Leydig cell proliferation/hyperplasia in relation to impaired fertility and Leydig cell tumor (AOP [51](#), [111](#), [120](#)) were searched. We identified one promising effect marker, Insulin-like factor 3 (INSL3) which can be measured either in blood or staining in the testis and is associated to fertility. INSL3 can be useful for districting the Leydig cell hyperplasia and Leydig cell tumor. Several possible effect markers were identified or suggested, and some are at gene expression level as well as imaging marker and the matrix are tissues. Thus, further studies are necessary to validate the finding in non-/low invasive matrices and confirm the association and septicity with the KEs and AOs of interest.

Table 1. Possible effect markers of Leydig cell proliferation and hyperplasia related to impaired fertility and increased Leydig cell tumors

Effect marker	Matrix	Measurement methods	Description of association with key event or adverse outcome in humans or if stated validation of measurement/effect marker.	Developmental status of the effect marker	Comments/Recommended for human epidemiological studies (Why, why not)	Author [ref.]
Insulin-like peptide 3 (INSL3)	Blood serum	- Hormone levels in serum: GC-MS (testosterone): electrochemiluminescence Immunoassay (LH, FSH, SHBG) - INSL3: fluorescent immunoassay and liquid chromatography–MS/MS	- No significant relationship between serum INSL3 concentration and semen parameters was observed. - There was a positive relationship between INSL3 and testosterone, FSH, but not LH concentration in general and heterogeneous populations. - No relationship was found between INSL3 and androgen receptor polymorphisms. -In general population, Leydig cell functional capacity as reflected in circulating INSL3 is highly consistent within an individual over long periods and that INSL3 is a powerful long-term index of Leydig cell status.	INSL3 has been suggested as a reliable biomarker for the number and mature differentiation status of the Leydig cells.	- INSL3 could be a constitutive and relatively robust indicator of Leydig cell functional capacity with little short-term biological variability, acutely independent of the HPG axis, avoiding of disadvantages of testosterone measurements.	Anand-Ivell et al 2022. [1]
Insulin-like 3 (INSL3)	Serum	Well-established and validated specific time-resolved fluorescent immunoassay.	- All hypogonadal subjects had significantly reduced INSL3 concentrations compared to the eugonadal subjects. - INSL3 showed a significant association with ever having had cancer.	New LC-MS procedure for measurement of INSL3 has been established and used.	- The circulating INSL3 represents a new and important independent parameter to identify primary Leydig cell insufficiency and hence sensitive biomarker of primary hypogonadism, and complementing the use of LH and/or T, which may be subject to influences at central/hypothalamic, pituitary, or on feedback systems.	Ivell et al 2022 [2]
Insulin-like 3 (INSL3)	Testicular tissue	- Immunohistochemistry (IHC)	- INSL3 expression were strongly and diffusely positive in the testicular tissue of patients with Leydig cell hyperplasia	The IHC staining is validated	INSL3 immunostaining could be helpful to highlight Leydig cells in the	Lakis et al 2019 [3]

			- In testicular tissue of patients with Leydig cell tumor, the INSL3 staining was markedly decreased or absent in tumor cells.		differential diagnosis between Leydig cell hyperplasia and Leydig cell tumor.	
Insulin-like factor 3 (INSL3)	- Gonadal tissue (testicular) - Blood serum	- INSL3 expression was conducted by Immunohistochemical staining - Serum INSL3 was quantified by liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) - Leydig cell hyperplasia was quantified based on the CYP11A1-positive cells, as CYP1A1 is a Leydig cell marker	- There was an overlap in expression between INSL3 and the Leydig cell markers CYP11A1. - No apparent link between serum INSL3 and clinical phenotype and histological phenotype. - Serum INSL3 concentrations seemed independent of other reproductive hormones and clinical features in males with 45,X/46,XY mosaicism.	Further studies are needed to elucidate the divergence between serum INSL3 and testosterone and the potential clinical use of INSL3 quantification.	INSL3 is considered a circulating marker that reflects Leydig cell number and differentiation status. Further prospective studies are needed to ascertain the clinical role of INSL3 in patients with 45,X/46,XY mosaicism.	Ljubicic et al. 2021[4]
Insulin-like 3 (INSL3)	Testis tissue	- Immunofluorescence (IFS): fluorescent staining - Gene expression: qPCR	- In the testicular adrenal rest tumors (TART) samples, no INSL3 staining was observed, indicating that there are no normal Leydig cells present in TART. - The expression levels of Leydig cell markers (<i>INSL3</i> and <i>HSD17B3</i>) were comparably high in both TART and testes tissue.	This study is the first study to report that TART have multiple steroidogenic properties. Further studies are needed to investigate the functional features of TART on mRNA and protein level.	The testicular adrenal rest tumors (TART) are lesions with both adrenocortical and Leydig cell features. Therefore, the origin of these tumors might be a more totipotent embryonic cell type such as fetal Leydig cells.	Smeets et al. 2015[5]
Imaging marker	Testicular tissue	- Scrotal and testicular ultrasonography - Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) - Histopathological analysis.	- In the boys with Leydig cell pathologies, testicular mass and scrotal asymmetry were detected. A smooth-edged, avascular, and hyperechoic mass was detected. - Leydig cell hyperplasia was determined in three boys and Leydig cell tumor in one boy.	This study focused on the surgery operation and effect markers were not discussed.	Ultrasonography was the main initial diagnostic modality for detecting testicular masses. MRI findings were in accordance with ultrasonography.	Emre et al. 2017[6]
Ultrasound guided excisional biopsy (DEB)	Testis	- Scrotal ultrasonography (SUS)	- Small incidental nodule (STN) is defined as a non-palpable (< 10 mm), asymptomatic solid	This is the experience of a single institution	- Frozen section examination (FSE) has demonstrated to be a	Fabiani et al. 2014[7]

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Diagnostic ultrasound guided excisional testicular biopsy (DEB) - Frozen section examination (FSE) 	<p>lesion with normal levels of oncological testicular markers.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SUS discovered STNs in 1.1 % patients and very small lesions (< 5 mm) in 50% of patients. - A concordance between testicular biopsies (FSE) and definitive pathologic report was observed in 75% of patients. 	<p>and needs to be confirmed by other studies.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ultrasound guided excisional biopsy with frozen section examination is the preferred option for initial management Intra-operative 	<p>highly reliable method to characterize testicular masses.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ultrasound guided excisional biopsy (DEB) and the close collaboration with pathologists are very useful in reducing errors in diagnosis of small incidental nodule (STN). - Ultrasound excisional biopsy is mandatory very difficult in many cases, especially without use of magnificent systems, when lesion is very small (< 5 mm). 	
Phosphodiesterases (PDEs)	testicular tissues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Expression of Phosphodiesterases (PDEs): QuantiGene plex assay (QGPA) - Real time PCR - Immunofluorescence analysis on human testis sections - Immunohistochemistry analysis on human testis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Both PDE8A and PDE8B are equally expressed in normal human Leydig cells. - Immunofluorescence analyses further reveals that PDE8A is also highly expressed in specific spermatogenic stages. -The expression of PDE8B but not of PDE8A is increased in transformed Leydig cells (Leydig cell tumors) compared to non-tumoral cells. - The up-regulation of PDE8B is not due to an increased abundance of Leydig cells in Leydig cell tumors compared to healthy tissue, but it is specifically due to a miss regulation of this enzyme in tumoral tissue. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - QuantiGene plex assay (QGPA) combining branched DNA (bDNA) signal amplification and multi-analyte profiling beads technologies enable the detection and quantitation of multiple mRNA targets simultaneously and the results obtained are more reliable since it reduces signal variability. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - This is the first study analyzing the expression of PDE genes in normal and tumoral human testis - Using different experimental approaches, the findings suggest that 1) a specific pool(s) of cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP) is/are regulated by PDE8A during spermiogenesis pointing out a possible new role of this PDE8 isoform in key events governing the differentiation and maturation of human sperm and 2) PDE8B can be involved in Leydig cell transformation. -Immunohistochemistry for inhibin and calretinin were used as confirmatory 	Campolo et al. 2022 [8]

					markers for the diagnosis of Leydig cell tumors.	
Prostein (P501S)	Testicular tissue	- Immunohistochemical stain	- P501S is a 553-amino acid protein and is specific to prostatic origin. - P501S showed routine expression in normal testicular tissue. - P501S staining showed diffuse moderate cytoplasmic positivity in 2/3 Leydig cell tumor of the testis.	Need validation	Cytoplasmic positivity for P501S can be seen in testicular Leydig cell tumor. Thus, P501S might be a potential marker of testicular Leydig cell tumor.	Arnesen et al 2020 [9]
Genetic marker	Testicular tissue	- Next-generation sequencing (NGS)	Compared to the healthy Leydig cell: - 132 genes involving the biological processes of response to temperature stimulus, positive regulation of cell death and cellular response to stress were downregulated while 78 genes associated with the biological processes of response to nutrient levels, toxic substances, oxidative stress were upregulated in Leydig cell tumours. - The most significant finding to emerge from this study is that changes in Leydig cell tumour transcriptome primarily involves (i) downregulation of apoptotic signalling that seems to be a characteristic feature of these type of tumours as well as (ii) disruption of vasculature development and other signalling molecules	Need validation	- It is the first time to report that a significant proportion of differentially expressed genes is directly involved in regulation of apoptotic process. The downregulation of these genes might be important to Leydig cell tumour development. - It is found a significant upregulation of heat shock protein genes that might be a unique feature of Leydig cell tumours when compared to other tumour types.	Kotula-Balak et al 2021 [10]
Genetic marker-global gene expression	Testis (foetal and adult)	- Transcriptome profiling was performed on Agilent whole human genome microarray 4 × 44 K chips. - Selected genes were studied at the protein level by immunohistochemistry (IHC).	- The transcriptomes of fetal Leydig cells and adult Leydig cells differed significantly. - The gene profiles of the normal adult Leydig cells and hyperplastic adult Leydig cells were similar despite morphological heterogeneity. - The study revealed several genes not known previously to be expressed in Leydig cells during early development, including Sulfotransferase family 2A member 1 (SULT2A1), WNT1-inducible signalling pathway protein 2 (WISP2), hydroxyprostaglandin dehydrogenase (HPGD)	Need validation	- This study identified several novel markers specific for either fetal Leydig cells or adult Leydig cells. Whether these genes can be used as Leydig cell effect marker needs more studies.	Lottrup et al 2017[11]

			<p>and insulin-like growth factor 2 mRNA binding protein 1 (IGF2BP1).</p> <p>- The expression changes of above genes were validated at the protein level.</p>			
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Reference

1. Anand-Ivell, R., et al., *Association of age, hormonal, and lifestyle factors with the Leydig cell biomarker INSL3 in aging men from the European Male Aging Study cohort*. *Andrology*, 2022. **10**(7): p. 1328-1338.
2. Ivell, R., et al., *The Leydig cell biomarker INSL3 as a predictor of age-related morbidity: Findings from the EMAS cohort*. *Front Endocrinol (Lausanne)*, 2022. **13**: p. 1016107.
3. Lakis, N.S., et al., *INSL3 Expression in Leydig Cell Hyperplasia and Leydig Cell Tumors*. *Appl Immunohistochem Mol Morphol*, 2019. **27**(3): p. 203-209.
4. Ljubicic, M.L., et al., *Serum Concentrations and Gonadal Expression of INSL3 in Eighteen Males With 45,X/46,XY Mosaicism*. *Front Endocrinol (Lausanne)*, 2021. **12**: p. 709954.
5. Smeets, E.E., et al., *Molecular characterization of testicular adrenal rest tumors in congenital adrenal hyperplasia: lesions with both adrenocortical and Leydig cell features*. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*, 2015. **100**(3): p. E524-30.
6. Emre, S., et al., *Testis sparing surgery for Leydig cell pathologies in children*. *J Pediatr Urol*, 2017. **13**(1): p. 51.e1-51.e4.
7. Fabiani, A., et al., *Diagnostic ultrasound-guided excisional testicular biopsy for small (< 1 cm) incidental nodules. A single institution experience*. *Arch Ital Urol Androl*, 2014. **86**(4): p. 373-7.
8. Campolo, F., et al., *cAMP-specific phosphodiesterase 8A and 8B isoforms are differentially expressed in human testis and Leydig cell tumor*. *Front Endocrinol (Lausanne)*, 2022. **13**: p. 1010924.
9. Arnesen, C., et al., *NKX3.1 and Prostein Expression in Testicular Tissue and Sex Cord-stromal Tumors*. *Am J Surg Pathol*, 2020. **44**(1): p. 61-67.
10. Kotula-Balak, M., et al., *Transcriptome analysis of human Leydig cell tumours reveals potential mechanisms underlying its development*. *Andrologia*, 2021. **53**(11): p. e14222.
11. Lottrup, G., et al., *Comparison of global gene expression profiles of microdissected human foetal Leydig cells with their normal and hyperplastic adult equivalents*. *Mol Hum Reprod*, 2017. **23**(5): p. 339-354.

Effect markers for androgen related AOPs (PARC 5.3.2 EMG)

Authors: Manhai Long, Maria Wielsøe, Eva Cecilie Bonefeld-Jørgensen – Department of Public Health, Aarhus University (AU-PH), Denmark

Biomarkers related to male fertility and malformation of male reproductive tract

As shown in Fig. 1, two AOPs ([51](#), [64](#)) linked to outcome of impaired fertility (AO [406](#)) and. The upstream key events for impaired fertility are hyperplasia in Leydig cell (KE [415](#)), increase proliferation in Leydig cell (KE [416](#)) and decreased sperm quantity or quality in the adult, decreased fertility (KE [520](#)). AOP [124](#) linked to decreased fertility (AO [330](#)) and the upstream key event is malformation of male reproductive tract (KE [809](#)).

AOP [288](#) linked to outcome of cryptorchidism malformation (AO [1616](#)) was identified. This AOP includes several key events including MIE [1609](#) and KEs ([1687](#), [1687](#), [1612](#), [1613](#), [1614](#) [1615](#)). The upstream key event for cryptorchidism malformation is impaired inguinoscrotal testicular descent phase (KE [1615](#)).

Three AOPs ([305](#), [306](#), [307](#)) linked to outcome of decrease in male anogenital distance (AGD) (AO [1688](#)) were identified. AOP [18](#) related to adverse outcome of male formation in male reproductive tract (AO [348](#)) and AOP [344](#) related to increased nipple retention (NR) (AO [1786](#)).

Fig. 1. Network of AOP 51 and AOP 64 related to the adverse outcome of impaired fertility (AO 406) and AOP 124 related to decreased fertility (AO 330). AOP 288 linked to adverse outcome of cryptorchidism (AO 1616), AOP 305, 306, 307 related to adverse outcome of decrease in anogenital distance (AGD) (AO 1688), AOP 18 related to adverse outcome of malformation in male reproductive tract (AO 348) and AOP 344 related to increased nipple retention (NR) (AO 1786). Yellow boxes are early events and green boxes are upstream key events. Blue boxes are adverse outcomes. For the events with orange border, relevant effect marker was identified and listed in the Year 1 AD 5.5 report (2023). The events with black border are those no effect markers relevant for epidemiological studies were identified. The blue boxes are the AO's.

Methods:

We searched for potential effect markers by focusing on the upstream events of the related adverse outcomes (KE [415](#), [416](#), [520](#), [809](#), [1615](#)) in PubMed using the search string in following box on the February 1, 2024. The search restricted to the last 5 years.

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("Proliferation"[Title/Abstract] OR "Hyperplasia"[Title/Abstract] OR "Malformation "[Title/Abstract]) AND ("effect marker"[Title/Abstract] OR "biomarker"[Title/Abstract] OR "gene expression"[Title/Abstract] OR "measurement"[Title/Abstract]) AND ("sperm"[Title/Abstract] OR "Leydig cells"[Title/Abstract] OR "reproductive tract"[Title/Abstract] OR "inguinoscrotal Testicular"[Title/Abstract]) AND (y_5[Filter]) AND (humans[Filter]) AND (male[Filter]) AND (english[Filter]) NOT (Review)
```

Methods

As shown in Fig. 2, of the 488 hits in the PubMed search, 208 articles are review articles or no full text published before 2019 and thus were excluded. Among the remaining 280 original articles, five article were comments or letters. There were 100 articles involved non-human species, while 11 studies were case reports or opinions. There were 111 articles not relevant to focused KE and AOs. Finally, 20 articles are included in the review of the possible effect markers for proliferation in Leydig cells and malformation of male reproductive tract (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Flow chart of literature search and selection for effect biomarker relevant to proliferation, hyperplasia in Leydig cells and male reproductive tract malformation.

Result and Discussion

Table 1 lists the included 20 studies regarding the possible effect markers of Leydig cell proliferation/hyperplasia and malformation of male reproductive tract. The adverse outcome of impaired fertility and decrease fertility are included in four AOPs (AOP [51](#), [64](#), [124](#), [288](#)) relevant for this search (Fig. 1).

Five studies measured Insulin-like factor 3 (INSL3) in serum/plasma [1-3] or INSL3 expression in testicular tissue [4, 5]. Serum INSL3 reference range have been established for puberty boy and males with hypogonadotropic hypogonadism and Klinefelter syndrome and serum level of INSL3 could represents an additional downstream marker of the Leydig cell function when assessing the hypothalamic–pituitary–gonadal (HPG) axis. The measurement of INSL3 expression has been used as specific marker of Leydig cell maturation. One study also showed serum level of inhibin B had similar function as INSL3 and indicated INSL3 as more accurately differentiated congenital hypogonadotropic hypogonadism in adult men while inhibin B better identifies boys with delayed puberty [1].

The other studies suggested expression of delta subunit of mitochondrial ATP synthase (ATP5D) as a potential biomarker for male fertility [6], and serum amyloid P component (SAP) concentration in seminal plasma might be a new, indirect biomarker for sperm concentration [7].

One study suggested eight genes (THEG, SPATA20, ROPN1L, GSTF1, TSSK1B, CABS1, ADAD1 and RIMBP3) can be used as potential biomarkers for the early detection of non-obstructive azoospermia (NOA) by using the publicly available database of testis [8]. Another study showed higher E2F1 copy number variations increased the risk of spermatogenic Impairment and suggested E2F1 gene is emerging as a novel, important determinant of testicular development and function [9]. Insulin-like growth factor 1 (IGF1) and CYP11A1 were used as Leydig cell specific marker in one study [10].

Two in vitro studies of human semen showed that Glycoprotein integrin $\alpha 5\beta 1$ can be a potential marker of male fertility [11] and metabolic hormone FGF21 positively modifies the activity and quality of the parameters of human spermatozoa [12]. But validation is necessary.

The rest of studies discussed the role of serum level of sex hormones [13, 14] and small protein Osteocalcin (OCN) [15] in impaired/decrease fertility. One study addressed that seminal plasma could be considered a promising matrix when evaluating the male reproductive health [16]. In addition, the genetic marker such as DEAH-Box Helicase 37 (DHX37) for the gonadal dysgenesis is suggested [17]. It was reported levels of apelin were negatively correlated with all sperm parameters [18] and expression of Estrogen sulfotransferase (SULTE1) and steroid sulfatase (STS) an unbalance of the STS/SULT1E1 pathway contributes to the testicular hyper-estrogenic microenvironment in patients with primary spermatogenic failure and Leydig cell dysfunction [19]. However, the specificity of these markers needs further validation. One study showed that scrotal magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is a very effective tool for the evaluation of azoospermic men and it is not dependent on operator experience [20].

Conclusion:

In this literature search, the potential effect markers for Leydig cell proliferation/hyperplasia and malformation of male reproductive tract in relation to impaired or decreased fertility. We identified one promising effect marker, INSL3, which can be measured in blood and is associated to fertility. Several *possible* effect markers were identified or suggested, and most are at gene expression level and the matrix are tissues. Thus, further studies are necessary to validate the finding in non-/low invasive matrices and confirm the association and specificity with the related KEs and AOs.

Table 1 Possible effect markers of Leydig cell proliferation and malformation of male reproductive tract

Effect marker	Matrix	Measurement methods	Description of association with key event or adverse outcome in humans or if stated validation of measurement/effect marker.	Developmental status of the effect marker	Comments/Recommended for human epidemiological studies (Why, why not)	Author [ref.]
-Insulin-like factor 3 (INSL3) - Inhibin B (INHB)	Blood serum	- Inhibin B (INB): solid-phase sandwich enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) - INSL3: well,-validated and specific time-resolved fluorescent immunoassay	- In adult men, serum level of INSL3 and INHB were lower in congenital hypogonadotropic hypogonadism patients than eugonadal men. - In boys, serum levels of INSL3 and INB were lower in boys with congenital hypogonadotropic hypogonadism than boys with constitutional delay of growth and puberty (constitutional delay of growth and puberty). - Positive correlation between INSL3 and INB both found in adult men with congenital hypogonadotropic hypogonadism and boy with constitutional delay of growth and puberty. - INSL3 more accurately differentiated congenital hypogonadotropic hypogonadism in adult men while INHB better identifies boys with delayed puberty - Pathologies affecting the hypothalamo-pituitary gonadal (HPG) axis including congenital hypogonadotropic hypogonadism and primary testicular disorders (i.e Klinefelter syndrome, cryptorchidism and anorchidism) are all associated with lower serum levels of INSL3.	Measurement methods are validated. Recently Liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) has been validated for the quantification of INSL3 and reference range established and tested in healthy boys progressing through puberty, males with hypogonadotropic hypogonadism and Klinefelter syndrome.	- Unlike testosterone, INSL3 is not subject to episodic fluctuation inherent to the feedback loop in the HPG axis, thus making INSL3 an emerging biomarker of disorders affecting the male HPG axis. - INSL3 could represents an additional downstream marker of the Leydig cell function when assessing the HPG axis	Abbara et al 2022 [1]
INSL3	- Serum - Semen	- Serum INSL3: Time-resolved fluorescent immunoassay and LC-MS/MS	- No significant associations between serum level of INSL3 and semen parameters, trinucleotide repeat variants of AR and LH concentration as well as T/LH ratio (an alternative	The measurement methods of INSL3 are validated.	- Two mutually supportive cohort studies in men from Sweden and Australia could not observed the significant association	Anand-Ivell et al 2021 [2]

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Semen parameters: CASA, DFI, TUNEL - Androgen receptor trinucleotide repeat analysis: nested PCR 	<p>measure of Leydig cell functional capacity) were observed.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - INSL3 positively associated with sex hormones (T, FSH) and testis size. 		<p>between serum INSL3 concentrations and semen parameters representing spermatogenesis.</p>	
INSL3	Plasma	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Plasma INSL3 was measured using a spectrophotometry enzyme immunoassay Elisa sandwich technique 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The appendix testis (AT) incidence in patients with cryptorchidism is lower compared to that of patients with normally descended testes (AT). - A positive correlation between the length of the AT and plasma concentrations of INSL3 was observed in boys with congenital cryptorchidism. - A longer AT may possibly reflect better testicular function in boys with congenital cryptorchidism 	<p>Measurement of INSL3 can be done using commercial kit.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Further studies are required in a larger study population with cryptorchidism to verify if the length of the AT strongly correlates with INSL3 plasma concentrations and testicular function. 	<p>Panagidis et al. 2020 [3]</p>
INSL3, AR expression	Testicular tissue	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Immunostaining - Immunohistochemistry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Androgen receptor (AR) expression and INSL3 expression are significantly reduced in Klinefelter syndrome (KS) patients compared to normal spermatogenesis controls, suggesting Leydig cells lack maturation in KS patients. 	<p>This study used INSL3 as a marker of Leydig cell maturation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - This study involved the large sample size of KS patients, and the results highlight a compromised somatic compartment demonstrated by some abnormal Sertoli Cell (SCs) features and the Leydig cells lack maturation. - INSL3 expression is effect marker of Leydig cells. 	<p>Giudice et al 2019 [4]</p>
INSL3, AR expression	Testicular	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scrotal ultrasound examination - Histopathological examination - Immunofluorescence experiment - Immunohistochemical experiment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The INSL3 and androgen receptor (AR) were highly expressed and roughly balanced in focal spermatogenesis - Immunofluorescence single and double labeling showed that the proportion of AR and INSL3 receptors is seriously imbalanced in the testicular tissue around the seminiferous tubules without spermatogenesis. - The concentration of INSL3 deposition in the seminiferous tubules 	<p>This study also performed literature review about Klinefelter syndrome. They found the changes with age of serum level of INSL3 was relatively stable compared to testosterone and luteinizing hormone.</p>	<p>As abnormal metabolism of Leydig cells led to imbalanced expression of the INSL3 receptor and AR, authors believed that the ratio of INSL3 combined with testosterone may be more suitable as an accurate indicator for predicting spermatogenesis in patients with Klinefelter syndrome.</p>	<p>Liu et al 2023 [5]</p>

			<p>with sperm was significantly higher than that in the seminiferous tubules without sperm.</p> <p>- A balanced of AR and INSL3 receptors is an important basis for ensuring spermatogenesis.</p>			
ATP5D (delta subunit of mitochondrial ATP synthase)	Semen	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sperm morphology: HE-staining and Diff-Quik staining. - ATP5D protein: ELISA - ATP5D mutation: singer sequencing. - Genotype Identification of ATP5D: qRT-PCR. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The expression of protein ATP5D in the sperm of infertile males was significantly lower than that in normal males. No ATP5D mutation is observed. This suggest ATP5D might affect male fertility at the protein level. - The ATP5D levels in the sperms were positively correlated with total sperm counts, sperm concentrations, normal morphology, forward vitality, and total vitality. -This study also performed animal study and showed ATP5D deletion or overexpression causes decreased sperm count, poor vitality, and severe sperm abnormalities, which leads to male infertility in male mice. 	The methods for measurement of ATP5D are routine lab methods.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The role of ATP5D in human male fertility is addressed. The ATP5D gene can be used as a candidate marker for identification of idiopathic male infertility. Thus, ATP5D is a potential biomarker for male fertility. 	Wang et al 2023 [6]
Serum amyloid P component (SAP)	Semen	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SAP concentration in seminal plasma: validated sandwich ELISA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Positive association between Serum amyloid P component (SAP) and sperm concentration, sperm number, semen volume and sperm motility - Negative association between SAP and nonprogressive motility and immobility. - Men with a sperm concentration lower than the WHO reference value had statistically significant lower SAP concentrations than men with a sperm concentration higher than or equal to the WHO reference value. - SAP levels in semen from azoospermic and postvasectomized men were lower than controls 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Serum amyloid P component (SAP) is a protein present in seminal plasma with a concentration of around 1 mg/ L. In serum, however, the level of SAP in men is around 40 mg/L. - The SAP-ELISA is based on commercially available reagents and can be easily implemented in the laboratories. SAP can also be measured in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - This study showed that the concentration of SAP in seminal plasma was correlated positively with sperm concentration, and this can enable distinction between samples with a sperm concentration of $< \text{or } \geq 5 \times 10^6 / \text{ml}$ and $< \text{or } \geq 15 \times 10^6 / \text{ml}$. Thus, SAP in seminal plasma is potentially a new, indirect biomarker for sperm concentration that can be easily performed and stored samples can be 	Sonesson et al 2021 [7]

				thawed seminal plasma samples.	used which is applicable in a research setting.	
Genetic marker	Testis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identification of common differential expressed genes (DEGs): gene expression omnibus (GEO) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Twenty-five DEGs were identified across five different datasets and are shown to be involved in impaired spermatogenesis and male infertility - Eight Genes THEG, TSSK1B, ADAD1, RIMBP3, CABS1, GTSF1, ROPN1L, SPATA20 significantly downregulated in impaired spermatogenesis and infertility - These genes are involved in spermatogenesis, spermatozoa structures, sperm maturation, sperm morphology, sperm motility, acrosome formation and maintains mitochondria function during spermatogenesis. 	The gene expression data is obtained from the Publicly available transcriptomic data	The alteration in the expression of THEG, SPATA20, ROPN1L, GSTF1, TSSK1B, CABS1, ADAD1 and RIMBP3 leads to impaired spermatogenesis and male infertility. Thus, these genes can be used as potential biomarkers for the early detection of non-obstructive azoospermia (NOA).	Omolaoye et al 2022 [8]
DNA dosage: Copy number variations (CNVs)	Peripheral blood leukocytes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - E2F1 Copy number variation (CNV) analysis: Quantitative real-time polymerase chain reaction (qPCR) Taq-Man Copy Number Assays - E2F1 and HSP70 expression: Real-time PCR 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Copy number variations (CNVs) play an important role in the onset of several diseases - It is observed that frequency of E2F1 CNVs in infertile men was significantly higher than control. - Significantly inverse association was found between E2F1 CNVs and both total sperm count and sperm concentration - This study reports a link between E2F1 CNVs and idiopathic male infertility. 	Need to validate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - E2F1 is a transcription factor and is a regulator of important cellular pathways. Recent studies have reported that CNVs involving the E2F1 gene are linked to non-obstructive azoospermia. - E2F1 gene is emerging as a novel, important determinant of testicular development and function 	Rocca et al 2019 [9]
Genetic marker	Testicular Tissues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNA-seq) profiling - Leydig cell-specific marker gene (<i>IGF1</i>) - Immunofluorescence staining with Leydig cell marker CYP11A1 was used to quantify Leydig cell number -Western Blot 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The quantification of Leydig cell numbers through immunostaining of CYP11A1, showed a significant decrease during aging. - In older Leydig cells, the genes PTEN, RHOB, and ROCK1/2 are upregulated. These genes suppress cell survival and proliferation and thus result in cell growth suppression. 	This study focuses primarily on transcriptomic profiling with additional protein validation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The potential candidate genetic biomarkers for the diagnosis of aging-associated testis pathology are suggested. - Future studies that involve large patient cohorts are needed to further validation. 	Nie et al. 2022 [10]

Sperm Integrin $\alpha 5\beta 1$	semen	- Immunofluorescence assay	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Glycoprotein integrin $\alpha 5\beta 1$ is distributed in sperm and most viable sperm displayed $\alpha 5\beta 1$ in the acrosomal region. - Integrin $\alpha 5\beta 1$ in the acrosomal region correlates with sperm quality -The early embryo development rate correlated positively with the localization of $\alpha 5\beta 1$ - The studies of co-incubation of sperm with oviductal cells showed that approximately 85% of release sperm displayed $\alpha 5\beta 1$ in the acrosomal region, which supports the importance of acrosomal $\alpha 5\beta 1$ from a more physiological perspective. 	This is an in vitro study using human semen. The further validation is needed.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - As sperm integrin positively correlates with sperm quality and integrin $\alpha 5\beta 1$ localized in sperm acrosomal region correlate with good rates of usable embryos obtained, the sperm integrin $\alpha 5\beta 1$ can be a potential marker of fertility in men. - The evaluation of sperm integrin $\alpha 5\beta 1$ immunolocalization could be a useful tool to select sperm with fertilizing ability from human semen samples before IVF. 	Vernaz et al 2022 [11]
FGF21	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Semen - Blood plasma 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ELISA - Immunoprecipitation assay - Western Immunoblotting - Immunohistochemistry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - FGF21 is a metabolic hormone mainly produced by the liver. FGF21 exist in both blood and seminal fluid. The concentration of FGF21 in seminal fluid was around 20-fold lower than that in the blood serum (50-5000pg/mL). - The levels of FGF21 in seminal fluid is independent of the BMI, semen volume, sperm concentration or abnormalities. - The FGF21 in seminal fluid is potentially produced by the different tissue of male reproductive tract. - The FGF21 was expressed in Leydig cells but not in spermatozoa. The receptors of FGF21 are localized in spermatozoa and FGF21 can transduce the signaling in spermatozoa. 	In vitro study using human semen. The measurement methods are commercial kits and software.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - These results seem to indicate that the metabolic factor, FGF21, positively modifies the activity and quality of the parameters of human spermatozoa. - It is proposed the endocrine factor FGF21 as a novel regulator of male reproductive function with direct actions on germ cells. 	Bourdon et al 2022 [12]
Sex hormones	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Testicular - Serum 	- Histological examination of testis (Morphometric analysis)	- Sertoli cell-only syndrome patients had lower testis volume, seminiferous tubule diameter but higher thickness of tubular membrane, intertubular space area and Leydig cell numbers	The finding of increased number of Leydig cells simultaneously with abnormal T/LH ratio suggests impaired	- It is hypothesized that the increased number of Leydig cells per clusters in biopsies with impaired spermatogenesis may be	Adamczewska et al 2020 [13]

		<p>Number of Leydig cell: semi-quantitative assessment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Serum hormones: enhanced chemiluminescence method 	<p>compared to subjects with normal spermatogenesis</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sertoli cell-only syndrome patients had higher serum levels of FSH and LH than normal spermatogenesis - In Sertoli cell-only syndrome group FSH and LH levels correlated positively with intertubular space area and Leydig cell number while T/LH ratio positively correlated with seminiferous tubule diameter but correlated with intertubular space area negatively. - In normal spermatogenesis group only positive correlation between FSH levels and area fraction of intertubular space area was observed. - Increased serum levels of LH and FSH, may reflect dysfunction of Leydig cells. 	<p>function of these cells. Increased serum levels of LH, and FSH, may reflect Leydig cells dysfunction</p>	<p>the result of smaller seminiferous tubule diameter and thus 'shrinkage' of tubular compartment resulting in regrouping of Leydig cell to form larger cluster</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It seems that reproductive hormones levels reflect the condition of testicular structure, and that FSH may be related to the changes in intertubular space area independently of impaired Leydig cell function. 	
Hormones	Serum	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Chemiluminescent microparticle immunoassay - Serum Inhibin B (INHB) was measured using an enzymatically amplified two-site two-step sandwich-type immunoassay (ELISA) - Serum AMH concentration was measured using a Gen II enzyme linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sertoli cells function marker, i.e. Inhibin B (INHB), Müllerian hormone (AMH) was significantly higher in Klinefelter syndrome than controls in early childhood. - During mini-puberty, FSH (Sertoli cells function marker) and Leydig cells function marker (LH and T) were significantly higher in Klinefelter syndrome infants than controls. - No significant differences were found in testicular volume, and penile length between Klinefelter syndrome and controls. - The presence of higher levels of gonadotropins, INHB and testosterone during mini-puberty and pre-puberty may be interpreted as an alteration of 	<p>The sex hormones can be measured using commercial kit.</p>	<p>This study of gonadal function in a population of young boys with Klinefelter syndrome demonstrates the importance of following boys at all ages, from birth until pre-puberty.</p>	<p>Spaziani et al 2021 [14]</p>

			the HPG axis in Klinefelter syndrome infants.			
Osteocalcin (OCN)	- Serum - Leukocytes	- Serum levels of carboxylated (cxOCN) and undercarboxylated osteocalcin (ucOCN): commercial Enzyme Linked Immunosorbent Assay - Genetic screening for GPRC6A rs2274911 polymorphism	- Compared to normozoospermia subjects, serum levels of both ucOCN and cxOCN were significantly reduced in azoospermic patients - Serum levels of ucOCN and cxOCN negatively correlated with serum FSH. Higher serum ucOCN associated with higher testosterone. - The genotype distribution of GPRC6A SNP differ between normozoospermic subjects (higher GG genotype) and azoospermic patients (higher AA genotype). - Compared to patients bearing the GG genotype, patients with the GA genotype had lower sperm count and lower normal morphology - Patients bearing the GA or AA genotype had lower serum testosterone levels. - The data suggest the involvement of ucOCN-GPRC6A axis in the regulation of testosterone production by the testis, subsidiary to hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal axis (HPG). - On the base of these results, the ucOCN-GPRC6A axis appears as complementary to the classical LH-mediated pathway in the regulation of testosterone production and, in turn, of spermatogenesis.	The measurement methods are validated. However, whether serum OCN can be used as biomarker of spermatogenesis needs further studies.	Osteocalcin (OCN) is a small protein, expressed by osteoblasts. Recent evidence supported the possible role of ucOCN as a hormone, showing to regulate testosterone biosynthesis in Leydig cells of animals. GPRC6A, a metabotropic G protein-coupled receptor expressed in the Leydig cells of the testis, mediates OCN activities.	Jawich et al 2022 [15]
Oxidized products of nucleic acids (8-oxo-Gua, 8-oxo-Guo)	- Seminal plasma - Urine	- Liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS)	- 8-oxodGuo concentrations in seminal plasma inversely associated with the semen volume - Higher number of significant correlations correlation between exposure biomarkers (chemicals	It is well known that oxidative stress can affect the male reproductive tract and spermatogenesis, which results in the production	Seminal plasma could be considered a promising matrix to measure toxicants or their metabolites at the male reproductive tract level,	Poli et al [16]

and 8-oxo-dGuo)			known to cause oxidative stress and with suspected male reproductive toxicity) and effect biomarkers (oxidized products of nucleic acids) were observed in seminal plasma than in urine, especially in the case of 8-oxodGuo.	of sperm of poor quality. oxidized products of nucleic acids measured in biological fluids, such as seminal plasma and urine could be suitable biomarkers of the effects of oxidative stress.	when reproductive effect are expected.	
Genetic marker-DHX37	Peripheral blood leukocytes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Whole-exome sequencing (WES) - Targeted disorders of sex development (DSD) gene panels - Sanger sequencing for DHX37 gene - Variant identification: American College of Medical Genetics criteria 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DEAH-Box Helicase 37 (DHX37) protein was identified in different testicular cells. DHX37 expression is found in Leydig cell cytoplasm and in germ cells at different stages of maturation. - The DHX37 variants identified in this cohort of disorders of sex development (DSD) patients was markedly higher than that observed in normal individuals - Four patients with micro-penis or perineal hypospadias and/or hypergonadotropic hypogonadism are reported to have deletions or rearrangements involving the 12q24 chromosomal region which contains DHX37. 	Need to validate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - This study observed DHX37 is expressed during specific stages of germ-cell maturation, in Leydig cells, and rarely in Sertoli cells. - The defects in DHX37 are associated with the Gonadal dysgenesis spectrum 	Da Silva et al 2019 [17]
Apelin	Semen	Apelin in seminal plasma and spermatozoa: sandwich quantitative enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Apelin was present in spermatozoa and apelin levels were negatively correlated with all sperm parameters, especially normal sperm morphology and positively with inflammatory marker IL-1β levels. - Apelin levels were significantly lower in spermatozoa of fertile subjects than those observed in spermatozoa of patients with varicocele and genitourinary infections. - Apelin/APJ receptor (APJ-R) is involved in many oxidative stress-induced pathological conditions. 	Needs validation	The specificity may not be strong due to mainly related to infection	Moretti et al 2023 [18]

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In testis, apelin and APJ-R labels were evident in Leydig cells and weak inside the seminiferous tubule. Apelin/APJ-R system is present in human spermatozoa and testicular tissue and probably involved in human fertility. 			
Genetic marker: expression of SULTE1 and STS	Testis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - RT-qPCR - Laser-capture microdissection - Immunofluorescence 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Estrogen sulfotransferase (SULT1E1) mRNA accumulation was similar in the testes of patients with Sertoli cell-only syndrome and patients with obstructive azoospermia and normal spermatogenesis - The amount of steroid sulfatase (STS) mRNA was higher in Sertoli cell-only syndrome cases and inversely correlated with T/LH ratio - Both SULT1E1 and STS mRNA abundance was similar in Leydig cell clusters and the tubular compartment, except for lower SUTL1E1 mRNA in the seminiferous tubules of Sertoli cell-only syndrome patients -The results suggest that an unbalance of the STS/SULT1E1 pathway contributes to the testicular hyper-estrogenic microenvironment in patients with primary spermatogenic failure and Leydig cell dysfunction. 	This study focused on Sertoli cell-only syndrome represents a common severe spermatogenic impairment in primary testicular failure with the absence of germ cells and is associated with major morphological and functional disturbance of the Leydig cell compartment.	Overexpression of steroid sulfatase (STS) in testis might be a potential biomarker of Leydig cell dysfunction in primary spermatogenic failure? But the marker related to estrogen.	Lardone et al. 2021 [19]
Imaging marker: MRI	Scrotum and lower pelvis	- Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Testicular volume and apparent diffusion coefficient values are useful parameters in distinguishing patients with obstructive azoospermia from patients with non-obstructive azoospermia. - Testes of obstructive azoospermia patients had significantly lower apparent diffusion coefficient values than non-obstructive azoospermia patients 	- Scrotal MRI is a very effective tool for the evaluation of azoospermic men and it is not dependent on operator experience.	- This study was able to make a diagnosis of obstructive azoospermia with a sensitivity of 81% and specificity of 90%, based on testicular apparent diffusion coefficient values alone	Regent et al 2020 [20]

References

1. Abbara, A., et al., *Insulin-like peptide 3 (INSL3) in congenital hypogonadotropic hypogonadism (CHH) in boys with delayed puberty and adult men*. *Front Endocrinol (Lausanne)*, 2022. **13**: p. 1076984.
2. Anand-Ivell, R., et al., *Male seminal parameters are not associated with Leydig cell functional capacity in men*. *Andrology*, 2021. **9**(4): p. 1126-1136.
3. Panagidis, A., et al., *Correlation between insulin-like peptide 3 and appendix testis length in congenital cryptorchidism*. *J Paediatr Child Health*, 2020. **56**(8): p. 1283-1289.
4. Giudice, M.G., M. Vermeulen, and C. Wyns, *Blood Testis Barrier and Somatic Cells Impairment in a Series of 35 Adult Klinefelter Syndrome Patients*. *Int J Mol Sci*, 2019. **20**(22).
5. Liu, H., et al., *Leydig cell metabolic disorder act as a new mechanism affecting for focal spermatogenesis in Klinefelter syndrome patients: a real world cross-sectional study base on the age*. *Front Endocrinol (Lausanne)*, 2023. **14**: p. 1266730.
6. Wang, Y.B., et al., *ATP5D Is a Potential Biomarker for Male Fertility*. *Oxid Med Cell Longev*, 2023. **2023**: p. 4923614.
7. Sonesson, A., et al., *Serum amyloid P component: a new biomarker for low sperm concentration?* *Asian J Androl*, 2021. **23**(5): p. 450-455.
8. Omolaoye, T.S., M.Y. Hachim, and S.S. du Plessis, *Using publicly available transcriptomic data to identify mechanistic and diagnostic biomarkers in azoospermia and overall male infertility*. *Sci Rep*, 2022. **12**(1): p. 2584.
9. Rocca, M.S., et al., *E2F1 copy number variations contribute to spermatogenic impairment and cryptorchidism by increasing susceptibility to heat stress*. *Andrology*, 2019. **7**(2): p. 251-256.
10. Nie, X., et al., *Single-cell analysis of human testis aging and correlation with elevated body mass index*. *Dev Cell*, 2022. **57**(9): p. 1160-1176.e5.
11. Vernaz, Z.J., et al., *Evaluation of sperm integrin $\alpha 5\beta 1$ as a potential marker of fertility in humans*. *PLoS One*, 2022. **17**(8): p. e0271729.
12. Bourdon, G., et al., *The Hepatokine FGF21 Increases the Human Spermatozoa Motility*. *Front Endocrinol (Lausanne)*, 2022. **13**: p. 775650.
13. Adamczewska, D., et al., *Features of gonadal dysgenesis and Leydig cell impairment in testes with Sertoli cell-only syndrome*. *Folia Histochem Cytobiol*, 2020. **58**(2): p. 73-82.
14. Spaziani, M., et al., *From mini-puberty to pre-puberty: early impairment of the hypothalamus-pituitary-gonadal axis with normal testicular function in children with non-mosaic Klinefelter syndrome*. *J Endocrinol Invest*, 2021. **44**(1): p. 127-138.
15. Jawich, K., et al., *RS 2247911 polymorphism of GPRC6A gene and serum undercarboxylated-osteocalcin are associated with testis function*. *J Endocrinol Invest*, 2022. **45**(9): p. 1673-1682.
16. Poli, D., et al., *The Relationship Between Widespread Pollution Exposure and Oxidized Products of Nucleic Acids in Seminal Plasma and Urine in Males Attending a Fertility Center*. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*, 2020. **17**(6).
17. da Silva, T.E., et al., *Genetic Evidence of the Association of DEAH-Box Helicase 37 Defects With 46,XY Gonadal Dysgenesis Spectrum*. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*, 2019. **104**(12): p. 5923-5934.
18. Moretti, E., et al., *Apelin is found in human sperm and testis and is raised in inflammatory pathological conditions*. *Cytokine*, 2023. **169**: p. 156281.
19. Lardone, M.C., et al., *Testicular steroid sulfatase overexpression is associated with Leydig cell dysfunction in primary spermatogenic failure*. *Andrology*, 2021. **9**(2): p. 657-664.
20. Regent, B., et al., *MRI in the evaluation of the azoospermic male*. *Diagn Interv Radiol*, 2020. **26**(4): p. 271-276.

Effect markers for androgen related AOPs (PARC 5.3.2 EMG)

Authors: Manhai Long, Maria Wielsøe, Eva Cecilie Bonefeld-Jørgensen – Department of Public Health, Aarhus University (AU-PH), Denmark

Proliferation in hepatocytes

One AOP ([117](#)) linked to outcome of Increase hepatocellular adenomas and carcinomas ([AO 719](#)). This AOP includes several events including activation of androgen receptor (MIE [785](#)) and KEs ([716](#) and [774](#)). The upstream key events for increased hepatocellular carcinoma are increased hepatocytes proliferation (KE [716](#)) and preneoplastic foci (KE [774](#)). We therefore search the possible effect markers focusing on these two events (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Network of AOP [117](#) linked to adverse outcome hepatocellular adenomas ([AO 719](#)). Yellow boxes are early events and green boxes are upstream key events. Blue box is the adverse outcome. The events with black border are those no effect markers relevant for epidemiological studies were identified.

Methods

Because the aim is to find novel effect markers for epidemiological studies, the search restricted to the last 5 years and the articles must be conducted in human with the information on the relevant KEs or AO. The search in PubMed using the following search string box were conducted on Febury 10, 2024.

("Preneoplastic foci "[Title/Abstract] OR "Proliferation"[Title/Abstract]) AND ("effect marker"[Title/Abstract] OR "biomarker"[Title/Abstract] OR "gene expression"[Title/Abstract] OR "measurement"[Title/Abstract]) AND ("hepatocytes "[Title/Abstract]) AND (y_5[Filter]) AND (humans[Filter]) AND (english[Filter]) NOT (Review)

As shown in Fig. 2, of the 52 hits in the PubMed search, 18 articles are review articles or no full text. Fourteen articles involved only non-human species and one article was retracted. There were 15 articles not relevant to the KEs or AO of interest. Finally, 4 articles were included in the review.

Fig. 2. Flow chart of literature search and selection for effect biomarker relevant to hepatocyte proliferation

Results and Discussion

Four relevant articles were found and the information regarding the possible effect marker in these studies are listed in Table 1. All four studies used tissue or human cells and the markers were at protein or gene level and proposed the markers as prognostic biomarker for the hepatocyte carcinoma [1-4]. The expression of protein Lysozyme, MicroRNA 155, and Toll-like receptor 3 were identified as independent prognostic biomarkers for hepatocellular carcinoma [2, 4]. Lysozyme has been found to exist ubiquitously in human blood, whether this marker can be used in the epidemiology studies needs further validation. Two studies established a score to evaluate the overall activity of genes on prognosis of hepatocellular carcinoma [1, 3].

Conclusion:

This literature review linked the *network of AOP 117 to adverse outcome hepatocellular adenomas (AO 719)*. The potential effect markers of hepatocyte proliferation or preneoplastic foci related to the adverse outcome of hepatocellular adenomas /carcinomas were suggested. The suggested effect markers need to be validated further before they can be used in epidemiological studies.

Table 1: Possible effect markers of increased hepatocytes proliferation and preneoplastic foci

Effect marker	Matrix	Measurement methods	Description of association with key event or adverse outcome in humans or if stated validation of measurement/effect marker.	Developmental status of the effect marker	Comments/Recommended for human epidemiological studies (Why, why not)	Author [ref.]
E2F transcription factors	Human hepatocellular carcinoma tissues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The gene expression profiles of human hepatocellular carcinoma patient cohorts were obtained from The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) and Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) databases - E2F targets score generated by using the Molecular Signature Database (MSigDB). - Immune cell infiltrations and cytolytic activity in the tumor microenvironment: xCell algorithm, - Gene set enrichment analysis: Gene set variation analysis (GSVA) method and Gene set enrichment analysis (GSEA) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - E2F transcription factors (E2F1-F8) play critical roles in cell cycle and each E2F transcription factors (E2F1-F8) have opposing functions during carcinogenesis as oncogenes or tumor suppressors. Therefore, the overall activity of E2F transcription factors was generated named as E2F targets score. - E2F targets score was associated with clinical aggressiveness of human hepatocellular carcinoma: tumor grade, tumor size, proliferation and pathological grade -The E2F target score associated with cancer aggressiveness and worse survival. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - This study is a retrospective study based on databases and performed a series analyses. - Because treatment data of the human hepatocellular carcinoma cohorts used in this study was not available, the utility of E2F target score as a predictive biomarker in human hepatocellular carcinoma patients can't be assessed. A prospective study is needed to validate this. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - This study used the previously generated E2F targets score that quantified the overall E2F target gene expressions and demonstrated that E2F score reflects the aggressiveness of human hepatocellular carcinoma and is a prognostic biomarker using multiple independent cohorts with a total of 655 hepatocellular carcinoma patients. 	Chida et al 2023 [1]
Lysozyme	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hepatocellular carcinoma tumor tissue - Human cell lines - Mice 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cell proliferation was monitored by the RTCA system on an xCELLigence RTCA DP instrument (ACEA Biosciences). - Immunoprecipitation, Mass Spectrometry, and Western Blot - Immunofluorescence - Immunohistochemistry (HCC tissue microarrays) - Public HCC Proteomic Data Processing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lysozyme preferred to be expressed in the poorly differentiated hepatocellular carcinoma cells with higher proliferative and metastatic potential. - Lysozyme promotes hepatocellular carcinoma proliferation and migration through targeting cell surface GRP78 of hepatocytes 	The used human cell lines and hepatocellular carcinoma tissue were bought from the commercial companies.	- Lysozyme expression is identified as an independent prognostic biomarker for hepatocellular carcinoma and therapeutic target for the subclass of human hepatocellular carcinoma with an aggressive phenotype	Gu et al 2023 [2]
Genetic marker	Not specify	- DNA repair pathway score was measured as the gene set variation analysis (GSVA) score for the "Hallmark DNA repair" gene set of the Molecular Signatures Database (MSigDB)	- DNA repair pathway was enhanced by the stepwise carcinogenic process of human hepatocellular carcinoma	- Quantification of the DNA repair activity in solid tumors is challenging due to technical difficulties. DNA repair capacity can be measured	- This study utilized the DNA repair pathway score as defined by the gene set variation analysis (GSVA) algorithm, with the transcriptomes of multiple	Oshi et al 2021 [3]

		Hallmark gene set collections using the GSEA algorithm in the Bioconductor package	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High DNA repair score human hepatocellular carcinoma was associated with significantly worse survival - High DNA repair score was associated with high microsatellite instability, intratumor, heterogeneity and mutation. - High DNA repair high HCC enriched cell proliferation and cancer aggressiveness related gene sets - DNA repair score reflected multiple gene expressions related to survival. 	by a direct assay or indirectly by cultivation of peripheral blood lymphocytes, but these assays are cost and labor intensive to conduct in large cohorts.	large hepatocellular carcinoma patient cohorts to quantify the enhancement of DNA repair in human hepatocellular carcinoma. It is found that the DNA repair score might be used to predict the outcome of hepatocellular carcinoma.	
-MiR -155 -TLR3	- Human hepatocellular carcinoma tissues - Cell lines (HepG2, SMMC-7721, and HeLa cells, human fetal hepatocytes L02 cell line)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Quantitative real-time PCR analysis (qRT-PCR) - Western blot - Cell proliferation assay: MTT - Luciferase reporter assay - Immunofluorescence staining - siRNA design and synthesis - RNA immunoprecipitation (RIP) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MicroRNA 155 (MiR-155) is highly expressed in human hepatocellular carcinoma tissues and cell lines - Toll-like receptor 3 (TLR3), a putative miR-155 target, is downregulated in human hepatocellular carcinoma - High miR-155 expression was associated with big tumor size, venous invasion, metastasis and stage, while low TLR3 expression showed opposite effect. 	The commercial kits were used for the measurements.	- This study using both human tissue and human cell lines verified that miR-155 and TLR3 might serve as a novel biomarker to predict the progression and prognosis of human hepatocellular carcinoma.	Yin et al 2020 [4]

Reference

1. Chida, K., et al., *E2F target score is associated with cell proliferation and survival of patients with hepatocellular carcinoma*. *Surgery*, 2023. **174**(2): p. 307-314.
2. Gu, Z., et al., *Aberrant LYZ expression in tumor cells serves as the potential biomarker and target for HCC and promotes tumor progression via csGRP78*. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, 2023. **120**(29): p. e2215744120.
3. Oshi, M., et al., *Enhanced DNA Repair Pathway is Associated with Cell Proliferation and Worse Survival in Hepatocellular Carcinoma (HCC)*. *Cancers (Basel)*, 2021. **13**(2).
4. Yin, L., et al., *In situ self-assembly of Au-antimiR-155 nanocomplexes mediates TLR3-dependent apoptosis in hepatocellular carcinoma cells*. *Aging (Albany NY)*, 2020. **13**(1): p. 241-261.

Table 1: Key event (KE) titles and ID numbers of AOP 39 and the number of measurement methods described in AOP 39 and those found so far in other sources (AOP-Wiki and literature search). Number of methods potentially applicable as effect markers are indicated in parentheses.

KE in AOP 39	KE number	Number of measurement methods described in AOP 39; (potentially applicable as effect marker)	Number of measurement methods from other sources (AOP-Wiki, literature search) (potentially applicable as effect marker)
MIE: Covalent binding, protein	396	0 (0)	0 (0)
KE1: Increased, secretion of pro-inflammatory mediators	1496	4 (3)	21 (8)
KE2: Activation, dendritic cells	398	3 (1)	0 (0)
KE3: Activation/proliferation, T cells	272	2 (0)	11 (5)
AO: Increase, allergic respiratory hypersensitivity response	313	8 (8)	50 (19)

Table 2: Potential effect markers identified for respiratory sensitization. Effect markers indicated with asterisc (*) are not described in AOP 39 (Covalent Binding, Protein, leading to Increase, Allergic Respiratory Hypersensitivity Response).

Effect marker	Matrix	Measurement methods	Description of association with key event or adverse outcome in humans or if stated validation of measurement/effect marker.	Developmental status of the effect marker	Comments / Recommended for human epidemiological studies (Why, why not)	Reference
Skin prick test	skin	Allergens are delivered epicutaneously. Positive: appearance of wheal. Left forearm is generally preferred.	Detects immediate (antibody-mediated) and delayed (cell-mediated) sensitivity	Some validation is needed. Antihistamines and several other drugs, skin disorders, time of day, age can affect the result. Lack of standardization.	It is a simple, inexpensive, quick and safe test. Several hundred types of allergens can be tested. It correlates well with serum specific IgE level.	1-3
Patch test	skin	Chemicals are applied to the skin (usually the back) at pre-determined concentrations. Some days later, following removal of the patch, inflammatory reaction is scored.	The cutaneous inflammatory reaction is driven by the local infiltration and activation of allergen-specific memory T-cells. This induces the recruitment of other immune cells, release of cytokines and inflammatory mediators.	Some validation is needed. It is time consuming, has low sensitivity. Interpretation of the response requires expert knowledge, and false positive and negative outcomes can be.	Patch test can be used at any age with negligible risk of anaphylaxis. It has high specificity. The extent of sensitization is indicated by the vigor of the induced skin reaction.	1, 3-4
Bronchial (methacholine) challenge test	breath	Bronchoconstriction provoked by metacholine can be quantified by spirometry.	The non-specific challenge with methacholine provides an assessment of airway hyperreactivity	Some validation is needed. The ability to distinguish allergic responses from irritant effects can be difficult.	It has relatively high sensitivity. A negative test can rule out occupational asthma.	3, 5-7

Specific inhalation challenge test (SIC)	breadth	The subjects receive inhalation challenges with low doses of the suspected substance to simulate workplace exposures. Serial measures of airflow are taken over a period of about 12 hours after exposure to test for immediate or delayed bronchoconstriction.	Alterations in breathing parameters such as respiratory rate, minute volume, tidal volume, peak expiratory flow, inspiratory and expiratory times and a flow-derived estimation of airflow restriction (enhanced pause, Penh) are often used for quantitative assessment of allergen induced airway hyperreactivity	Some validation is needed. Patient cooperation is required: not practical for young children and elderly. Difficult, costly, potentially dangerous for the patient, can be false negative or positive outcomes. Requires a specialized center. Negative test does not exclude OA.	Despite limited availability, lack of standardized protocols, and recognized possibilities of false-positive and false-negative results, SIC has been used as the main reference standard for the diagnosis of OA in research publications.	3, 5-9
Fractional exhaled nitric oxide (FeNO)	breadth	Measurement of NO level in exhaled breath using chemiluminescence reaction.	NO is produced by airway epithelial cells, eosinophils, macrophages by NOS and iNOS enzyme. Airway inflammation drives the expression of iNOS, increasing NO production.	Some validation is needed. It can be affected by smoking, virus infection, dietary nitrate intake. It has low specificity and low sensitivity.	It can be an option for patients who cannot provide sputum samples in appropriate amounts.	5, 10-11
Immunoglobulin E (IgE) level	serum	ELISA measurement	IgE plays a pivotal role in responses to allergens. IgE primes the IgE-mediated allergic response by binding to Fc receptors found on the surface of mast cells and basophils.	Some validation is needed. There is variation by geography due to differences in allergen exposure and individual susceptibility. Genetic factors may also influence. The sensitivity is highest if blood is taken less than 30 days after last exposure. It was not possible to identify specific IgE in all patients with confirmed chemical respiratory	It has relatively high specificity. No effects of anti-histaminis or steroids.	2,3, 9-10, 12

				allergy (particularly for diisocyanates).		
Basophil activation test	whole blood	Flow cytometry. CD63 (it is in the same lysosomal granule as histamine) is translocated to the membrane after degranulation.	Basophils are key effector cells in immediate type allergic reaction	Some variation is needed. Fresh blood is needed. Patient should be tested within a year of last exposure. Steroids and other immunosuppressants should be omitted prior to testing. 10-20% of population does not respond to this test (no or low response to the positive control).	Easy, antihistamines do not affect the results.	12
Absolute eosinophil count *	whole blood, nasal secretion, sputum	cell count	Eosinophils reflect airway inflammation, which might cause obstructive airflow limitation.	Some variation is needed. Nonallergic stimulation (e.g. smoking) can also trigger eosinophil proliferation. Affected by age, stress, menstrual cycle hormones, pollution in residence area, other diseases, infections, parasites. Standardization is needed for appropriate cut-off of clinically relevant eosinophilia.	It is easy, accessible, cost-effective.	2,3,5,10,11
Periostin level *	serum	ELISA measurement	Extracellular matrix protein, whose expression correlates with IL-4 and IL-13 activity in epithelial cells and lung fibroblasts. It stimulates eosinophil degranulation, and the production of TGF- β and cysLTs from eosinophils.	It is not validated. Several periostin splice variants complicate its detection. Baseline periostin level is higher	Stability of serum periostin level over disease progression. No seasonal effect.	10,11

				in children.		
Eosinophil peroxidase (EPO) level *	serum, saliva	ELISA measurement	Eosinophils contain cationic proteins in their granules which have strong cytotoxic potential.	It is not validated.	Serum EPO level positively correlated with the number of blood eosinophils. Saliva EPO level correlated with sputum eosinophils. Positively correlated with total IgE levels.	2,10
Eosinophil cationic protein (ECP) level *	serum, BALF, nasal secretion	ELISA measurement	Marker for eosinophilic disease. Elevated ECP levels were found in allergic asthma.	It is not validated. Affected by age, smoking, circadian rhythm, seasonal variation. Shows time and temperature dependency during serum sampling. There is no internationally established cut-off value for the diagnosis of asthma.	May provide complementary value with lung function test and FeNO.	2, 10
Eosinophil-derived neurotoxin/eosinophil protein X (EDN) level *	serum, sputum, urine, BALF, nasal lavage fluid	ELISA measurement	It is a granular protein, released from activated eosinophils. Positive correlation with eosinophil count, higher serum levels in severe asthma,	It is not validated.	Could be a biomarker for asthma severity in adults and children. May help distinguish between asthma from respiratory infections. Could be measured in several biological fluid: easy to obtain. Less affected by circadian rhythm, smoking or gender than eosinophil count. Easier to work with than with ECP.	2, 10

Lymphocyte transformation test (LTT) *	blood	Allergen-reactive memory T-cells (from blood of a sensitized individual) are re-stimulated with allergens in vitro for 5-7 days in culture. Measurement of proliferation	Related to T-cell activation/proliferation key event.	It is not validated. Timing of drawing blood relative to the time of sensitization could be an important factor. The availability of memory T-cells is reduced if there is an on-going hypersensitivity response: the assay should not be conducted during the 4 weeks following an allergic reaction or positive patch test.	It allows the assessment of the responsiveness a particular cell subset, but it does not provide a holistic reflection of the immun response.	4
Transcriptomics assays *	blood, sputum	real-time PCR, microarray, RNA sequencing	1700 differentially expressed genes in adult asthma patients compared to controls.	It is not validated.	Most omics studies are only from a single time point, do not represent the evolution of gene expression.	11,13
Metabolomics assay *	exhaled air	Mass spectrometry	Several circulating metabolites differ from those of healthy individuals. E.g. alkanes (exhaled air volatile organic compound) is a promising biomarker of asthma	It is not validated.	Non-invasive, repeat testing is accessible	11,13
Proteomics assay *	serum	liquid chromatography coupled online to mass spectrometry with the use of iTRAQ isobaric labels	18 proteins were identified as potential biomarkers of asthma phenotype and disease severity (eg, FCN2 and MASP1 for non-allergic asthma, or HSPG2 and IGFALS for allergic asthma).	It is not validated.		13
IL-5, IL-4, and IL-13 levels *	serum	ELISA measurement	Cytokines produced by Th2 cells and eosinophils and mast cells, stimulating Th2 cell differentiation, B cell proliferation and antibody production.	It is not validated.		13
miRNA expression *	blood, BALF, exhaled breath	real-time PCR, microarray	Some miRNAs, such as miR -21 and miR -223 , have already been implicated in the pathogenesis of asthma or even as biomarker of the disease (miR -21)	It is not validated.	It should be noted that the differences in individual miRNA-ratios were rather small and therefore a combination	14,15

					of five miRNA-ratios was necessary to obtain a reliable biomarker with good sensitivity and specificity.	
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References

1	BERNSTEIN, J. A., GHOSH, D., SUBLETT, W. J., WELLS, H. & LEVIN, L. 2011. Is trimellitic anhydride skin testing a sufficient screening tool for selectively identifying TMA-exposed workers with TMA-specific serum IgE antibodies? <i>J Occup Environ Med</i> , 53, 1122-7.
2	Baldacci, S., Omenaas, E., & Oryszczyn, M. P. (2001). Allergy markers in respiratory epidemiology. <i>European Respiratory Journal</i> , 17(4), 773-790.
3	Gupta, N., Agarwal, P., Sachdev, A., & Gupta, D. (2019). Allergy testing—An overview. <i>Indian pediatrics</i> , 56, 951-957.
4	Popple, A., Williams, J., Maxwell, G., Gellatly, N., Dearman, R. J., & Kimber, I. (2016). The lymphocyte transformation test in allergic contact dermatitis: new opportunities. <i>Journal of immunotoxicology</i> , 13(1), 84-91.
5	Üzmezoğlu, B. A. (2021). Inhalation Challenge Tests in Occupational Asthma: Why Are Multiple Tests Needed?. <i>Turkish Thoracic Journal</i> , 22(2), 154.
6	Boverhof DR, Billington R, Bhaskar Gollapudi B, Hotchkiss JA, Krieger SM, Poole A, Wiescinski CM, and Woolhiser MR. 2008. Respiratory sensitization and allergy: Current research approaches and needs. <i>Tox Appl Pharm</i> 226:1-13.
7	Beach, J., Russell, K., Blitz, S., Hooton, N., Spooner, C., Lemiere, C., ... & Rowe, B. H. (2007). A systematic review of the diagnosis of occupational asthma. <i>Chest</i> , 131(2), 569-578.
8	Beckett, W.S., 2005. Revised protocol: criteria for designating substances as occupational asthmagens on the AOEC List of Exposure Codes.
9	Tee, R. D., Cullinan, P., Welch, J., Burge, P. S., & Newman-Taylor, A. J. (1998). Specific IgE to isocyanates: a useful diagnostic role in occupational asthma. <i>Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology</i> , 101(5), 709-715.
10	Rodriguez del Rio, P., Liu, A. H., Borres, M. P., Södergren, E., Iachetti, F., & Casale, T. B. (2022). Asthma and allergy: unravelling a tangled relationship with a focus on new biomarkers and treatment. <i>International Journal of Molecular Sciences</i> , 23(7), 3881.
11	Kuruville, M. E., Lee, F. E. H., & Lee, G. B. (2019). Understanding asthma phenotypes, endotypes, and mechanisms of disease. <i>Clinical reviews in allergy & immunology</i> , 56, 219-233.
12	Vera-Berrios, R. N., Feary, J., & Cullinan, P. (2019). Basophil activation testing in occupational respiratory allergy to low molecular weight

	compounds. <i>Current Opinion in Allergy and Clinical Immunology</i> , 19(2), 92-97.
13	Ogular, I., Pat, Y., Ardicli, O., Barletta, E., Cevhertas, L., Fernandez-Santamaria, R., ... & Akdis, C. A. (2021). Advances and highlights in biomarkers of allergic diseases. <i>Allergy</i> , 76(12), 3659-3686.
14	Fujita, Y., Yoshioka, Y., Ito, S., Araya, J., Kuwano, K., & Ochiya, T. (2014). Intercellular communication by extracellular vesicles and their microRNAs in asthma. <i>Clinical Therapeutics</i> , 36(6), 873-881.
15	Milger, K., Götschke, J., Krause, L., Nathan, P., Alessandrini, F., Tufman, A., ... & Krauss-Etschmann, S. (2017). Identification of a plasma mi RNA biomarker signature for allergic asthma: A translational approach. <i>Allergy</i> , 72(12), 1962-1971.

Marine toxins and their immunomodulating effects

PARC task 5.3.2a: AOP development Effect Marker Group

Ghent University

Jana Asselman, Eveline Diopere, Friedel Dewulf*

jana.asselmann@ugent.be

eveline.diopere@ugent.be

friedel.dewulf@ugent.be

Azaspiracids (ASP)

Until now, 24 different AZAs have been described, with azaspiracid-1 (AZA1), -2 (AZA2), -3 (AZA3) as the predominant ones (Gerssen et al., 2010)

Regulatory limit: 0.16 µg/g

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Diarrhetic shellfish poisoning (Salas et al., 2011)

Mice:

- Deformation of intestinal epithelial villi
- Damage to T and B lymphocytes
- Accumulation of fatty acid deposits in the liver
- Increased prevalence of lung tumors
- Hyperplasia within the stomach lining

IN VITRO

Cell model	Conc+Incubation time	Major findings	Reference
HEK-293 cells	IC50 value range: 0.64-0.84 µM	Open-State Blocker of hERG Potassium Channels : AZA1, AZA2, and AZA3 each bind to and block the hERG (human ether-a-go-go` related gene) potassium channel heterologously expressed in HEK-293 mammalian cells. Inhibition of K ⁺ current for each AZA analogue was concentration-dependent (IC50 value range: 0.64–0.84 µM).	(Twiner et al., 2012)

Lymphocytes and neuronal cells	10 ⁻⁷ –10 ⁻⁶ M	modulate cytosolic calcium concentrations, cause an increase in cellular cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP), and may change intracellular pH	(Alfonso et al., 2006)
Epithelial cells: MCF-7 cells	10 ⁻¹⁰ – 10 ⁻⁹ M	Nanomolar concentrations of AZA-1 reduced MCF-7 cell proliferation and impaired cell-cell adhesion. AZA-1 altered the cellular pool of the adhesion molecule E-cadherin by inducing a dose- and time-dependent accumulation of an E-cadherin fragment (E-cadherin-related antigen [ECRA100]) , with a concentration inducing the half-maximal effect (EC50) of 0.47nM. The immunological characterization of ECRA100 revealed that it consists of an E-cadherin molecule lacking the intracellular domain, and these data showed that the effect induced by AZA-1 in MCF-7 cells is undistinguishable from that induced by yessotoxin (YTX) in the same experimental system. A comparison of toxin effects in MCF-7 and Caco 2 cells confirmed that the effects induced by AZA-1 and YTX are undistinguishable in these cells.	(Ronzitti, Hess, Rehmann, & Rossini, 2007)

Brevetoxin (NSP)

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Ingestion

NSP (Neurotoxic shellfish poisoning) syndrome includes gastrointestinal symptoms and neurological signs such as abdominal pain, paresthesia, cold allodynia, vertigo, ataxia, muscle pain, weakness, headache, excessive salivation, lacrimation, urination, diarrhea, and temperature reversal characteristic of muscarinic stimulants (Bourdelais et al., 2004) (Pierre et al., 2020). Those symptoms occur within few minutes to several hours after seafood ingestion and last 1 to 3 days. (Pierre et al., 2020)

Studies on marine organisms revealed a link between brevetoxin exposure and oxidative stress. The activity of the oxidative stress marker superoxide dismutase (SOD) was detected and correlated to the plasma brevetoxin levels and reactive oxygen in rescued Florida manatees after exposure to a red tide bloom. When compared to healthy turtles, a two-fold increase in SOD was observed in rescued loggerhead turtles which correlated with plasma brevetoxin levels at 500 ng / ml. Brevetoxin exposure at 5.4-15.0 µg/L increased catalase activity in coral larvae and lipid peroxidation in coral larvae and fish gills (Chen, 2016).

Inhalation

Aerosolized brevetoxins from natural blooms of *K. brevis* cause respiratory distress resulting from airway constriction, an effect observed at pM concentrations (Bourdelais et al., 2004).

Inhalation of PbTx aerosols result in respiratory symptoms especially in persons with underlying airway diseases such as asthma. Upper-airway symptoms include cough, sneezing and rhinorrhea, involving sensory fiber activation. Lower-airway symptoms include chest tightness, wheezing and shortness of breath. Burning sensations in nose and throat, associated with itch on the facial skin, watery eyes and neurological symptoms such as headache, have been reported. These symptoms support the hypothesis that PbTx exert sensory effects through inhalation. Current treatment is only symptomatic due to the lack of a specific antidote for PbTx intoxications (Pierre et al., 2020)

In animal models of allergic inflammation, inhalation of PbTx results in a histamine H1-mediated bronchoconstriction suggestive of mast cell activation (Hilderbrand, Murrell, Gibson, & Brown, 2011). In animal studies with inhaled brevetoxins, suppressed splenic antibody production was observed among Sprague-Dawley rats inhaling aerosols of crude *K. brevis* extract 4 hr/day for 1 and 4 weeks. (Benson et al., 2005)

Report on the effects of airway challenges with lysed cultures of *Karenia brevis* (crude brevetoxin), pure brevetoxin-2, brevetoxin-3, and brevetoxin-tbm (brevetoxin-2 minus the side chain) on pulmonary resistance and tracheal mucus velocity, a marker of mucociliary clearance, in allergic and nonallergic sheep: Picogram concentrations of toxin caused bronchoconstriction in both groups of sheep. Brevetoxin-tbm was the least potent, indicating the importance of the side chain for maximum effect. Both histamine H1- and cholinergic-mediated pathways contributed to the bronchoconstriction. A synthetic antagonist, β -naphthoyl-brevetoxin-3, and brevenal, a natural antagonist, inhibited the bronchoconstriction. Only crude brevetoxin and brevetoxin-3 decreased tracheal mucus velocity; both antagonists prevented this. More importantly, picomolar concentrations of the antagonists alone improved tracheal mucus velocity to the degree seen with mM concentrations of the sodium channel blocker amiloride. Thus, *Karenia brevis*, in addition to producing toxins that adversely affect the airways, may be a source of agents for treating mucociliary dysfunction (Abraham et al., 2005).

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Mechanistically, PbTxs interact with site 5 of the alpha subunit of the voltage-dependent **sodium channels** (Nav) including tetrodotoxin (TTX)-sensitive Nav channels (TTX-s Nav) and the TTX-resistant Nav channels (TTX-r Nav), which are largely expressed in sensory nerves. PbTx binding causes conformational changes of the channel, shift in the activation voltage and impairment of inactivation. This, in turn, increases sodium entrance, leading to membrane cell hyperexcitability and subsequently to sensory disturbances. (Pierre et al., 2020)

Cell model	Concentration	Effect	Reference
		Activates voltage-gated sodium channels . By binding to Site 5 associated with the α -subunit of voltage-gated sodium channels, brevetoxins produce four distinct effects: a shift of the activation potential	(Bourdelaïs et al., 2004)

		<p>to more negative values; a prolongation of mean open time; inhibition of inactivation; and, visualization of multiple subconductance states. By virtue of these actions on normal sodium channel function, the brevetoxins cause massive fish kills, produce marine mammal poisoning and are responsible for human health problems.</p> <p>Brevenal: Brevenal Is a Natural Inhibitor of Brevetoxin Action in Sodium Channel Receptor Binding Assays. Brevenal competes with tritiated brevetoxin for site 5 associated with the voltage-sensitive sodium channel (VSSC). Brevenal displacement of specific brevetoxin binding is purely competitive in nature.</p>	
Jurkat cells	5 – 10 µg/L PbTx-2 or PbTx-6	<p>PbTx-2 was shown to induce apoptosis in human Jurkat cells. When Jurkat cells exposed to 5-10 µg/ml PbTx-2 or PbTx-6, the decrease of cellular metabolic activity was observed. After 24h, the viability of cells that were treated with PbTx-2 decreased. In contrast, apoptosis was increased under PbTx-2 or PbTx-6 exposure.</p>	(Chen, 2016)

<p>A549 and murine macrophages RAW 264.7</p>	<p>Brevenal at nonamolar level and picomolar level</p>	<p>Brevenal is one member of the family of the brevetoxins that have demonstrated low in vitro toxicity against human/murine cell lines and potent anti-inflammatory effects on adenocarcinoma cell line A549 and murine macrophages RAW 264.7. Brevenal reduced the LPS-induced production of the pro-inflammatory chemokine IL-8 (A549) at the nanomolar level and the production of the pro-inflammatory cytokine TNF-alpha (RAW 264.7) at the picomolar level. Such findings suggest the unexploited potential of brevenal for applications on pulmonary diseases.</p>	<p>(Saide, Martínez, Ianora, & Lauritano, 2021)</p>
<p>T cell lines (Jurkat), monocyte cell lines (U-937), alveolar macrophage cell lines (MH-S), and mouse bone marrow derived mast cells, sea turtle and dolphin peripheral blood leukocytes</p>		<p>Immunotoxic effects. Post inhalation and/or ingestion of brevetoxin, interactions with these cells initiate innate and adaptive immune responses. Preliminary studies show the possibility for lasting immune deficiencies in severe cases, but the mechanisms involved in immune activation and dysfunction resulting from brevetoxin exposure remain unclear.</p>	<p>(Brammer-Robbins et al., 2022)</p>
	<p>K_s of 25 μM and 0.6 μM</p>	<p>proteolytic activity of papain and cathepsin L in the presence of brevetoxin b: inhibition of papain and cathepsin L with K_s of 25 μM and 0.6 μM, respectively</p>	<p>(Sudarsanam, Virca, March, & Srinivasan, 1992)</p>

		<p>→ Note: the two classes of intracellular proteases implicated in antigen presentation are cysteine and aspartate proteases</p>	
<p>mouse bone marrow– derived mast cells (BMMCs)</p>	<p>measurements at multiple concentrations and multiple time points! :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 10⁵ through 10¹² M - 1, 4, 8, 24 h <p>observed effects occurred at the two highest concentrations of 10⁵ and 10⁶ M PbTx-2</p>	<p>PbTx can directly activate mouse mast cells leading to degranulation and inflammatory cytokine production and the activation involves Ca²⁺ signaling.</p> <p>Following in vitro exposure to PbTx-2, we examined cellular viability, mast cell degranulation (β-hexosaminidase release), intracellular Ca²⁺ and Na⁺ flux, and the production of inflammatory mediators (IL-6). PbTx-2 induced significant cellular toxicity within 24 h as measured by LDH release and Annexin-V staining. However, within 1 h of exposure, PbTx-2 induced BMMC degranulation and an increase in IL-6 mRNA expression independent of the high-affinity IgE receptor (FcϵRI) stimulation. Activation of BMMCs by PbTx-2 was associated with altered intracellular Ca²⁺ and Na⁺ levels. Brevenal, a naturally produced compound that antagonizes the activity of PbTx, prevented changes in intracellular Na⁺ levels but did not alter activation of BMMCs by PbTx-2.</p>	<p>(Hilderbrand et al., 2011)</p>

		<p>These findings demonstrate that PbTx-2 activates mast cells independent of FcεRI providing insight into critical events in the pathogenesis.</p> <p>Within minutes of PbTx exposure, BMMCs exhibited an increase in cytosolic Ca²⁺ levels consistent with cellular activation and degranulation.</p>	
Alveolar macrophage cell line MH-S	Brevetoxin-2: 0.5 µg/mL	<p>Exposure of an alveolar macrophage cell line (MH-S) to an environmentally and physiologically relevant dose of brevetoxin-2 (0.5 µg/ml) did not significantly alter cellular growth over a 24 h time period. However, exposure of MH-S cells to brevetoxin-2 for 6 h increased phagocytosis of latex beads, increased secretion of interleukin (IL-2, IL-4, and tumor necrosis factor-α), and decreased secretion of IL-5. Very few changes were seen in gene expression following 3 or 6 h exposure to brevetoxin-2. These results show that brevetoxin-2 induced an immune response indicative of inflammation in an alveolar macrophage cell line, indicating that inhalation of brevetoxin-2 may lead to lung inflammation through an</p>	

		alveolar macrophage-initiated pathway	
	<p>PbTx-2 and PbTx-3 at concentrations ranging from 10 to 35 μM were incubated with a mixture of pre-reduced TrxR and Trx for one hour</p> <p>PbTx-2 exhibited a dose dependent inhibition of Trx/TrxR activity with an IC50 of 25 μM, whereas PbTx-3 had no effect</p>	<p>PbTx-2 is inhibitor of Trx/TrxR system (Chen, 2016)</p> <p>Some Trxs can also regulate cell death via denitrosylation and modulate the inflammatory response. In addition, it has been shown that Trx plays an essential role in the life cycle of viruses. Many transcription factors are redox regulated by thioredoxin, with either their activation or inactivation dependent on thioredoxin-catalyzed reduction. Thioredoxin is critical for redox regulation of NFkB, a transcription factor that controls expression of numerous inflammatory genes. (Arnér & Holmgren, 2000)</p>	<p>(Chen, 2016)</p> <p>(Arnér & Holmgren, 2000)</p>
In sensory neurons		<p>PbTx-1-induced sensory disturbances involve the PAR2-TRPV4 pathway. PAR2, Cat-S, PKA, and PKC are involved in TRPV4 sensitization induced by PbTx-1 in sensory neurons.</p> <p>PbTx-1-induced calcium increase and substance P release involved Cat-S, PAR2 and transient receptor potential vanilloid 4 (TRPV4). The PbTx-1-induced signaling pathway included protein kinase A (PKA) and</p>	<p>(Pierre et al., 2020)</p>

		TRPV4, which are compatible with the PAR2 biased signaling induced by Cat-S.	
U-937	50 μ M: 1h, 2h, 3h	After the human U-937 cells were treated with PbTx-2, the amount of glutathione was decreased while oxidative stress occurred (Walsh, Leggett et al. 2009)	(Walsh et al., 2009)

Cyclic imines

This group includes: spiroptides (SPX), gymnodimines (GYM), pinnatoxins (PnTX), and pteriatoxins (PtTX). (Visciano et al., 2016)

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Cell model	Concentration	Effect	Reference
rat pheochromocytoma (PC12) cells	GYM A: 0.5 μ M SPX1: 0.5 μ M	GYM A and SPX 1 activates nicotinic AChRs (nAChRs) while only GYM A activate muscarinic AChRs (mAChRs). The activation of AChRs and the subsequent influx of calcium ions into the cell illustrates the putative capacity of the toxins to mimic acetylcholine.	(Nieva, 2021)
AREc32 (Luciferase reporter gene assay) and NfkB- BLA (Beta-lactamase reporter gene assay) THP-1 cells assays.	GYM A and SPX1 : nanomolar concentration range (non-cytotoxic)	potentially induce adaptive stress response pathways. AREc32 cells administered with either GYM A or SPX 1 provided a	(Nieva, 2021)

		<p>different response on the oxidative stress pathway. No cytotoxicity and no activation of the response pathway was observed in cells treated with GYM A up to the highest tested concentration at 1.85 μM. The lack of cytotoxicity and activation indicates that GYM A (at 1.85 μM) might not have the capacity to induce potential oxidative stress response. In contrast, cells treated with SPX 1 showed cytotoxicity at IC10 = 871.0 \pm 161.6 nM and induction of the oxidative stress response pathway at ECIR1.5 = 393 \pm 36 nM. The difference in activity indicates that SPX 1, as compared to GYM A, is more likely to induce the oxidative stress response by activating the antioxidant response element (ARE) in the cells.</p> <p>Nf-κB-bla THP-1 cells treated with either GYM A or SPX 1 showed a similar response showed on the inflammation pathway. No cytotoxicity could be recorded in cells treated with the toxins due to the large variability of the ToxBLAzer cell viability stain. It was possible to measure the ECIR1.5 where cells were still viable (cell viability > 50%,</p>	
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		<p>Figure S12). Induction of Nf-κB was at ECIR1.5 = 586 ± 68 nM and 795 ± 127 nM for GYM A and SPX 1, respectively. This shows that GYM A and SPX 1 can induce the Nf-κB signalling pathway and might activate the expression of proteins that participates in regulating inflammation.</p> <p>Summarized: SPX1: induction of oxidative stress response pathways GYM A and SPX 1 induces inflammatory response pathway</p>	
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Domoic acid

Regarding the DA group, there are ten identified DA isomers: isodomoic acids A, B, C, D, E, F, G, and H (iso-DA (A–H)), and the isomers DA C50 -diastereomer and epi-DA (Otero & Silva, 2022)

Domoic acid (DA) is chemically tricarboxylic amino acid, an analog of L-glutamate, which is an excitatory neurotransmitter. Previous studies showed that excitotoxic incidence caused by DA can lead to several biochemical responses in the brain region, viz., free radical generation, oxidative stress, neuronal inflammation, etc. DA has been reported to possess excitotoxic effects by activating ionotropic glutamate receptors (iGluRs) at the postsynaptic membrane and co-activation of AMPA/ kainite receptors. These receptors are ligand-gated ion channels, which mediates excitotoxicity through its integrative action on ionotropic GluRs. Activation of GluRs results in cellular depolarization and elevated levels of calcium influx. Thus, activating cascade of enzymes resulted in degradation of proteins, membranes, nucleic acids, and finally leads to neuronal loss (Ramya, Kumar, Chandrasekhar, & Anilakumar, 2022).

Amnesic shellfish poisoning

IN VIVO

Symptoms in ill people comprised three kinds of signs: (1) gastrointestinal (nausea, vomiting, abdominal cramps and diarrhea), (2) cardiovascular (arrhythmias and unstable blood pressure) and (3) neurological signs (disorientation, headache, hallucination, seizures, memory impairment and coma). Impairment of memory was the reason to denominate this condition as amnesic shellfish poisoning (ASP) (Radad, Moldzio, Al-Shraim, Al-Emam, & Rausch, 2018). Studies have implicated that DA-induced toxicity includes gastrointestinal effects at lower doses and neurotoxic effects at higher doses (McCully, 2009).

DA is a kainoid group of neurotoxin, which is affecting neuroexcitotoxicity by binding glutamate receptors at higher affinity (McCully, 2009)

In mice

Domoic acid was injected to the mice to induce excitotoxicity (DA; 3 mg kg⁽⁻¹⁾ bwt.⁽⁻¹⁾)

- DA-induced oxidative stress was measured by estimating antioxidant enzymes such as CAT, SOD, GPx, and GR. DA-treated group showed significantly reduced levels of antioxidant enzymes as compared to control mice (p < .05).
- DA exposure significantly increased lipid peroxidation and protein oxidation in mice brain, which was measured as MDA and protein carbonyl levels, respectively.
- The expression of GABA was significantly declined in DAadministered group.
- An upregulation of MAPK8 by 1.3 ± 0.3 fold was observed in DATreated group (p < .05).
- The expression levels of CREB and BDNF were significantly downregulated in mice administered with DA (p < .05). The levels of inflammatory marker, that is, **NF-kB** was significantly increased by DA administration (p < .05). An upregulation of apoptotic marker levels was observed in DA-induced mice brain when compared with control group (p < .05). The antiapoptotic protein, that is, Bcl2 was downregulated; whereas, Bax and Caspase 3 were found to be upregulated by DA administration.

(Ramya et al., 2022)

Mice were injected intraperitoneally with a single dose of DA (2.5 µg/g b.w.) and sampled after 12, 24, or 48 hr. In vivo exposure resulted in a significant increase in monocyte phagocytosis (12-hr), a significant decrease in neutrophil phagocytosis (24-hr), a significant decrease in monocyte phagocytosis (48-hr), and a significant reduction in T-cell mitogen-induced lymphocyte proliferation (24-hr). (Levin, Leibrecht, Ryan, Van Dolah, & De Guise, 2008)

IN VITRO

Cell model	Concentration	Effects	Reference
primary astrocytes from the hippocampus and the brain stem	10 μ M	RNA was extracted and used for biomarker analysis. The biomarker analysis was done for the early response genes including c-fos, c-jun, c-myc, Hsp-72; specific marker for the astrocytes- GFAP and the glutamate receptors including GluR 2, NMDAR 1, NMDAR 2A and B. Although, the astrocyte-GFAP and c-fos were not affected, c-jun and GluR 2 were down-regulated. The microarray analysis revealed that the chemokines / cytokines , tyrosine kinases (Trk), and apoptotic genes were altered. The chemokines that were up-regulated included - IL1- α , IL-1B, IL-6, the small inducible cytokine, interferon protein IP-10, CXC chemokine LIX, and IGF binding proteins. The Bax, Bcl-2, Trk A and Trk B were all downregulated.	(Gill, Hou, Ghane, & Pulido, 2008)
Leukocytes and splenocytes	Exposures tested at 0, 1, 10, or 100 μ M DA.	In vitro exposure significantly reduced neutrophil and monocyte phagocytosis at 1 μM. B- and T-cell mitogen-induced lymphocyte proliferation were both significantly increased at 1 and 10 μ M, and significantly decreased at 100 μ M.	(Levin et al., 2008)

		Modulation of cytosolic calcium suggests that DA exerts its effects through ionotropic glutamate subtype surface receptors at least on monocytes.	
primary mesencephalic cell cultures	10 – 100 μ M	treatment of cultures with DA on the 8th DIV for 4 days resulted in significant loss of dopaminergic neurons and decreasing their neurites at the concentrations 10 and 100 μ M compared to untreated control cultures. Also, it slightly decreased the expression of NeuN and GFAP proteins at the concentration 100 μ M compared to untreated control cultures. Similar neurotoxic effect of DomA was reported in some cellular and animal models. DomA was shown to have no effect on LDH release into culture media indicating selective damage to dopaminergic neurons and absence of overall neurotoxicity in DomA-treated primary mesencephalic cell culture.	(Radad et al., 2018)

Okadaic acid

IN VIVO

The ingestion of OA contaminated shellfish results in diarrhetic shellfish poisoning (DSP) syndrome characterized by severe gastrointestinal symptoms, including diarrhea (92%), nausea (80%), vomiting (79%), abdominal pain (53%), and chills (10%). The intensity of these symptoms in humans depends upon the amount of toxin ingested. An intake of 40 µg of OA equivalents is the minimum dose required to produce DSP symptoms in human adults. They appear within 30 min to 4 h after intake and continue for about three days, but they are not considered lethal and hospitalization is usually not required (Valdiglesias, Prego-Faraldo, Pásaro, Méndez, & Laffon, 2013).

A median lethal dose (LD50) of 192 µg/kg level was established after intraperitoneal injection in mice, whereas the lowest observed adverse effect level (LOAEL) in mice, by acute oral administration, was deduced to be 75 µg/kg body weight. Human data from Japan (eight people, age 10–68) indicate a LOAEL of 1.2 to 1.6 µg/kg body weight. In a second study from Norway, 38 of 70 adults were affected with DSP at levels ranging from 1.0 to 1.5 µg/kg body weight. Recently, based on the information of different studies, the Scientific Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain concluded that the LOAEL for human illness is in the region of 50 µg OA equivalents/person. At the tissue level, OA was early reported to induce long-lasting contraction of smooth muscle from human arteries and rabbit aorta. As smooth muscle contraction is triggered by the phosphorylation of one of the small subunits of myosin, it was suggested that OA might activate myosin P-light chain kinase or inhibit a myosin P-light chain phosphatase, leading to the diarrhetic effect. Other later authors proposed the OA-induced stimulation of the phosphorylation of proteins that control sodium secretion by intestinal cells as the cause of diarrhea. After evaluating OA-fed mice at different times, Wang et al. recently confirmed that OA remarkably inhibited the intestinal PP activity, recovering the normal levels within 6 to 24 h. However, they compared several protein profiles and concluded that OA toxicity in mouse intestines was complex and diverse, and that multiple proteins, other than PP, were involved in the diarrhetic process. In addition to DSP symptoms, severe morphological alterations were observed in different rodent organs, especially intestine and liver, after OA administration. These alterations include formation of blebs on the cell surface, pronounced changes of the cell appearance, desquamation of the degenerated epithelium from the lamina propria, and degeneration of absorptive epithelium and of endothelial lining cells. (Valdiglesias et al., 2013)

Model	Dose	Effect	Reference
Mice	Orally fed 17.8 µg/kg	In a study employing mice orally fed 17.8 µg/kg OA, different immunotoxic effects were observed including thymus morpho-functional modifications and atrophy, depletion in the lymphoid compartment, and angiogenesis.	(Visciano et al., 2016)

		Results of this study suggested that low oral doses of OA are able to induce immunostimulation and systemic immunotoxicity. Furthermore, an inflammatory cell response was activated in these animals by the recruitment of granulocytes, a higher number of active macrophages and increased immunoreactivity to cytokines.	
Rats	OKA (200 ng) intracerebroventricular (ICV) was administered in rats.	OA, after intracerebroventricular administration, caused memory impairment in rats and neuroinflammatory changes, including increased expression of proinflammatory cytokine tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α) and interleukin 1 beta (IL-1 β) in the hippocampus and cortex brain regions of these animals.	(Kamat et al., 2012)

IN VITRO

At the molecular level, OA is a specific inhibitor of several types of serine/threonine protein phosphatases and a tumor promoter in animal carcinogenesis experiments (Valdiglesias et al., 2013).

Inhibition of phosphatases 1 and 2A (Seumen, Grimm, & Hauck, 2021)

These toxic effects have been classically related to the inhibition of protein phosphatases; however, the cellular and molecular effects of this toxin are not always clearly explained by this inhibition, and the existence of other targets, different from phosphatases, cannot be excluded. In fact, the existence of OA binding proteins other than phosphatases was already demonstrated in several marine organisms. This potential existence of OA non-phosphatase targets would explain the conflicting reports in the literature on OA cytotoxic effects, mainly, both, apoptosis and cell proliferation, in many cell types. In brief, little

is known about the molecular mechanisms and the components involved in the cellular responses induced by OA beyond its role as phosphatase inhibitor and a re-evaluation of the mechanism of toxicity of this compound was already suggested (Valdiglesias et al., 2013).

Cell model	Concentration	Effect	Reference
many, but not all, cell types including intestinal cells, neuronal cells, hepatic cells, lung cells, blood cells, etc.		The most extensively reported cytotoxic effect of OA is apoptosis induction. OA is known to cause growth inhibition or apoptosis in many, but not all, cell types including intestinal cells, neuronal cells, hepatic cells, lung cells, blood cells, etc. The mechanisms involved in this process include alterations in the expression of specific genes, decrease in the mitochondria membrane potential, activation of multiple caspase isoforms, cytochrome c release from the mitochondrial intermembrane space to the cytosol, inhibition of protein synthesis, and cytoskeletal disruption. It seems that all these events are directly related to OA ability of inhibiting the phosphatase activity. I	(Valdiglesias et al., 2013)
		One of the OA main cellular targets is the cytoskeleton .	(Valdiglesias et al., 2013)
different cell types, including leukemia cells, intestinal colon cells, lymphocytes, fibroblasts, and neuronal cells		A number of studies reported OA-induced cell cycle alterations, mainly mitotic arrest and premature chromosome condensation , in	(Valdiglesias et al., 2013)

		different cell types, including leukemia cells, intestinal colon cells, lymphocytes, fibroblasts, and neuronal cells. These effects on cell cycle can be due to the absence of dephosphorylation control of some kinases, as a consequence of protein phosphatases inhibition caused by OA. This imbalance would lead to an increase in proliferation, aberrant mitosis, or growth arrest, depending on the cell type. In addition, PP2A activity appears to be required for the metaphase–anaphase transition, which would explain the mitotic arrest found in OA-treated cells	
		OA was also shown to induce oxidative stress in a number of in vitro and in vivo studies, and to affect different catabolic and anabolic pathways—including glycolysis, lipolysis, and gluconeogenesis—in several cell types. Besides, the expression of different metabolism-related genes was found to be altered after OA exposure	(Valdiglesias et al., 2013)
		The exposure dose can also account for the divergent results concerning the OA cytotoxic effects. OA was demonstrated to have a concentration dependent effect on	(Valdiglesias et al., 2013)

		<p>cell cycle and apoptosis induction. Thus, Ishida et al. found different cell cycle arrest in myeloid leukemic cells, either at G1/S phase or at G2/M phase, depending on the OA dose. Recently, Fieber et al. also observed that OA stimulates genes involved in the cell cycle progress at low concentrations whereas it promotes apoptosis at high concentrations. These results support the previous ones in which OA was found to induce mitotic arrest, followed by apoptosis in a synchronized manner [67].</p>	
Human peripheral monocytes	<p>0.05 µg/L: stimulation 0.1-1.0 µg/L: depression</p>	<p>In vitro, OA was early reported to produce important alterations on interleukin-1 (IL-1) production by human peripheral monocytes with stimulation at low concentration (0.05 µg/mL), a marked depression at medium concentrations (0.1–1.0 µg/mL) and cell death at higher levels</p>	(Valdiglesias et al., 2013)
HL-60 cells	maximal activation at 100 nM	<p>Interleukin 8 (IL-8) production was dramatically increased (up to 200-fold) in HL-60 cells treated with OA. In this study, OA induced an important stimulation of IL-8 production at both transcriptional and post-transcriptional levels.</p>	(Sonoda et al., 1997)

		<p>OA stimulation was accompanied by a marked increase in IL-8 mRNA expression and also by activation of a transcription factor, NF-kB. In addition, an essential role of the NF-kB site in the IL-8 gene activation was confirmed by the chloramphenicol acetyltransferase assay. IL-8 production by OA was inhibited by protein kinase inhibitors, including staurosporine, H-7, K252a, herbimycin A, and genistein. OA induced significant tyrosine phosphorylation of p44, which was presumed to be Erk1, a member of the mitogen-activated protein kinase family, with concomitant activation of the mitogen-activated protein kinase activity. In parallel, rapid degradation of IκB-α, an inhibitory component of NF-kB, was observed. Since OA-activated Erk1 phosphorylated recombinant IκB-α in vitro, we assumed that Erk1 is involved in the phosphorylation and subsequent degradation of IκB-α, thus leading to the activation of IL-8 gene transcription.</p>	
<p>Mouse T lymphocytes:T lymphocyte EL-4 cells</p>	<p>5 nM</p>	<p>A recent in vitro study employing mouse T lymphocytes also reported that low concentrations of OA (5 nM), within the range previously</p>	<p>(López, Rodríguez, Mirón, Camacho, & Grima, 2011)</p>

		<p>detected in mice bloodstream after oral administration, induced down-regulation of T cell receptor (TCR) expression levels in these cells, compromising the T cell activation and, consequently, the immune response.</p> <p>OA induce a specific, not very rapid, and reversible TCR down-regulation in T lymphocyte EL-4 cells that was time and concentration dependent. These data suggested that OA mediated TCR down-regulation without affecting kin but by a reduction of kout probably following OA-induced inhibition of PP2A</p>	
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Pectenotoxin

Approximately 15 different PTXs have been described to date. Pectenotoxin-2 (PTX2), pectenotoxin-2 seco acid (PTX2sa) and 7-epi pectenotoxin-2 seco acid (7-epi PTX2sa) are the predominant analogues in European shellfish (Gerssen et al., 2010)

IN VIVO

IN VITRO

Cell model	Concentration	Effects	Reference
human monocytic leukemia (U937 and THP-1), human acute myeloblastic leukemia (HL-60) and human erythroid chronic myeloid leukemia (K562)	<p>Treatment for 48 h.</p> <p>The tested concentrations: 0, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10 ng/mL</p>	Artikel 'Pectenotoxin-2 abolishes constitutively activated NF-kB, leading to suppression of NF-kB related gene products and potentiation of apoptosis'	(Kim et al., 2008)

	<p>PTX-2 inhibited constitutive NF-kB binding activity in a dose-dependent manner</p>	<p>Treatment for 48 h with more than 4 ng/ml PTX-2 resulted in significant inhibition in cell viability in all tested leukemia cells.</p> <p>PTX-2 inhibits constitutively expressed NF-kB activation, and the expression of anti-apoptotic and proliferative genes known to be regulated by NF-kB activity. PTX-2 treatment suppressed TNF-a-induced phosphorylation of Akt. PTX-2 suppresses nuclear translocation and activity of NF-kB through blocking of Ikbα degradation.</p> <p>The effect of PTX-2 on NF-kB activity appears to be mediated through its phosphorylation of Ikb and NF-kB proteins.</p>	
<p>Caco-2/HT29-MTX co-cultures</p>	<p>200 nM = 171 ng/mL → This is much higher than the concentrations in the previous observations!! Thus this could maybe explain the difference in observation??</p>	<p>IL-8 gene was up-regulated in a concentration-dependent manner reaching 4.4-fold with 200 nM PTX2.</p>	<p>(Reale, Bodi, Huguet, & Fessard, 2021)</p>

Saxitoxin

IN VIVO

At the molecular level, saxitoxin can induce cytotoxicity and disrupt homeostasis in fish by triggering excessive production of reactive oxygen species (ROS).

In zebrafish: immunosuppression! Oxidative stress. Transcriptional responses showed similar trends to those of the biochemical parameters, as genes involved in the antioxidant defense system and immunity were downregulated. In male zebrafish: the expression of IL1beta and IFNgamma was downregulated in response to saxitoxin. In females, the expression of IL1beta, IFNgamma and TNFalpha was downregulated (Haque, Nam, Han, Park, & Rhee, 2022).

IN VITRO

Yessotoxin

The group of YTXs is composed of close to 90 known analogs (YTX, homoYTX, hydroxyYTX, carboxyYTX and desulfoYTX among others) [4], however, the chemical structures for most of these compounds remain unclear (Tobío, Alfonso, Madera-Salcedo, Botana, & Blank, 2016).

IN VIVO

No records about human intoxications induced by this compound have been published. YTX is poorly absorbed after oral administration and most of the toxin is recovered from the lower intestine and feces. Besides, only ultrastructural cardiac damages without other alterations were reported after oral, intraperitoneal or intravenous administrations to rats and mice. Controversial data were published after intraperitoneal administration. In these senses, a wide range of lethal doses (LD50) have been reported, from 80 to 750 µg/kg, with erratic and no well-defined tissue alterations (Alfonso, Vieytes, & Botana, 2016)

Although no lethality was observed after oral administration in mice (doses up to 54 mg/Kg), YTXs were reported to be lethal after intraperitoneal injection causing restlessness, dyspnoea, shivering, jumping and cramps albeit at relatively high levels of median lethal dose (LD50) values ranging from 80 to 750µg/Kg depending on the mouse strain used. (Tobío et al., 2016)

To analyse the potential role of YTX as an anti-cancer drug *in vivo* we used the well-established **B16F10 melanoma preclinical mouse model**. Our results demonstrate that a few local application of YTX around established tumours dramatically **diminished tumour growth in the absence of any significant toxicity** as determined by the absence of weight loss and haematological alterations. This reveals an important potential for its use as an anti-cancer drug. (Tobío et al., 2016)

IN VITRO

YTXs bind to PDE1, PDE3 and PDE4 and to exonuclease PDE1. (Alfonso et al., 2016)

Modifications in second messenger levels, protein levels, immune cells, cytoskeleton or activation of different cellular death types have been published as consequence of YTX exposure. In summary, **cAMP, calcium, PDEs (phosphodiesterases), PKC and AKAP-149 as well as mitochondria**, are involved in the mechanism of action of YTX (Figure 2). The role of each and the final effect depend on the cellular model studied.

Figure 2. Cross-talks between second messengers and main intracellular organelles involved in the mechanism of action of YTX. Straight lines: pathway directly modulated by YTX. Dotted lines: Calcium levels affect YTX modulation on cGMP, cAMP, AKAP149-PKA-PDEs complex and mitochondria activity. Dashed lines: the effect of YTX is possibly mediated by the modulation of AKAP149-PKA-PDEs complex.

Cellular model	Concentration	Effects	References
Fresh human lymphocytes	1 μ M (they show effects after 50 to 250 seconds)	YTX produced a calcium influx through nifedipine and SKF 96365 (1-[b-[3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-]propoxyl]-4-methoxyphenyl]-1H-imidazole hydrochloride)-sensitive channels . In addition, YTX also produced an inhibition of capacitative calcium entry activated by thapsigargin or by preincubation in a Ca ²⁺ -free medium.	(de la Rosa, Alfonso, Vilariño, Vieytes, & Botana, 2001)
human hepatocellular carcinoma cells: Bel7402 cells	100 ng YTX per well in a 24-well plate (concentration was not clearly indicated!)	YTX caused cytosolic Ca ²⁺ level increase in Bel7402 cells and the YTX-evoked Ca ²⁺ increase was successfully blocked by EGTA and nifedipine. Therefore, our results indicated that YTX may cause apoptosis via inducing Ca ²⁺ entry in Bel7402 cells.	(Pang, Qu, Gao, Tang, & Wang, 2014)
HL7702 human liver cells		YTX induced the usual hallmarks of apoptosis, including chromatin condensation, DNA laddering, activity of caspase-3 deregulation and loss of mitochondrial membrane potential. Furthermore, YTX caused cytosolic calcium levels to increase	(Pang, Qu, Gao, & Wang, 2012)

primary cultures of rat cerebellar neurons	25 nM, 1 h	YTX induced a two-fold increase in cytosolic calcium that was prevented by the voltage-sensitive calcium channel antagonists	(Pérez-Gómez et al., 2006)
A primary culture of rat cardiomyocytes	0.01 – 1 μ M; 24, 48 and 72 h	<p>In this article: no effect on Ca²⁺ and cAMP!</p> <p>a time- and concentration-dependent reduction in the beating frequency after 1, 5, and 24 h incubation with YTX (0.1 – 1μM). This effect was neither associated to the uncoupling between the membrane electrical activity and Ca²⁺ release from intracellular stores nor to the impairment of the mechanisms controlling the Ca²⁺ homeostasis. In addition, 1 μM YTX did not modify basal cAMP levels in cardiomyocytes. MTT and SRB assays revealed that incubation of cardiomyocytes with YTX (0.01 – 1 μM; 24, 48, and 72 h) caused a decrease in cell viability in a concentration- and time-dependent way. This effect was still evident in cardiomyocytes exposed to YTX for 1, 5, and 24 h and cultured up to 72 h in YTX-free medium. Our results demonstrate that, at nanomolar concentrations, a short incubation with YTX causes an inhibition of the beating activity and an irreversible</p>	(Dell'Ovo et al., 2008)

		reduction of viability of cardiac cells in vitro.	
Rat liver mitochondria: Morris Hepatoma 1C1 cells	Nanomolar concentrations Effect within minutes of the addition of submicromolar concentrations	This paper demonstrates that YTX is a very powerful compound that opens the permeability transition pore (PTP) of the inner mitochondrial membrane of rat liver mitochondria at nanomolar concentrations. The effect requires the presence of a permissive level of calcium, by itself incapable of opening the pore. Moreover, YTX induces membrane depolarization. YTX caused PTP opening in Morris Hepatoma 1C1 cells within minutes of the addition of submicromolar concentrations of the toxin.	(Bianchi et al., 2004)
Human lymphocytes	1 μ M	Cells regulate cAMP levels by a balance between adenylyl cyclases (Acs, synthesis) and PDEs (hydrolysis), both enzymatic groups including several isozyme families. cAMP is a signal often modulated by lipophilic marine toxins and, therefore, it is a good candidate to study YTX mechanism of action At 1 μ M YTX: after 10 min incubation YTX decreases cAMP levels. Nevertheless, within the first 90 s after addition of YTX, there is a transient, though very repetitive, increase in cAMP levels before the	(Alfonso, de la Rosa, Vieytes, Yasumoto, & Botana, 2003)

		<p>sustained decrease. The decrease is completely dependent on the presence of extracellular calcium, since by replacing the external medium with a calcium-free one, the effect of YTX is completely opposite, showing a sustained increase, which is triggered in few seconds.</p> <p>In order to understand the mechanisms of action of YTX in cAMP pathway, we used different cAMP modulators and we checked YTX effect. Cells regulate cAMP levels by a balance between Acs (synthesis) and PDEs (hydrolysis), both enzymatic groups including several isozyme families. The target of YTX seems to be the PDE system.</p> <p>20 h of incubation with 1 μM YTX, which is associated with a decrease in cAMP levels: increases IL-2 production, which indirectly confirms a decrease in cAMP.</p>	
K-562 lymphocytes and fresh human lymphocytes	Different concentrations depending on the aim	One to 10 μ M of YTX for 10 min: YTX induces a decreases on cAMP levels in fresh human lymphocytes in a medium with Ca ²⁺ , whereas in a Ca ²⁺ free medium the toxin effect is opposite and thus, cAMP levels have been increased. In K-562 cell line, YTX increases cAMP levels in a	(Tobío, Fernández-Araujo, Alfonso, & Botana, 2012)

		<p>medium with Ca²⁺. Surprisingly, in a Ca²⁺-free medium, both YTX concentrations have an opposite effect in cAMP levels. → YTX effect on cAMP levels and thus in PDEs activity is different in primary and tumoural lymphocytes</p> <p>30 nM YTX incubated during 24 and 48 h: YTX treatment did not affect fresh human lymphocytes viability after 24 and 48 h treatment. However, in K-562 cell line, cell viability decreases around 20% when the toxin is incubated during 24 h and 80% at 48 h.</p> <p>In K-562 cells: 0.2, 0.5 and 1 μM were used to analyse a dose-response effect in the cytosolic Ca²⁺ levels: in a medium with Ca²⁺, no effects were observed when YTX was added to the cells. In a Ca²⁺-free medium YTX induces a significant increase on Ca²⁺ pools depletion. This Ca²⁺ pools depletion induces an increase on cytosolic Ca²⁺ levels (from 70 nM on untreated cells to 100 nM with YTX 0.2 mM, 120 nM with YTX 0.5mM and 150 nM with YTX 1 mM).</p>	
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		<p>The effect of YTX on Ca²⁺ pools depletion, the cAMP pathway and mitochondrial reservoirs are functionally related. Anchor kinase A proteins (AKAPs) are the proteins that integrate cAMP and mitochondria. PKA and PDE4 are anchored by AKAP149 to the mitochondria. Moreover, AKAP149 and PKA junction is crucial for cell survival. Cytosolic expression of AKAP149 protein was studied in presence of YTX. K-562 cells and fresh human lymphocytes were incubated during 10 min in presence of 5 μM YTX. In tumoural lymphocytes YTX induces a statistical decrease on AKAP149 expression from 1.15 to 0.4 fmol. In fresh human lymphocytes YTX has a striking opposite effect, since toxin induces a significant increase on cytosolic AKAP149 levels from 1.1 to 2.4 fmol.</p>	
J774 cell line	1 or 10 nM; 12 hours	<p>Impairs immune function by reducing phagocytic activity in the J774 cell line and increasing cytokine expression in J774 phagocyte mammalian cells. We found that macrophages exposed to 10 or 1 nM YTX display a</p>	(Orsi et al., 2010)

		<p>reduced phagocytic activity against <i>Candida albicans</i>; moreover, phagosome maturation is also inhibited in these cells. The inhibition of both phagocytosis and phagosome maturation likely involves cytoskeletal alterations, since a striking rearrangement of the F-actin organization occurs in YTX-treated J774 macrophages. Surprisingly, YTX also enhances cytokine production (TNF-α, MIP-1a and MIP-2) by J774 macrophages</p>	
EL-4 cells		<p>Controls immunological impact on T-lymphocyte EL-4 cells via reversible T-cell receptor complex downregulation. induce a specific, not very rapid, and reversible TCR down-regulation in T lymphocyte EL-4 cells that was time and concentration dependent. YTX-induced TCR down-regulation was partially mediated by PKC activation</p>	(López et al., 2011)
fresh rat mast cells and in the Human Mast Cell lines HMC-1 ⁵⁶⁰ and HMC-1 ^{560,816}	1 – 10 M; 48 h	<p>The activation of mast cells induced after immunological stimulation was highly inhibited in the presence of YTX. Besides in HMC-1 cell lines, inhibition of cellular stimulation and no modifications in cellular viability after 48 h incubation in the presence of YTX (1–100 nM) were observed (unpublished results).</p>	(Alfonso et al., 2016)

<p>Bone marrow-derived mast cells (BMMCs) from the bone marrow of C57BL/6</p> <p>RBL-2H3</p>	<p>RBL-2H3 cells and BMMCs were treated with 10 or 30 nM YTX for 30 or 60min before stimulating them with specific antigen (DNP-HSA) for 45min in the presence or absence (removal) of YTX</p>	<p>In RBL-2H3 cells no significant effect was observed at low and high antigen doses (10ng/mL and 1000ng/mL) while at more optimal stimulatory doses (100ng/mL), a slight decrease in the degranulation response was observed at 30nM of YTX, particularly when the toxin remained present during the stimulation period. A decrease of the degranulation response was also observed in BMMCs after 1h incubation of YTX, independently of whether it had been removed before stimulation or not. The inhibitory effect required prolonged preincubation with YTX as it was only observed after pretreatment for 1h, while no effect was observed after 30 min. Although these results demonstrate that YTX decreases β-hexosaminidase release, its effect was not very potent reaching with a maximum inhibition of 25% in both BMMCs and RBL cells.</p> <p>As YTX was shown previously to be toxic to tumour cells at relatively low concentrations, we performed control experiments to evaluate whether the toxin had any effect on MC viability. Fig 2 shows that using the MTT assay YTX did not induce</p>	<p>(Tobío et al., 2016)</p>
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		<p>any cytotoxic effect neither in BMMCs nor in RBL-2H3 after short (30min) incubation times. However, after 1h of incubation time a slight but significant decrease or tendency to decrease in cell viability was observed in RBL-2H3 cells at the high YTX concentrations (30, 50 and 100nM). This effect became highly prominent after 24, 48 and 72h suggesting that the toxin exhibited significant toxicity towards the RBL-2H3 MC cells line. Surprisingly, the effect was different when BMMCs were examined as no significant toxicity of YTX could be observed. Only with the highest concentration of YTX (100nM) a tendency for some toxicity was observed at 48h and 72h of treatment. Taken together, these results indicate that YTX has a clear cytotoxic effect for the MC tumour line, while primary MCs were highly resistant to YTX induced toxicity</p>	
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- Abraham, W. M., Bourdelais, A. J., Sabater, J. R., Ahmed, A., Lee, T. A., Serebriakov, I., & Baden, D. G. (2005). Airway responses to aerosolized brevetoxins in an animal model of asthma. *American journal of respiratory and critical care medicine*, *171*(1), 26-34.
- Alfonso, A., de la Rosa, L., Vieytes, M. R., Yasumoto, T., & Botana, L. M. (2003). Yessotoxin, a novel phycotoxin, activates phosphodiesterase activity: effect of yessotoxin on cAMP levels in human lymphocytes. *Biochemical pharmacology*, *65*(2), 193-208.
- Alfonso, A., Vieytes, M. R., & Botana, L. M. (2016). Yessotoxin, a promising therapeutic tool. *Marine drugs*, *14*(2), 30.
- Alfonso, A., Vieytes, M. R., Ofuji, K., Satake, M., Nicolaou, K., Frederick, M. O., & Botana, L. (2006). Azaspiracids modulate intracellular pH levels in human lymphocytes. *Biochemical and biophysical research communications*, *346*(3), 1091-1099.
- Arnér, E. S., & Holmgren, A. (2000). Physiological functions of thioredoxin and thioredoxin reductase. *European journal of biochemistry*, *267*(20), 6102-6109.
- Benson, J. M., Hahn, F. F., March, T. H., McDonald, J. D., Gomez, A. P., Sopori, M. J., . . . Bossart, G. D. (2005). Inhalation toxicity of brevetoxin 3 in rats exposed for twenty-two days. *Environmental Health Perspectives*, *113*(5), 626-631.
- Bianchi, C., Fato, R., Angelin, A., Trombetti, F., Ventrella, V., Borgatti, A. R., . . . Lenaz, G. (2004). Yessotoxin, a shellfish biotoxin, is a potent inducer of the permeability transition in isolated mitochondria and intact cells. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA)-Bioenergetics*, *1656*(2-3), 139-147.
- Bourdelais, A. J., Campbell, S., Jacocks, H., Naar, J., Wright, J. L., Carsi, J., & Baden, D. G. (2004). Brevenal is a natural inhibitor of brevetoxin action in sodium channel receptor binding assays. *Cellular and molecular neurobiology*, *24*, 553-563.
- Brammer-Robbins, E., Costa, K. A., Bowden, J. A., Martyniuk, C. J., Larkin, I., & Denslow, N. (2022). Putative high-level toxicity pathways based on evidence of brevetoxin immunotoxicity in marine fauna. *Aquatic Toxicology*, 106298.
- Chen, W. (2016). Characterization of Interaction Between Brevetoxin and Its Native Receptor and Identification of the Role of Brevetoxin in *Karenia brevis*.
- de la Rosa, L. A., Alfonso, A., Vilariño, N., Vieytes, M. R., & Botana, L. M. (2001). Modulation of cytosolic calcium levels of human lymphocytes by yessotoxin, a novel marine phycotoxin☆. *Biochemical pharmacology*, *61*(7), 827-833.
- Dell'Ovo, V., Bandi, E., Coslovich, T., Florio, C., Sciancalepore, M., Decorti, G., . . . Tubaro, A. (2008). In vitro effects of yessotoxin on a primary culture of rat cardiomyocytes. *Toxicological sciences*, *106*(2), 392-399.
- Gerssen, A., Pol-Hofstad, I. E., Poelman, M., Mulder, P. P., Van den Top, H. J., & De Boer, J. (2010). Marine toxins: Chemistry, toxicity, occurrence and detection, with special reference to the Dutch situation. *Toxins*, *2*(4), 878-904.
- Gill, S. S., Hou, Y., Ghane, T., & Pulido, O. M. (2008). Regional susceptibility to domoic acid in primary astrocyte cells cultured from the brain stem and hippocampus. *Marine drugs*, *6*(1), 25-38.
- Haque, M. N., Nam, S.-E., Han, Y.-S., Park, H. S., & Rhee, J.-S. (2022). Chronic exposure to sublethal concentrations of saxitoxin reduces antioxidant activity and immunity in zebrafish but does not affect reproductive parameters. *Aquatic Toxicology*, *243*, 106070.
- Hilderbrand, S. C., Murrell, R. N., Gibson, J. E., & Brown, J. M. (2011). Marine brevetoxin induces IgE-independent mast cell activation. *Archives of toxicology*, *85*(2), 135-141.
- Kamat, P. K., Tota, S., Rai, S., Swarnkar, S., Shukla, R., & Nath, C. (2012). A study on neuroinflammatory marker in brain areas of okadaic acid (ICV) induced memory impaired rats. *Life sciences*, *90*(19-20), 713-720.
- Kim, M.-O., Moon, D.-O., Heo, M.-S., Lee, J.-D., Jung, J. H., Kim, S.-K., . . . Kim, G.-Y. (2008). Pectenotoxin-2 abolishes constitutively activated NF-κB, leading to suppression of NF-κB related gene products and potentiation of apoptosis. *Cancer letters*, *271*(1), 25-33.

- Levin, M., Leibrecht, H., Ryan, J., Van Dolah, F., & De Guise, S. (2008). Immunomodulatory effects of domoic acid differ between in vivo and in vitro exposure in mice. *Marine drugs*, 6(4), 636-659.
- López, A. M., Rodríguez, J. J. G., Mirón, A. S., Camacho, F. G., & Grima, E. M. (2011). Immunoregulatory potential of marine algal toxins yessotoxin and okadaic acid in mouse T lymphocyte cell line EL-4. *Toxicology letters*, 207(2), 167-172.
- McCully, K. S. (2009). Chemical pathology of homocysteine. IV. Excitotoxicity, oxidative stress, endothelial dysfunction, and inflammation. *Annals of Clinical & Laboratory Science*, 39(3), 219-232.
- Nieva, J. A. (2021). *Isolation, Characterization and Bioactivity Screening of Cyclic Imines*. Universität Kiel,
- Orsi, C. F., Colombari, B., Callegari, F., Todaro, A. M., Ardizzoni, A., Rossini, G. P., . . . Peppoloni, S. (2010). Yessotoxin inhibits phagocytic activity of macrophages. *Toxicon*, 55(2-3), 265-273.
- Otero, P., & Silva, M. (2022). Emerging Marine Biotoxins in European Waters: Potential Risks and Analytical Challenges. *Marine drugs*, 20(3), 199.
- Pang, M., Qu, P., Gao, C.-L., Tang, X., & Wang, Z.-L. (2014). Effect of yessotoxin on cytosolic calcium levels in human hepatocellular carcinoma cells in vitro. *Biomedical Reports*, 2(1), 93-96.
- Pang, M., Qu, P., Gao, C.-L., & Wang, Z.-L. (2012). Yessotoxin induces apoptosis in HL7702 human liver cells. *Molecular Medicine Reports*, 5(1), 211-216.
- Pérez-Gómez, A., Ferrero-Gutierrez, A., Novelli, A., Franco, J. M., Paz, B., & Fernández-Sánchez, M. T. (2006). Potent neurotoxic action of the shellfish biotoxin yessotoxin on cultured cerebellar neurons. *Toxicological sciences*, 90(1), 168-177.
- Pierre, O., Fouchard, M., Buscaglia, P., Le Goux, N., Leschiera, R., Mignen, O., . . . Le Garrec, R. (2020). Calcium Increase and Substance P Release Induced by the Neurotoxin Brevetoxin-1 in Sensory Neurons: Involvement of PAR2 Activation through Both Cathepsin S and Canonical Signaling. *Cells*, 9(12), 2704.
- Radad, K., Moldzio, R., Al-Shraim, M., Al-Emam, A., & Rausch, W.-D. (2018). Long-term neurotoxic effects of domoic acid on primary dopaminergic neurons. *Toxicology in Vitro*, 52, 279-285.
- Ramya, E. M., Kumar, G. P., Chandrasekhar, Y., & Anilakumar, K. R. (2022). Adaptogenic potential of ginsenosides against domoic acid-induced toxicity by regulating neuronal stress and kinate receptors: Ex vivo and in silico studies. *Journal of Food Biochemistry*, e14089.
- Reale, O., Bodi, D., Huguet, A., & Fessard, V. (2021). Role of enteric glial cells in the toxicity of phycotoxins: Investigation with a tri-culture intestinal cell model. *Toxicology letters*, 351, 89-98.
- Ronzitti, G., Hess, P., Rehmann, N., & Rossini, G. P. (2007). Azaspiracid-1 alters the E-cadherin pool in epithelial cells. *Toxicological sciences*, 95(2), 427-435.
- Saide, A., Martínez, K. A., Ianora, A., & Lauritano, C. (2021). Unlocking the health potential of microalgae as sustainable sources of bioactive compounds. *International journal of molecular sciences*, 22(9), 4383.
- Salas, R., Tillmann, U., John, U., Kilcoyne, J., Burson, A., Cantwell, C., . . . Silke, J. (2011). The role of Azadinium spinosum (Dinophyceae) in the production of azaspiracid shellfish poisoning in mussels. *Harmful algae*, 10(6), 774-783.
- Seumen, C. H., Grimm, T. M., & Hauck, C. R. (2021). Protein phosphatases in TLR signaling. *Cell Communication and Signaling*, 19(1), 1-18.
- Sonoda, Y., Kasahara, T., Yamaguchi, Y., Kuno, K., Matsushima, K., & Mukaida, N. (1997). Stimulation of interleukin-8 production by okadaic acid and vanadate in a human promyelocyte cell line, an HL-60 subline: possible role of mitogen-activated protein kinase on the okadaic acid-induced NF- κ B activation. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 272(24), 15366-15372.

- Sudarsanam, S., Virca, G. D., March, C. J., & Srinivasan, S. (1992). An approach to computer-aided inhibitor design: application to cathepsin L. *Journal of Computer-Aided Molecular Design*, 6(3), 223-233.
- Tobío, A., Alfonso, A., Madera-Salcedo, I., Botana, L. M., & Blank, U. (2016). Yessotoxin, a marine toxin, exhibits anti-allergic and anti-tumoural activities inhibiting melanoma tumour growth in a preclinical model. *PLoS One*, 11(12), e0167572.
- Tobío, A., Fernández-Araujo, A., Alfonso, A., & Botana, L. M. (2012). Role of yessotoxin in calcium and cAMP-crosstalks in primary and K-562 human lymphocytes: The effect is mediated by Anchor kinase a mitochondrial proteins. *Journal of Cellular Biochemistry*, 113(12), 3752-3761.
- Twiner, M. J., Doucette, G. J., Rasky, A., Huang, X.-P., Roth, B. L., & Sanguinetti, M. C. (2012). Marine algal toxin azaspiracid is an open-state blocker of hERG potassium channels. *Chemical research in toxicology*, 25(9), 1975-1984.
- Valdiglesias, V., Prego-Faraldo, M. V., Pásaro, E., Méndez, J., & Laffon, B. (2013). Okadaic acid: more than a diarrheic toxin. *Marine drugs*, 11(11), 4328-4349.
- Visciano, P., Schirone, M., Berti, M., Milandri, A., Tofalo, R., & Suzzi, G. (2016). Marine biotoxins: occurrence, toxicity, regulatory limits and reference methods. *Frontiers in microbiology*, 7, 1051.
- Walsh, C. J., Leggett, S. R., Henry, M. S., Blum, P. C., Osborn, S., & Pierce, R. H. (2009). Cellular metabolism of brevetoxin (PbTx-2) by a monocyte cell line (U-937). *Toxicon*, 53(1), 135-145.

Table NT1. Initial categorization and search of DNT MIEs, KEs and AOs with no EMs described in the AOPwiki

		Event	Description	Potential Effect Biomarkers
<i>Molecular Interactions</i>	Thyroid System Disruption	MIE 1656	Thyroid Receptor Antagonism	T3, T4 levels; TSH levels
		MIE 279	Thyroperoxidase Inhibition	Thyroglobulin antibodies; TPO antibodies
	Neurotransmitter System Disruption	MIE 424	Inhibition of Na ⁺ /I ⁻ -symporter (NIS)	Iodide uptake tests
		MIE 201	Binding of antagonist to NMDA receptors	Glutamate levels; NMDAR expression
	Receptor Activation/Inhibition	MIE 239	Activation of Pregnane-X receptor, NR1I2	PXR levels; CYP3A4 expression
<i>Cellular Responses</i>		MIE 2023	Inhibition of Ceramide Synthase	Ceramide levels; Sphingosine levels
	Synaptic Function and Plasticity	KE 52	Decreased Calcium influx	Intracellular Ca ²⁺ concentration; Voltage-gated calcium channel expression
		KE 195	Inhibition of NMDARs	NMDAR expression; Postsynaptic density proteins
		KE 385	Decrease of synaptogenesis	Synapsin I/II levels; PSD-95 levels
		KE 383	Reduced Presynaptic release of glutamate	Vesicular glutamate transporter expression
	Neurotrophin Signaling	KE 381	Reduced levels of BDNF	BDNF levels; TrkB receptor expression
	Lipid Metabolism and Transport	KE 2024	Reduced complex sphingolipids	Sphingomyelin levels; GM1 ganglioside levels
		KE 2033	Increased sphingolipid-1-phosphate	S1P levels; Sphingosine kinase activity
		KE 2025	Affected folate transporter	Folate plasma levels; Folate receptor expression
		KE 2026	Decreased folate uptake	Homocysteine levels; Cellular folate levels
<i>Tissue and System Level Changes</i>	Brain Function Alterations	KE 2022	Altered function of the brain	EEG patterns; Cognitive tests
	Metabolic Processes	KE 295	Upregulation of glucuronyltransferase activity	Bilirubin levels; UGT1A1 enzyme activity
<i>Adverse Developmental Outcomes</i>	Structural Defects and Functional Impairment	AO 1561	Neural tube defects	Ultrasound imaging; AFP levels in amniotic fluid
		AO 319	Loss of Cochlear function	Audiometry tests; Otoacoustic emissions

Table NT2. Initial categorization and search of ANT MIEs, KEs and AOs with no EMs described in the AOPwiki

		Event	Description	Potential Effect Biomarkers
<i>Molecular Interactions</i>	Ion Channel Disruption	MIE 51	Inhibition, Ca ⁺⁺ ATPase	Intracellular Ca ²⁺ levels, ATPase activity
	Receptor Dysregulation	MIE 2039	Inhibition GABA _A receptor	GABA receptor function, chloride influx assays
		MIE 2036	Activation of metabotropic glutamate receptor	mGluR activity, downstream signaling
		MIE 388	Overactivation, NMDARs	NMDAR activity, calcium imaging
Metabolic Inhibition	MIE 1260	Direct mitochondrial inhibition	Mitochondrial respiration assays, ATP levels	
	MIE 1686	Deposition of Energy	Energy metabolism markers, ADP/ATP ratio	
Cellular Compartment Disruption	MIE 1258	Decompartmentalization	Membrane integrity assays, cytosolic enzyme levels	
Cellular Responses	Synaptic Function	KE 2078	Loss of drebrin	Synaptic plasticity assays, drebrin levels
		KE 1944	Synaptic dysfunction	Synaptic vesicle assays, synaptic protein expression
	Neuronal Integrity	KE 1261	Mitochondrial impairment	Mitochondrial enzyme assays, electron transport chain function
		KE 50	Increase, Ca ⁺⁺ (intracellular)	Intracellular calcium concentrations, calpain activity
		KE 1527	Increase, Cell membrane depolarization	Electrophysiological assays, ion channel function
	Cellular Stress	KE 2017	Endoplasmic reticulum stress	ER stress markers, unfolded protein response
		KE 2038	Activation of calpain signalling	Calpain activity assays, calpain substrate cleavage
	Oxidative Stress	KE 257	Increase, Reactive Oxygen Species production	ROS assays, antioxidant capacity

Tissue/System Level Changes	Nitric Oxide Signaling	KE 193	Decreased, Nitric Oxide	NO production assays, nitric oxide synthase activity
	Protein Aggregation	KE 1942	Accumulation, Cytosolic toxic Tau oligomers	Tau aggregation assays, tau imaging
		KE 1943	Hyperphosphorylation of Tau	Phospho-tau assays, Western blot
Adverse Outcomes	Neuronal Transport	KE 1582	Impaired axonal transport	Axonal flow rates, imaging of dynein/kinesin function
	Neurodegeneration	AO 1263	Necrosis	Cell death markers, lactate dehydrogenase activity
	Oxidative Damage	AO 356	Increased, Oxidative damage	Lipid peroxidation assays, DNA oxidation markers
	Sensory Function	AO 1873	Impaired olfactory function (anosmia)	Olfactory threshold tests, olfactory bulb imaging
	Cognitive Impairment	AO 1941	Memory Loss	Cognitive tests, neuroimaging for memory-related activity